

**The Raven Hydrological Modelling Framework -
Simulating Runoff in a Swiss context**

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Abstract

In hydrological modelling, hypothesis testing is a strategy to systematically assess the usefulness of representations of reality. Modular modelling frameworks allow the efficient development of models from building blocks. The Raven modelling framework offers to examine the influence of changing process representations, numerical algorithms, parametrization, spatial and temporal discretization and forcing data. In this thesis, the five conceptual models GR4J, HBV, HMETS, HYMOD and MOHYSE are emulated in Raven to generate runoff simulations for eleven Swiss catchments. For pre-processing and input file generation, the Python library Raven-Tools is developed and published. Parameters are optimized with a split-sample calibration/validation scheme with 40 years of total data. For each catchment and model, 20 optimization trials are run with different random seeds and the result with the highest non-parametric Kling-Gupta Efficiency ($KG E_{np}$) in the calibration period is selected for further analysis. Using $KG E_{np}$ as performance metric emphasizes three parts of the hydrographs during optimization: Volume, variability and dynamics. The results indicate HBV's strong performance and robustness of its results over both periods. GR4J showed a tendency to overemphasize ascents and descents. HYMOD exhibits a trend to lag behind observations. Furthermore, the analysis of $KG E_{np}$'s components provides valuable insights. It is concluded that Raven is a powerful tool that is expected to contribute to increased understanding about hydrologic process representation through hypothesis testing.

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List of Abbreviations

α	Variability component of KGE_{np}
β	Volume component of KGE_{np}
KGE_{np}	non-parametric Kling-Gupta Efficiency
R_s	Dynamics component of KGE_{np}
AMSI	Automatic Model Structure Identification
DDF	Degree Day Factor; used in degree day method
DDS	Dynamically Dimensioned Search
DECIPHr	Dynamic fluxEs and ConnectIvity for Predictions of HydRology
ECHSE	Eco-Hydrological Simulation Environment
ET	Evapotranspiration
Flex	Flux Exchange
GR4J	Modèle du Génie Rural à 4 paramètres Journalier
HBV	Hydrologiska Byrans Vattenbalansavdelning
HMETS	Hydrological Model of École de technologie supérieure
HRU	Hydrological Response Unit
HYMOD	Hydrologic Model
KGE	Kling-Gupta Efficiency
MARRMoT	Modular Assessment of Rainfall-Runoff Models Toolbox
MMF	Modular Modelling Framework
MOHYSE	MOdèle HYdrologique Simplifié à l'Extrême
MOPEX	Model Parameter Estimation Experiment
NSE	Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency
ODE	Ordinary Differential Equation
OSTRICH	Optimization Software Toolkit for Research Involving Computational Heuristics
PB	Percent Bias
PDE	Partial Differential Equation
PDM	Probability Distributed Model
PET	Potential Evapotranspiration
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
SAR	Snow Accounting Routine
SCE	Shuffled Complex Evolution
SUMMA	Structure for Unifying Multiple Modelling Alternatives
SWE	Snow Water Equivalent
UH	Unit Hydrograph
VE	Volumetric Efficiency

1 Introduction

Environmental modelling is done for a number of reasons, such as to increase knowledge on the functioning of natural systems and to be able to make predictions about their behaviour (Beven, 1989; Clark, Kavetski *et al.* 2011). In hydrology, modellers want to understand how catchments behave when water and its constituents moves towards the outlet (Fenicia, Savenije *et al.* 2008). Because reality is too complex to be perfectly replicated and understanding about environmental systems is incomplete, models use simplifications and general assumptions (Beven, 2002a; Clark, Schaeffli *et al.* 2016; Gharari *et al.* 2021). Several strategies exist to develop a model: Physically-based try to mimic real physical processes as they are understood and measured (Freeze and Harlan, 1969; Simmons *et al.* 2019). Conceptual models aim to reproduce the results with general assumptions about the functioning of hydrologic processes, as perceived by a modeller (Beven, 2002b; Beven, 2002a; Refsgaard and Henriksen, 2004). They are frequently employed to represent proxies for physical processes with parameters that can be calibrated (Refsgaard and Henriksen, 2004). Furthermore, conceptual models are frequently used to test alternative hypotheses about the adequate representation of hydrologic processes (Clark, Kavetski *et al.* 2011), the production of good results efficiently without the extensive need for data that physical models have or doing analysis on catchments where data is scarce (Clark, Nijssen *et al.* 2015). Aggregations can include the *temporal*, *spatial* (Kavetski *et al.* 2011; Mai, Craig, Tolson and Arsenault, 2022) or *functional* (Gharari *et al.* 2021) dimensions.

Models can be seen as hypotheses about the representation of reality. This allows for a systematic approach towards the identification of useful models in a given situation (Beven, 2006; Clark, Kavetski *et al.* 2011). Moreover, some models will perform better for some hydrologic processes, while underperforming for others. Therefore, a hypothesis can be understood as containing multiple sub-hypotheses, e.g. about the representation of a hydrologic process, each of whose performance can be assessed individually. Such a „constituent hypothesis“ is a claim that the investigated representation of a hydrologic process is sufficiently able to mimic reality (Clark, Kavetski *et al.* 2011, p. 3). Thus, it becomes possible to examine which part of a model led to its acceptance or rejection. Additionally, in case of rejected constituent hypotheses, a modeller could replace the corresponding process implementation with a more suitable one. Using performance metrics, it is possible to define thresholds of accepting or rejecting such a hypothesis (Clark, Kavetski *et al.* 2011). Moreover, in the case of multiple models being accepted, modellers could decide to use the best-performing one or accept that multiple models are more or less equally capable of representing observed streamflows (Beven, 2006).

When comparing the results of multiple models, more than one might be acceptable, depending on the performance metrics used and the acceptability criteria, a concept called *equifinality* (Beven, 2000; Beven, 2006). Satisfactory solutions are *behavioural*; they are distinguished from *non-behavioural* ones, which are rejected (Efstratiadis and Koutsoyiannis, 2010). Equifinality can be arrived at through multiple paths, e.g. with different „model inputs, model structures, model parameters sets, [and] model errors“ (Beven, 2006, p. 25), though the origin of the phenomenon lies in uncertainty (Beven, 2006; Efstratiadis and Koutsoyiannis, 2010). There are multiple ways in which equifinality can be taken into consideration when modelling: In order to identify parameter sets which lead to similar performances, a multi-objective calibration approach can help identify acceptable parameter sets. Efstratiadis and Koutsoyiannis (2010) distinguish two types of multi-objective calibration: Pareto-approaches and aggregated performance metrics that are calculated using several subcomponents. In Pareto-approaches, calibration is carried out with multiple objectives and solutions are grouped into *dominated* and *non-dominated*. Dominated solutions lie on the Pareto front, which marks acceptable solutions. This strategy has the advantage that modellers can investigate trade-offs between objectives and perhaps use this information to improve the model (Vrugt, Diks *et al.* 2005; Efstratiadis and Koutsoyiannis, 2010). Although they emphasize that single-objective calibration is less suited than multi-objective approaches, even for models with only a few parameters, Efstratiadis and Koutsoyiannis (2010) also acknowledge that finding solutions on the Pareto front which are non-dominated for multiple control periods was inefficient. Moreover, they conclude that a Pareto-based approach requires such an amount of computational resources, that this task was „impossible“ with „reasonable effort“ (Efstratiadis and Koutsoyiannis, 2010, p. 74). A possible alternative are aggregated performance metrics,

which include components that target different types of simulation quality, such as peak flow, or variability. Therefore, they aggregate different sub-objectives into a single measure, although Efstratiadis and Koutsoyiannis (2010) note that information on trade-offs between sub-criteria is lost, compared to a Pareto-approach.

Conceptual models are developed making assumptions on how hydrologic processes in a catchment lead from precipitation to runoff. Modellers decide on the extent to which they want to simplify complex reality into a model. Therefore, parameters in conceptual models often represent a specific characteristic of the catchment or the hydrologic processes. Although they may have physically-informed parts, their parameters are usually chosen so that model simulations fit observations as well as possible. Future runoff predictions may lack confidence, since the underlying assumptions on the functioning of processes or catchment characteristics may change (Clark, Nijssen *et al.* 2015). Having been in use for nearly half a century, HBV is one of the more established conceptual models. It was introduced by Bergström (1976) and has experienced several adaptations, leading to multiple versions being in use today (Bergström, 1992; Moore, 1993; Lindström *et al.* 1997; Seibert, 1997; Seibert, 2005; Seibert and Bergström, 2022). The GR4J model only has four parameters, making it extremely parsimonious (Perrin *et al.* 2003). In combination with Cemaneige, it can also carry out snow accounting (Valéry, 2010; Valéry, Andréassian *et al.* 2014a; Valéry, Andréassian *et al.* 2014b). Its simplicity and good performance both contribute to its popularity (Troin, Arsenault and Brissette, 2015; Roy, Gupta *et al.* 2017; Arsenault, Gatién *et al.* 2015; Arsenault, Brissette *et al.* 2018; Shen, Tolson *et al.* 2022; Mai, 2023b). In contrast, HMETs dedicates ten parameters alone to snow accounting (Martel *et al.* 2017). Since its original publication, it has been used in a number of studies (Roy, Gupta *et al.* 2017; Arsenault, Brissette *et al.* 2018; Arsenault, Breton-Dufour *et al.* 2019; Hamaoui, 2019; Tarek *et al.* 2020; Shen, Tolson *et al.* 2022). HYMOD, on the other hand, which was built on the probability-distributed principle, does not include a snow routine (Moore, 1985; Wagener, Boyle *et al.* 2001; Moore, 2007). It, too, has been applied in a range of studies (Bastola and Murphy, 2013; Parra *et al.* 2018; Wang and Solomatine, 2019; Bastola, 2022). Finally, MOHYSE was designed to teach hydrological modelling (Fortin and Turcotte, 2007). However, it also proved to be popular outside of education (Roy, Royer *et al.* 2010; Turcotte *et al.* 2010; Ibarra Zavaleta *et al.* 2015; Troin, Arsenault and Brissette, 2015; Castaneda-Gonzalez *et al.* 2019). This list is by no means exhaustive. The models mentioned above, however, exemplify the broad range of intentions developers may have in mind during the model creation process. While some may put more focus on snow accounting, others could have a vision of a toolbox in mind that allows them to educate their students about hydrological modelling.

In order to facilitate the exchange of model components, e.g. to test alternative hypotheses, a number of modular modelling frameworks (MMF) have been developed. They allow the easy composition of hydrological models from building blocks, either to emulate existing models or to create new ones. Hence, hydrologic process implementations can be exchanged. When using open-source code, users can extend functionality in case of missing features (Clark, Kavetski *et al.* 2011; Fenicia, Kavetski *et al.* 2011; Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020). Clark, Kavetski *et al.* (2011, p. 2) use the term „multiple-hypothesis framework“ as a way of hypothesis testing. Clark, Slater *et al.* (2008) introduced the *Framework for Understanding Structural Errors (FUSE)* to create 79 model structures and to assess their respective performances simulating runoff in two catchments of the Model Parameter Estimation Experiment (MOPEX). SUPERFLEX was developed to facilitate “mix and matching” of building blocks (Fenicia, Kavetski *et al.* 2011, p. 3) as a continuation of the *Flux Exchange (FLEX)* hydrological model (Fenicia, Savenije *et al.* 2006), while the *Eco-Hydrological Simulation Environment (ECHSE)* was born out of the realization that „at a certain level of abstraction, the specific model engines [...] were actually identical“ (Kneis, 2015, p. 112). Streamlining model creation in a single framework, it is argued, could save time. The *Structure for Unifying Multiple Modelling Alternatives (SUMMA)*, on the other hand, was specifically designed to allow hypothesis testing (Clark, Nijssen *et al.* 2015), a stated aim also of Coxon *et al.* 2019 who published the modelling framework *Dynamic fluxEs and Connectivity for Predictions of Hydrology (DECIPHeR)*. They note the framework was best performing in the western and northern parts of the UK with its comparatively wetter catchments. The *Modular Assessment of Rainfall-Runoff Models Toolbox (MARRMoT)* by Knoben *et al.* (2019a) allows modellers to pick and choose elements of 46 conceptual models, while *Raven* offers the options to distribute parameters,

vary them with time or blend individual process representations (Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020). Finally, *SuperflexPy* was published as a Python package with explicit simplicity of use in mind during development (Dal Molin, Kavetski and Fenicia, 2021). This list is by no means exhaustive. Many more frameworks exist or are currently in development.

The Raven modelling framework has been used in a number of applications, utilizing both its ability to emulate other hydrological models and building new ones from modules representing hydrologic processes. In order to assess model structural adequacy as proposed by Gupta, Clark *et al.* (2012) and others, Mai, Craig and Tolson (2020) blended different process options in Raven using weighted averages for a Canadian catchment plus benchmark models. While their focus was on conducting a sensitivity analysis of process options, Chlumsky, Mai *et al.* (2021b) employed Raven to calibrate both model structure and parameters of 12 Canadian catchments. In this case, weighted representation of structures is shown to be computationally more efficient than calibrating the 108 individual fixed model structures. Their results express high Nash-Sutcliffe (NSE) values. Both the results of Mai, Craig and Tolson (2020) and those of Chlumsky, Mai *et al.* (2021b) can be used to identify processes that contribute most to uncertainty. Similarly, Spieler *et al.* (2020) utilize Raven's capability to assemble models modularly by flexibly choosing process representations; not being bound by predefined fixed model structures allows identifying one, which is best suited to mimic the desired hydrographs. Raven in routing-only mode was applied by Han, Mai *et al.* (2020) on a Canadian drainage basin, using the diffusive wave method. Thus, they are able to show that removing lakes from the setup has a negative effect on model performance. Furthermore, the study validates the quality of a Canadian lake-river routing product developed by the authors.

1.1 Research gaps

Horton, Schaepli and Kauzlaric (2022) compiled a list of streamflow simulations that have been carried out in Switzerland over the last two decades. An excerpt thereof is shown in Table 1, listing only those catchments that are used in this thesis. It shows that the Broye, Dischmabach, Thur and Ticino catchments feature relatively often, while the Venoge is present only in one of the mentioned studies. Furthermore, there are a number of physically-based models used, such as the WaSiM-ETH or Alpine3D. Of the five conceptual models GR4J, HBV, HMETS, HYMOD and MOHYSE, only HBV and HYMOD are known to have been used on any of the eleven investigated catchments. As has been argued above, MMFs are a promising tool for hypothesis testing. Furthermore, they can be employed to examine how different models or process representations can lead to equifinal solutions. One of these MMFs – *Raven* – offers a range of process algorithms to pick and choose from. Alternatively, several conceptual models can be emulated. Raven, to the best of the author's knowledge, has not been previously used in a comparison of conceptual models in Switzerland. Furthermore, a modelling study comparing GR4J, HBV, HMETS, HYMOD and MOHYSE in any Swiss context has, to the best of the author's knowledge, never been carried out.

1.2 Study Goal

The present thesis aims to optimize parameters of the five conceptual models GR4J, HBV, HMETS, HYMOD and MOHYSE for the eleven Swiss catchments Broye, Dischmabach, Lonza, Massa, Rhône, Saltina, Sitter, Thur, Ticino, Venoge and Weisse Lütschine using the Raven hydrological modelling framework. To facilitate data pre-processing, Raven input file generation and analysis of the results, a Python library *Raven-Tools* is developed. With the optimal parameter sets, the models are run to create runoff simulations, whose performance shall be compared using a number of metrics.

Table 1: Existing streamflow simulations with references. Only catchments modelled in this thesis are listed.

Source	Catchment	Model
Jasper, Gurtz <i>et al.</i> (2002)	Ticino	WaSiM-ETH
Gurtz <i>et al.</i> (2003)	Dischmabach	WaSiM-ETH, PREVAH
Jasper, Calanca, Gyalistras <i>et al.</i> (2004)	Ticino, Thur	WaSiM-ETH
Zierl and Bugmann (2005)	Dischmabach, Saltina	RHESSys
Horton, Schaefli, Mezghani <i>et al.</i> (2006)	Dischmabach, Lonza, Rhône Weisse Lütschine	GSM-SOCONT
Jasper, Calanca and Fuhrer (2006)	Thur	WaSiM-ETH
Abbaspour <i>et al.</i> (2007)	Thur	SWAT
Zappa and Kan (2007)	Thur, Rhône	PREVAH
Bavay <i>et al.</i> (2009)	Dischmabach	ALPINE3D
Schaefli and Zehe (2009)	Rhône	GSM-SOCONT
Rößler and Löffler (2010)	Lonza	WaSiM-ETH
Fundel and Zappa (2011)	Thur	PREVAH
Fuhrer and Jasper (2012)	Broye, Dischmabach, Rhône Ticino, Thur	WaSiM-ETH
Rössler, Dieckkrüger <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Lonza	WaSiM-ETH
Fundel and Zappa (2011)	Thur	PREVAH
Rahman <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Rhône	SWAT
Addor <i>et al.</i> 2014	Thur, Venoge	HBV, PREVAH, WaSiM-ETH
Rössler, Froidevaux <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Lonza	WaSiM-ETH
Staudinger, Weiler <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Broye, Sitter, Dischmabach	HBV
Viviroli and Seibert (2015)	Broye, Dischmabach, Thur Sitter, Weisse Lütschine	PREVAH
Girons Lopez and Seibert (2016)	Thur, Sitter	HBV
Griessinger <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Broye, Dischmabach	HBV
Melsen <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Thur	VIC
Schaefli (2016)	Dischmabach	SEHR-ECHO
Staudinger, Stoelzle <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Dischmabach, Sitter	HBV
Wever <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Dischmabach	ALPINE3D
Brunner, Sikorska <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Broye	HBV
Hakala <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Dischmabach, Sitter	HBV
Jenicek <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Dischmabach, Sitter	HBV
Zarrineh, Abbaspour, Van Griensven <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Broye	SWAT
Brunner, Farinotti <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Entire Switzerland	PREVAH
Müller-Thomy and Sikorska-Senoner (2019)	Weisse Lütschine	HBV
Dal Molin, Schirmer <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Thur, Sitter	General Model
Zarrineh, Abbaspour and Holzkämper (2020)	Broye	SWAT
Dal Molin, Kavetski, Albert <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Thur, Sitter	HYMOD (snow reservoir added)

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Conceptual Model Structures

Five conceptual hydrological models, GR4J, HBV, HMETs, HYMOD and MOHYSE are used to create hydrographs for each catchment. The following sections briefly outline each conceptual model's history, basic structure, routines to account for snow and, if present, glaciers and finally provide an overview of studies comparing performances. Preceding this, however, it might be of value to define a few of the terms used throughout the remainder of this thesis.

2.1.1 Terminology

As mentioned above, the goal of a *conceptual model* is to describe reality by simplifying it to those processes which the developer deems most important. It is not built to replicate physical processes exactly with those mathematical equations describing them in the physically most consistent way; rather, a conceptual model is created to serve a specific purpose (Refsgaard and Henriksen, 2004), e.g. producing acceptable hydrographs or deepen understanding of hydrologic processes. Moreover, a *model* in this thesis is defined as unique for each catchment. Thus, the combination of input data and the set of parameters chosen are unique for each model. This definition follows the suggestions of Refsgaard and Henriksen (2004). The processes of *calibration* and *validation* hence are also meaningful only for a single model; they have to be carried out for each of them. There have been valuable contributions to the definition of the term *validation* and possible advantages of using *evaluation* instead (Wagener, Reinecke *et al.* 2022). The authors point out that the underlying assumption of model *validation* was the existence of a model being capable of fully representing reality. Instead, they suggest to focus on an *evaluation* of a model's adequacy to represent reality. Currently, however, *validation* is used by most studies (Mai, 2023b). Acknowledging the points highlighted by Refsgaard, Stisen *et al.* (2022), *validation* is nonetheless utilized in the present thesis in order to be consistent with most research literature on the topic currently published. By comparing *performance criteria* of the models, their ability to represent reality is judged (Refsgaard and Henriksen, 2004). For brevity, the combination of conceptual model and corresponding setup in a specific catchment may sometimes be mentioned as '*Conceptual Model/Catchment*' within this thesis, i.e. the setup of HYMOD in the Venoge catchment would be called HYMOD/Venoge.

2.1.2 GR4J

The version of the *modèle du Génie Rural à 4 paramètres Journalier (GR4J)* used in Raven was developed by Perrin (2000) and presented in Perrin *et al.* (2003) as an improvement to the GR3J model, first outlined by Edijatno and Michel (1989). The aim was to produce hydrographs with a daily temporal resolution that are „satisfactory“ (Perrin *et al.* 2003, p. 285).

GR4J is a lumped model with 4 parameters, which consists of two conceptual stores, a *production* and a *routing* store. Furthermore, two unit hydrographs delay precipitation to runoff; one routing to the routing store, the other to runoff. Perrin *et al.* (2003) note that the relatively low number of parameters was in part achieved by setting fixed numbers, where other models have free parameters. One example in GR4J is a fixed split ratio that divides water into the two unit hydrographs.

GR4J does not include snow accounting, though routines of *Cemaneige*, developed by Valéry (2010) and further described by Valéry, Andréassian *et al.* (2014a), can be coupled to GR4J, increasing the number of parameters to 6. Valéry, Andréassian *et al.* (2014a) compare multiple snow accounting routines (SAR), using HBV and GR4J, as well as doing a sensitivity analysis of *Cemaneige* (Valéry, Andréassian *et al.* 2014b). Coupling GR4J with *Cemaneige*, Valéry (2010) notes, outperforms GR4J coupled with MOHYSE's SAR or coupled with that of HBV. Coupling HBV with its own SAR, however, gives mixed results compared to HBV with *Cemaneige*. This is explained by HBV's snow correction factor. Although *Cemaneige* performs slightly better in semi-distributed mode, running it in lumped mode is also possible (Valéry, Andréassian *et al.* 2014b). Algorithms to account for glaciers are not included in GR4J (Perrin *et al.* 2003).

Perrin *et al.* (2003) compare GR4J to 19 other models over 429 catchments, using five efficiency metrics. They point out that GR4J's „results are statistically among the best“, compared with similar models (Perrin *et al.* 2003, p. 287). Pagano *et al.* (2010) recommend GR4J for „future modelling experiments“, highlighting it as the „model of choice“ (Pagano *et al.* 2010, p. 66).

Pushpalatha *et al.* (2011) propose GR6J, an improved version of GR5J and compare its performance to GR4J, HBV0, MOHYSE and others. While their GR6J outperforms all of them, it is noteworthy that GR4J scores high as well. MOHYSE and HBV0, on the other hand, both have mixed results. Pushpalatha (2012) compares and reviews performance metrics, focussing on low flows with GR4J and MORD. In order to evaluate generalist parameter sets, Andréassian *et al.* (2014) use GR4J and a set of 27 parameters and hence omit calibration. Weighing and combining models to produce a single hydrograph can be done with several approaches, some of which are evaluated by Arsenault, Gatien *et al.* (2015) using HMETS, MOHYSE and GR4J-CN, among others. Examining snow models in a Canadian catchment, Troin, Arsenault and Brissette (2015) detail the larger uncertainty of simulations produced by GR4J, compared to HMETS and MOHYSE, a finding confirmed by Troin, Arsenault, Martel *et al.* (2018) in their uncertainty assessment for model components in climate change simulations employing the same three models. They furthermore underline GR4J's underestimation of spring peak flow magnitudes, a shortcoming not shared with HMETS and MOHYSE in that study. Arsenault, Brissette *et al.* (2018) stress the need for calibration periods to be as long as possible, using GR4J-CN and HMETS. Both models are also utilized by Shen, Tolson *et al.* (2022) to argue for an update to the split-sample approach.

Raven 3.5 can emulate GR4J and template files are provided (Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020; Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b; Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023a). It is coupled with Cemaneige in this thesis. Table 2 provides an overview of the parameters, as well their ranges used in the optimization. As was done by Mai (2023b), an additional parameter AVG_ANNUAL_SNOW is used in the Raven input files, representing average annual snow as snow water equivalent (SWE), measured in millimetres. While Mai (2023b, Table A.2) uses [1.0, 30.0] as lower and upper parameter limits in the optimization, in the present thesis, the recommendations of Craig and the Raven Development Team (2023b) were followed, so as not to confine the parameter too much (see Table 2).

Table 2: GR4J model parameters with range. AVG_ANNUAL_SNOW has been added as recommended by Mai (2023b). Sources: [1] Perrin *et al.* (2003); [2] eWater Ltd (2020); [3] Pagano *et al.* (2010); [4] Poncelet (2018, file CemaNeige.py); [5] Craig and the Raven Development Team (2023b).

Parameter	Description	Range	Sources
x_1	Maximum capacity of production store	0.1 – 1.2 m	1,2,3
x_2	Groundwater exchange coefficient	-5 – 3 mm	1,2,3
x_3	One day ahead maximum capacity of the routing store	1 – 500 mm	1,2,3
x_4	Time base of unit hydrograph UH1	0.5 – 4 d	1,2,3
Cémaneige x_1	Air-snow coefficient	0 – 1	4
Cémaneige x_2	Melt Factor	3.5	5
AVG_ANNUAL_SNOW	Average annual snow as SWE	0 – 100 mm	4

2.1.3 HBV

The *Hydrologiska Byråns Vattenbalansavdelning model (HBV)* was originally developed by Bergström (1976), who presented different versions of it, HBV-1 to HBV-4. HBV has constantly been improved and adapted since. It was developed with the aim of conducting operational hydrological forecasts in Swedish catchments (Bergström, 1992), while not being overly complex. Lindström *et al.* (1997) created a distributed version, HBV-96. Although not present in the original version by Bergström (1976), modifications have been published to include glaciers. Moore (1993) contributed a set of equations to simulate glacial storage and release, creating a version of HBV upon which Environment Canada's (EC) version HBV-EC was built (Canadian Hydraulics Centre, National Research Council, 2008). HBV-EC is adapted to Canadian settings (Moore, 1993) and it is semi-distributed, using elevation zones (see also Hamilton *et al.* 2000). The model is included in the EnSim hydrologic software suite (Canadian Hydraulics Centre, National Research Council, 2008). Finally, Seibert (1997) published a *light* version with a graphical user interface aimed at teaching hydrological modelling. Raven is able to emulate HBV-EC (Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020) and HBV *light* (from version 2.9.1) (Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b). HBV-EC is the only one of the five models tested in this study that explicitly includes algorithms to deal with glacial freezing, melt and release.

Sten Bergström structured HBV into three components containing specific subroutines: 1. snow accounting, 2. soil moisture accounting and 3. response and river routing (Bergström, 1976; Bergström, 1992). HBV-EC is semi-distributed, making use of elevation bands. Moore (1993)'s adaptation of Bergström (1976)'s version is structurally similar, except for an added fourth component that models glaciers. Water is routed through a set of reservoirs, whose configuration Moore (1993) adapted from HBV-3. Water which has not percolated through the soil to runoff is stored up to field capacity. Outflow from glacial storage and the linear reservoirs are added to constitute the total runoff.

HBV includes its own SAR, which is carried out in each elevation band. To determine partitioning of rain/snow in the precipitation, Raven includes a process option that is a linear transition based on the average daily temperature (Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b). This corresponds with Bergström (1976)'s highlight that the threshold value may be variable within a certain range. A snowfall correction factor modifies snow accumulation. Furthermore, snow melt is calculated using a degree day approach. HBV's method, as it is implemented in Raven, additionally corrects for forest cover, slope, aspect and the solar angle (Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b; Canadian Hydraulics Centre, National Research Council, 2008). Modifying the melt factor according to land use and topographical parameters has also been outlined in Moore (1993)'s introduction of HBV-EC. Glacial melt is calculated by the same degree day method, but multiplied with a factor greater than one to simulate albedo differences between snow and ice. Meltwater is retained in a glacial storage reservoir, whose outflow is governed by a set of algorithms that simulate seasonal and inter-annual patterns of meltwater runoff (Moore, 1993).

Moore (1993, p. 163) tests HBV-EC in a glaciated Canadian context and reports an „encouraging“ model performance with NSE values around 0.8. He points out, however, an underestimation of August flows and total runoff, attributing this to a fixed temperature lapse rate, leading to classification of rain as snow. In a comparison with HYMOD, Parra *et al.* (2018) identify HBV to be more suitable on a daily scale than HYMOD. They highlight HBV's better ability to simulate quick runoff responses. HYMOD, they note, outperforms HBV for low streamflow, on the other hand. Müller-Thomy and Sikorska-Senoner (2019) use HBV in lumped mode to assess two disaggregation methods of precipitation in the Weisse Lüttschine and other catchments. For an overview of more studies using HBV in Swiss catchments, see Table 1.

A summary of HBV's parameters and their ranges is given in Table 3. Template files for Raven are provided (Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020; Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b; Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023a). Due to a bug in the pre-processing of the elevation bands, HBV-EC in this thesis was run with the same spatial discretization as the other models, that is with an HRU for the non-glaciated part and, if present in the respective catchment, one for the glaciated part. Instead of calculating potential evapotranspiration during pre-processing, Raven's capabilities were utilized with the PET_HAMON algorithm (Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b). This method was chosen for consistency with as great a number of other models in this study (see Table 7).

2.1.4 HMETS

The *Hydrological Model of École de technologie supérieure (HMETS)* was put forward by Martel *et al.* (2017). Although usage of HMETS prior to 2017 is mentioned by Martel *et al.* (see for example Chen *et al.* (2011) and Arsenault, Gatién *et al.* (2015)), its structure was first outlined by Martel *et al.* (2017). Their stated goal was to develop a conceptual model that could easily be used as an educational tool. Students should thus be able to understand how hydrological modelling works. Nonetheless, their expectation for was for HMETS to produce useful results. The Matlab code has been open-sourced (Francois Brissette, 2023).

The model is lumped, has 21 parameters and requires little data: precipitation and temperature (minimal and maximal); additionally, discharge observations. The snow routines included are modelled with 10 parameters, dedicating a comparatively large number to this part of the model. Evapotranspiration is based on Oudin *et al.* (2005)'s method, which depends on the date, location and daily mean temperature. Runoff at the outlet consists of four parts: surface runoff, delayed

Table 3: HBV model parameters with range. Sources: [1] Bergström (1976); [2] Bergström (1992); [3] Lindström *et al.* (1997); [4] Knoben *et al.* (2019b); [5] Herman *et al.* (2013); [6] *Exercise 5* (2023); [7] Seibert (2005); [8] Craig and the Raven Development Team (2023b); [9] Gannon (2023); [10] Parra *et al.* (2018); [11] Wang and Solomatine (2019).

Parameter	Description	Range	Sources
T_0	Rain/Snow temperature	-3 – 3 °C	4,5,6,9,10
C_{melt}	Melt factor	1 – 10 mm °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹	1,2,3,5,6,8,9,10
C_{refr}	Refreezing Factor	0 – 3.5 mm °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹	3,6,7,8
C_{wh}	Water holding capacity of snow fraction	0.04 – 0.07	3,6,8
$Porosity$	Porosity	0.1 – 0.6	8
F_c	Field capacity	0 – 1 m	1,2,3,5,6,9,10,11
β	Beta	0 – 7	1,2,3,5,6,8,9,10,11
$C_{perc,fast}$	Max. percolation rate fast reservoir	0.01 – 1000 mm d ⁻¹	1,2,3,5,6,8,9,10,11
K_0	Baseflow coefficient fast reservoir	0.01 – 0.6 d ⁻¹	1,2,3,5,6,8,9,10,11
K_1	Baseflow coefficient slow reservoir	0.01 – 0.6 d ⁻¹	1,2,11
B_{max}	Maxbas	1 – 3 d	1,2,3,5,6,8,9
PC_{alt}	Precipitation lapse factor	0 – 100 mm d ⁻¹ km ⁻¹	1,2,8
TC_{alt}	Adiabatic lapse factor	0 – 7 °C km ⁻¹	1,2,8
LP	Threshold for reduction of evaporation	0 – 0.9	1,2,3,5,6,8,9,10,11
α	$Baseflow_{N-1}$	0 – 9	1,2,3,11
C_{flux}	Maximum capillary rise rate	0.1 – 1 mm d ⁻¹	3,4,11
$Thickness_{Topsoil}$	Thickness topsoil	0.1 – 10 m	4,8
$C_{melt,forest}$	Snow melt forest correction	0.01 – 0.99	1,2,8
C_{glac}	Linear storage coeff. for glacial melt	0.1 – 2	1,2,8
C_{RF}	Rainfall correction factor	0.5 – 2	1,2,8
C_{SF}	Snowfall correction factor	0.4 – 1.2	1,2,8
$n_{Baseflow}$	Baseflow power value	1-10	3,8
$HBV_{TimeToPeak}$	Time to peak (used in Gamma UH)	$0.5 \times B_{max}$	8
$HBV_{InitialThicknessTopsoil}$	Initial Thickness Topsoil	$0.5 \times Thickness_{Topsoil}$	8

runoff, hypodermic flow and groundwater flow. Subsurface storage is modelled using two reservoirs: the *vadose* and *phreatic* zone, which produce hypodermic and groundwater flows. If at capacity, they contribute to delayed runoff. Both surface and delayed runoff are transformed by a unit hydrograph (UH) (Martel *et al.* 2017). The UHs have the shape of a gamma function.

SAR are based on a degree-day approach to simulate snowmelt and refreeze processes. They are structured into three steps: 1. Overnight refreezing in the snowpack occurs when a threshold temperature condition is met; 2. snowmelt is based on a degree day factor (DDF) model developed by Vehviläinen (1992), which varies with cumulative snowmelt; 3. snowpack water retention capacity is also dependent on cumulative snowmelt. By including cumulative snowmelt, Martel *et al.* (2017) wanted to simulate snowpack aging, which results in a lower surface albedo compared to fresh snow (Dingman, 2015).

In the original paper outlining HMETS, Martel *et al.* (2017) compare its performance to that of MOHYSE after running both on 320 US catchments, with 30 runs per catchment. They highlight that HMETS was „significantly“ better, with a median *NSE* of 0.72 over all catchments for the validation period, compared to 0.64 for MOHYSE (Martel *et al.* 2017, p. 1312). Although Martel *et al.* (2017) published their article on the model structure in the *International Journal of Engineering Education* with civil engineering students pointed out explicitly as their target users, HMETS has been employed in a number of studies outside the educational context, such as by Tarek *et al.* (2020) to evaluate an ERA5 reanalysis dataset. Assessing performance and uncertainty of snow models in a Canadian catchment, Troin, Arsenault and Brisette (2015, p. 313) note the similarity of HMETS’ and MOHYSE’s results in terms of „magnitude of variability“ and „direction of simulated discharges“. Shen, Chen *et al.* (2018) note that HMETS struggled to reproduce low flow variation when calibrated with *KGE*, but performed better when using *NSE*. GR4J’s reproduction of low flow was worse with either criterion. Shen, Tolson *et al.* (2022) use HMETS as a more complex alternative to GR4J in their comparison of a number of data splitting methods in model calibration and validation, citing the former model’s „robust performance“ (Shen, Tolson *et al.* 2022, p. 8). Advancing the *Automatic Model Structure Identification (AMSI)* method of Spieler *et al.* (2020), Chlumsky, Mai *et al.* (2021b) blend individual conceptual model process algorithms with weighted sums, an idea originally outlined by Mai, Craig and Tolson (2020). Chlumsky, Mai *et al.* (2021b, p. 9) stress „the quality of the [HMETS] model structure“. This method is further updated by Chlumsky, Mai *et al.* (2023), using GR4J, HBV and HMETS components.

HMETS is emulated in RAVEN. A set of default parameter ranges can be obtained from the source code, which is written in Matlab and is openly available on Mathworks (Francois Brissette, 2023). For parameters used in this thesis, see Table 4. HMETS does not prevent simulated discharge values from being below zero. Therefore, negative values produced by HMETS are assessed in this study and reported if they are deemed too significant. This is carried out qualitatively, i.e. not using a predefined fixed threshold for rejection. Furthermore, HMETS uses data to estimate rain/snow fractioning. This was replaced by the RAINSNOW_DINGMAN process option in Raven.

Table 4: HMETS model parameters with range. Sources: [1] Martel *et al.* (2017); [2] Francois Brissette, 2023; [3] Hamaoui (2019); [4] Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b.

Parameter	Description	Range	Sources
ddf_{min}	Minimum ddf	0 – 20 mm °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹	1,2,3,4
ddf_{max}	$ddf_{max} = ddf_{min} + ddf_{plus}$		1,2,3,4
ddf_{plus}	Difference between ddf_{min} and ddf_{max}	0 – 20 mm °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹	1,2,3,4
T_{bm}	Base melting temperature	-2 – 3 °C	1,2,3,4
K_{cum}	Parameter adjusting ddf for snowpack ageing	0.01 – 0.2 mm ⁻¹	1,2,3,4
fc_{min}	Minimum water retention fraction	0 – 0.1	1,2,3,4
fc_{max}	Maximum water retention fraction	0.01 – 0.35	1,2,3,4
fc_{plus}	$fc_{plus} = fc_{max} - fc_{min}$		1,2,3,4
C_{cum}	Water retention capacity parameter	0.005 – 0.05 mm ⁻¹	1,2,3,4
T_{bf}	Base refreezing temperature	-5 – 2 °C	1,2,3,4
K_f	Refreeze factor	0 – 5 mm °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹	1,2,3,4
Fe	DDF aggradation exponent	0-1	1,2,3,4
ET_{eff}	Effective Evapotranspiration	0 – 3	1,2,3,4
C_r	Surface & delayed runoff fraction	0 – 1	1,2,3,4
C_{vp}	Groundwater recharge fraction	0.00001 – 0.02	1,2,3,4
C_{va}	Hypodermic flow fraction	0 – 0.1	1,2,3,4
C_p	Groundwater flow fraction	0.00001 – 0.01	1,2,3,4
LV_{max}	Thickness vadose zone	0 – 500 mm	1,2,3,4
LP_{max}	Thickness phreatic zone	0 – 2000 mm	1,2,3,4
α_1	Shape parameter for surface gamma UH	0.3 – 20	1,2,3,4
β_1	Rate parameter for surface gamma UH	0.01 – 5	1,2,3,4
α_2	Shape parameter for delayed gamma UH	0.5 – 13	1,2,3,4
β_2	Rate parameter for delayed gamma UH	0.15 – 1.5	1,2,3,4

2.1.5 HYMOD

The *Hydrologic Model (HYMOD)* was described by Boyle (2001) and Wagener, Boyle *et al.* (2001). It has been developed with simplicity of structure and number of parameters in mind. HYMOD is based on the *probability-distributed principle*, which assigns a probability to runoff volumes (Moore, 1985; Moore, 1999). Furthermore, the same structure was used by Wagener, Boyle *et al.* (2001) to argue for a hydrological modelling framework. An improved version, HYMOD2, was created by Roy, Gupta *et al.* (2017).

The model has five parameters, consists of three quick response reservoirs sharing a recession coefficient and a single slow flow reservoir. While the number of quick response reservoirs in Boyle (2001) was a parameter to be optimized, it is fixed to three in other studies (Wagener, Boyle *et al.* 2001; Vrugt, Gupta *et al.* 2003; Vrugt, Diks *et al.* 2005; Sun *et al.* 2010; Roy, Gupta *et al.* 2017). In HYMOD, soil moisture accounting is carried out using a *Probability Distributed Model (PDM)*, as it was proposed by Moore (1985) (see also Moore, 2007). With the PDM principle, the capacity of the soil moisture storage is assigned a probability, which expresses variability of storage capacities within a catchment. Considering that runoff from initially empty stores is only generated at the end of a time step, if precipitation input exceeds storage capacity of the shallowest store, this capacity can be called critical for this time step. Therefore, for each time step, a probability of exceedance of this critical capacity can be calculated, which is used in HYMOD to compute the catchment area that contributes to runoff at any given time step (Boyle, 2001; Moore, 2007). Runoff generated thus is then delayed in the quick and slow flow tanks, which finally lead

to runoff. HYMOD aggregates data in a lumped way. Potential evapotranspiration can be taken from data, as in Boyle (2001), Wagener, Boyle *et al.* (2001), Vrugt, Diks *et al.* (2005) and Shafii, Basu *et al.* (2017); Raven template files use Hamon’s approach (Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b).

Snow accounting is not provided originally (Boyle, 2001; Shafii, Basu *et al.* 2017).

There have been a number of sensitivity analyses done on HYMOD parameters, for example by Bastola and Murphy (2013) and Herman *et al.* (2013). Parra *et al.* (2018) compare HBV and HYMOD with a sensitivity analysis. They particularly put emphasis on HYMOD’s inaccuracy in flow peak representations. The model, they note, seems more suited to simulate low streamflows and they recommend HYMOD to be used on monthly data. Furthermore, Parra *et al.* (2018) detected larger drops in NSE values from calibration to validation when using HYMOD, compared to HBV. HYMOD was employed in a comparison with machine-learning based models in Herath *et al.* (2021, p. 4390), where HYMOD performed „poorly“ with validation KGE and NSE of 0.6 and 0.52, respectively, contrasted with 0.79 and 0.66, respectively, achieved by the machine learning informed MIKA-SHA_FUSE model. In a study to regionalize HYMOD parameters, Bastola (2022) yielded a range of NSE values from 0.48 to 0.88, noting that the parameters C_{max} , α and K_s were found to be more sensitive than K_q and B_{exp} .

HYMOD is emulated in Raven. For parameter ranges used in this thesis, see Table 5. In line with suggestions in the template files provided by Craig and the Raven Development Team (2023b), Hamon’s approach to PET estimation is chosen in this study. Although HYMOD does not include a snow accounting routine, one can be coupled in Raven. In the present thesis, this is performed, as it was deemed profitable due to the high elevations of some of the catchments, a strategy also utilized by Parra *et al.* (2018). Snow melts at the potential melt rate, calculated using the degree-day method as outlined in Dingman, 2015. The method is summarized in more detail below.

Table 5: HYMOD model parameters with range. Sources: [1] Moore (1985); [2] Vrugt, Gupta *et al.* (2003); [3] Bastola and Murphy (2013); [4] Bastola (2022); [5] Knoben *et al.* (2019b); [6] Wang and Solomatine (2019); [7] Craig and the Raven Development Team (2023b).

Parameter	Description	Range	Sources
K_q	Residence time of quick reservoir	0 – 1 d	2,3,4,5,6
C_{max}	Max. Soil Moisture Capacity	1 – 2000 mm	2,3,4,5,6
T_0	Rain/snow threshold temperature	-3 – 3 °C	5,7
K_s	Residence time of slow reservoir	0 – 1 d	2,3,4,5,6
C_{melt}	Degree-day factor for snow melt	0 – 20 mm °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹	5,7
T_{melt}	Threshold temperature for snow melt	-3 – 3 °C	5,7
B_{exp}	Spatial variability of soil moisture capacity in catchment	0 – 10	2,3,4,5,6
PET_{corr}	PET correction factor	0 – 1	7
α	Flow distribution quick/slow reservoir	0 – 1	2,3,4,5,6

2.1.6 MOHYSE

The *MOdèle HYdrologique Simplifié à l’Extrême (MOHYSE)* was developed by Fortin and Turcotte (2007) with simplicity in mind. Having been created as part of a hydrological modelling course at the University of Quebec, another aim was being able to teach the modelling process (Fortin and Turcotte, 2007; Martel *et al.* 2017).

MOHYSE has 10 parameters, two of which are used to direct snow calculations. Potential evapotranspiration is estimated using a set of equations, which firstly take into account the seasonal variation of sunlight, depending on the catchment location, and secondly the absolute humidity of the air at saturation point. Two reservoirs represent the quicker reacting *vadose* zone and the slower *aquifer*. Both contribute to streamflow, each depending on its respective reservoir level. Furthermore, once the vadose zone reservoir is full, surface runoff is generated, adding directly to streamflow. Before reaching the catchment outlet, water is routed through a unit hydrograph with a gamma function (Fortin and Turcotte, 2007; Arsenault, Gatién *et al.* 2015; Troin, Arsenault and Brissette, 2015; Arsenault, Breton-Dufour *et al.* 2019).

Snow accounting is implemented using a degree-day method, partitioning rain and snow by a temperature threshold (Fortin and Turcotte, 2007). Snowmelt is governed by a melt factor and its calculation follows the form of Equation (1). Snow modelling is accounted for with the two parameters c_f (melt rate) and T_f (melt temperature) (Troin, Arsenault and Brissette, 2015), as summarized in Table 6.

Roy, Royer *et al.* (2010) made use of MOHYSE’s ability to estimate melting discharge with snow-covered areas from satellite data. In the Canadian River du Nord catchment, Turcotte *et al.* (2010) employ MOHYSE to improve simulations of spring flood with snow water equivalent (SWE) observations. They note, however, that „significant errors“ were still present (Turcotte *et al.* 2010, p. 872). Contrasting MOHYSE’s snow routine with that of other models, Valéry, Andréassian *et al.* (2014a, p. 25) highlight MOHYSE’s comparatively „very simplistic“ approach to account for rain/snow partitioning, dedicating only one parameter. In that study, the model tends to perform weaker than the others, but not using any SAR would yield even lower results. Arsenault, Gatien *et al.* (2015)’s study on averaging the simulations of multiple models into a single hydrograph have been noted above. Following Ibarra Zavaleta *et al.* (2015)’s implementation of MOHYSE in tropical parts of Mexico, Arsenault, Breton-Dufour *et al.* (2019) employ it to assess three regionalization methods there as well. Additionally, GR4J and HMETS are used.

MOHYSE is emulated in Raven and template files are provided (Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020; Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b). For an overview of the parameter ranges used in this thesis, see Table 6. MOHYSE uses data to estimate rain/snow fractioning. This was replaced by the RAINSNOW_DINGMAN process option in Raven for this thesis.

Table 6: MOHYSE model parameters with range. Sources: [1] Fortin and Turcotte (2007); [2] Hamaoui (2019); [3] Larocque *et al.* (2010); [4] Ibarra Zavaleta *et al.* (2015); [5] Craig and the Raven Development Team (2023b).

Parameter	Description	Range	Sources
c_{ETP}	PET coefficient	0.5 – 2	1,2,3,4
c_{TR}	AET coefficient	0.5 – 1	1,2,3,4
c_f	Melt factor	2 – 4 mm °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹	1,2,4
T_f	Degree day melt temperature	-5 – 5 °C	1,2,3,4
V_{max}	Thickness TOPSOIL	0.5 – 10 m	1,2
c_{VA}	Percolation coefficient	0.01 – 0.99	1,2,3,4
c_V	Drainage coefficient vadose	0.01 – 0.99	1,2,3,4
c_A	Drainage coefficient aquifer	0.01 – 0.99	1,2,3,4
α	UH shape parameter	0.5 – 5	1,2,3,4
β	UH scale parameter	0.01 – 20	1,2,3,4

All five models approach potential snow melt with a degree-day method. They have the general form shown in Equation (1) (adapted from Dingman (2015, eq. 5.71)), where SM is snowmelt (mm d⁻¹), C_{Melt} a melt factor (mm d⁻¹ °C⁻¹), T_I the atmospheric temperature for that time interval (°C) and T_b (°C) a base temperature that is at the melting point (usually 0 °C). This approximation is empirical and has been developed as an alternative to energy-based methods which requires fewer measurements (Brubaker *et al.* 1996; Ferguson, 1999; Dingman, 2015). In the Raven model configurations in this thesis, HBV and HMETS use their own adaptations of the approach, while GR4J, HYMOD and MOHYSE use the form outlined above. For an overview of Raven process options for all five models used in this thesis, see Table 7.

$$SM = C_{Melt} \times \max[(T_I - T_b), 0] \quad (1)$$

2.2 Raven Hydrologic Modelling framework

Acknowledging the structural uncertainties in hydrological modelling, Craig, Brown *et al.* (2020) created Raven as a toolbox to test hypotheses about the functioning of a hydrological system, as proposed e.g. by Wagener, Boyle *et al.* (2001), Wagener, McIntyre *et al.* (2003), Fencia, Savenije *et al.* (2008), Clark, Kavetski *et al.* (2011) and Fencia, Kavetski *et al.* (2011). With Raven, it is not only practicable to test hypotheses, but also their constituting subcomponents. Craig, Brown *et al.* (2020, p. 3) list *process representations, model structures, discretization approaches, parametrizations* and *numerical algorithms* as sources of uncertainties, each of which shall be addressed in the following paragraphs outlining Raven.

Table 7: Process options chosen for GR4J, HBV, HMETS, HYMOD and MOHYSE in this study. All snowmelt methods are based on degree day factor (DDF) approaches. Options in *italics* highlight changes compared to the default in Raven template files. UH: Unit Hydrograph; DDF: Degree Day Factor.

Model	Routing	PET	Snow Balance	Snowmelt	Rain/Snow	Glacier
GR4J	Dump	Hamon	Cemaneige	DDF	Dingman	-
HBV	Triangular UH	<i>Hamon</i>	Pot. Melt Rate	HBV (DDF)	HBV (linear transition)	Melt: DDF Release: Linear storage coeff.
HMETS	Dump	Oudin	HMETS (DDF)	HMETS (DDF)	<i>Threshold</i>	-
HYMOD	Nash UH	Hamon	Pot. Melt Rate	DDF	Threshold	-
MOHYSE	Gamma UH	MOHYSE	Pot. Melt Rate	DDF	<i>Threshold</i>	-

For each hydrological response unit (HRU), a set of coupled ordinary (ODE) and partial (PDE) differential equations are solved to calculate the variables describing the HRU at a certain time step. This is performed by *global algorithms*. Craig, Brown *et al.* (2020) emphasize that users are not restricted to a single predefined numerical algorithm, but can rather choose between alternatives that solve the set of ODEs and PDEs to investigate the effects. To calculate how much a hydrologic process changes a state variable, *process algorithms* are used. They return their result to the global algorithms, which then modify state variables accordingly. Process algorithms are never permitted to apply their changes of state variables themselves. Hence, they can be exchanged with ease, since global algorithms do not depend on a specific process algorithm, again allowing to compare alternatives (Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020). Raven handles spatial discretization with HRUs. Each reacts differently to forcings, depending on its characteristics, such as land use, topography or soil profile (Clark, Nijssen *et al.* 2015; Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020). Several HRUs may be combined to form a subbasin and multiple subbasins, in turn can build a watershed. Using a single HRU would yield a model in lumped mode. Other spatial discretizations are possible. Temporal discretization can be different for global and process algorithms. In the Raven configuration files, modellers define the time step to be used for simulations. However, process algorithms, not being coupled to global ones, are allowed to use finer granularity (Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020). Modellers define how to connect process representations to build models. Although a number of template files exist that allow an easy set-up to emulate several models (Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023a), users are free to pick and choose among algorithms themselves (Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020). In Raven, parameters are structured into the classes vegetation, land use/land type, terrain, soil and soil profile. For example, a modeller may wish to define a generic vegetation class „coniferous forest“, which is re-used for several HRUs. Furthermore, it is possible to vary parameters temporally using time series. Forcings available as measurements per gauge can be read in as time series, which are then interpolated among the gauges used in the model. Alternatively, grid-based netCDF files are supported, along with grid weight files listing each cell’s contribution to the total contributing area. With at least precipitation and temperature, Raven is able to generate other needed forcing data. Alternatively, users may also provide them themselves. Routing is separated into in-catchment, in-channel and reservoir routing (Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020). Models in Raven are set up with five ASCII text files, defining 1. general model structure, 2. HRUs, 3. parameters, 4. time series and 5. initial conditions. Along with the forcing data, discharge observations and the Raven executable, a model may thus be defined. Depending on the model complexity, additional time series may be necessary, such as for reservoir levels or parameters. Moreover, simulations and performance metrics generated with Raven are output to text files as well (Craig, Brown *et al.* 2020; Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b).

Mai, Craig and Tolson (2020) estimate that Raven can create 8×10^{12} different model configurations, as of version 3.0. Raven is coded in C++, with the source code being open and hosted on a GitHub repository (*RavenHydroFramework* 2023).

2.3 Parameter Optimization

Since Raven’s configuration and output is based on text files, it can easily be coupled to other software, enabling parameter optimization with tools that read Raven’s output and write parameters for the next model run into the configuration files.

One option is the *Optimization Software Toolkit for Research Involving Computational Heuristics* (OSTRICH). It performs parameter optimization by minimizing a user-defined cost-function (Matott, 2017b; Matott, 2017a). Although RAVEN also has the capability of computing a number of performance metrics, such as the Nash-Sutcliffe-Efficiency (NSE) or the root mean squared error (RMSE) after each run (Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b), their choice is limited. Since optimization in the present study is based on the non-parametric Kling-Gupta efficiency as a cost function, which is not available in RAVEN, the Python libraries HydroErr and HydroEval are used to calculate a number of metrics (Roberts *et al.* 2018; „Hydroeval“ 2023).

The *dynamically dimensioned search algorithm* (DDS) was proposed by Tolson and Shoemaker (2007) as an alternative to the *shuffled complex evolution algorithm* (SCE) prevalent at that time, aiming to be computationally more efficient while easy to use. A fundamental principle of DDS is to adjust the number of parameters perturbed from the current best set for each time step, depending on the computational budget left. With the iteration count increasing, the algorithm reduces the number of perturbed parameters, thus changing the search scope from global to gradually more local (Tolson and Shoemaker, 2007). The authors stress that this strategy, while able to find „good“ solutions within the computational budget, was not designed to produce the „optimal“ parameter set. Furthermore, they argue that DDS could be applied in calibrations with up to 30 parameters. In a comparison of algorithms, Arsenault, Poulin *et al.* (2014) found DDS to be among the three best methods for models with many parameters. DDS is moreover used in studies by Spieler *et al.* (2020), Seiller *et al.* (2017), Shafii and Tolson (2015) and Zink *et al.* (2018). A version optimized for parallel computing was presented by Tolson, Vimal *et al.* (2014) and it is available in OSTRICH. DDS merely requires modellers to set the *scalar neighbourhood size perturbation parameter* r and the computational budget. r governs perturbation ranges around the parameters to be optimized, the budget defines the maximum number of iterations allowed. Tolson and Shoemaker (2007) point out the robustness of the default value of 0.2 for r . This value was also used by Spieler *et al.* (2020), Chlumsky, Mai *et al.* (2021a) and Mai (2023b). Mai (2023b) varies the budget as a multiple of the parameters to be optimized; Chlumsky, Mai *et al.* (2021b) use 10'000, Spieler *et al.* (2020) use 5 different budgets, with the maximum at 10'000; Zink *et al.* (2018) use 1'000; Shafii and Tolson (2015) use 5'000; Arsenault, Poulin *et al.* (2014) compare DDS to other algorithms with a budget of 25'000 runs; Yen *et al.* (2015) compare DDS with up to 5'000 runs to other algorithms and conclude that DDS performs best. Hence, the parallel DDS algorithm in OSTRICH is used in this thesis with a budget of 5'000 and perturbation parameter of 0.2.

The split-sample calibration and validation scheme has originally been proposed as *split-sample test* by Klemesš (1986). Although it is still used in the majority of studies (Shen, Tolson *et al.* 2022), there have been a number in recent years arguing for its update or outright abandon (Mai, 2023b; Arsenault, Brissette *et al.* 2018). Shen, Tolson *et al.* (2022), for example, employ GR4J and HMETS to argue for the model calibration to be carried out using the entirety of data instead of using only a sub-period. As originally proposed by Klemesš (1986) and applied in a number of studies, calibration and validation periods are split evenly in this thesis, since the overall length of the data period is deemed to be of sufficient length. Both periods span over 20 years, with calibration beginning on the 1st of January 1981 and ending 31st of December 2000, and validation starting the day after and ending on 31st of December 2020.

Each model calibration is carried out 20 times, using different seed numbers in OSTRICH. The random seeds used in the model setups are listed in Table 17 in Appendix A.1. Of these 20 runs, the one with the highest $KG E_{np}$ for the calibration period is selected for further analysis. This approach aims to reduce randomness in finding a solution; a thorough sensitivity analysis, however, is not carried out, since it is outside the scope of this study. Running each model only once would risk finding local optima while missing global ones. As the number of simulations increases, using different random seeds each time, confidence grows that the optimal solution found might represent a global optimum, although it is not guaranteed. The calculation of the total number of model calibration problems solved with DDS is 1100 (5 models x 20 trials x 11 catchments). Selecting the best-performing hydrograph during calibration for each model gives 55 hydrographs that are assessed further (5 models x 11 catchments). To increase computation speeds, Raven, OSTRICH and all model input files are uploaded to the University of Bern Linux HPC Cluster (Ubelix) (*High Performance Computing* (HPC) 2016), which allows parallel execution. Raven and Ostrich executables are compiled on the cluster. After each parameter optimization

run, OSTRICH executes a Python script which calculates the performance metrics outlined below on the hydrograph produced by RAVEN. Of these, the non-parametric version of the Kling-Gupta efficiency (Pool *et al.* 2018) is fed to OSTRICH's cost function. All Raven model configuration files, as well as the corresponding OSTRICH input files, are shown in Listings 1 to 30 in Appendix A.2.

2.3.1 Performance Metrics

The following paragraphs give a brief overview of the non-parametric Kling-Gupta efficiency KGE_{np} and its predecessors and furthermore of the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Percent Bias (PBias) and Volumetric Efficiency (VE). Mai (2023b) uses GR4J to highlight the importance of choosing an objective function that is best suited for the purpose of the study. The first paragraph with its description of KGE_{np} is intended to serve this purpose.

The *Kling-Gupta efficiency (KGE)* is a metric which is often used to compare model performances. It has been proposed by Gupta, Kling *et al.* (2009) as an alternative to the *Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE)*, originally developed by Nash and Sutcliffe (1970). The NSE is centered around the mean flow; the contribution of high flows especially will be underestimated, while low flows contribute over-proportionally, which leads to an incorrect assessment of variability (Gupta, Kling *et al.* 2009). This, however, has not been the only criticism of NSE as a performance measure. As Schaeffli and Gupta (2007) note, a major drawback is that normalization with the mean value of observed flows will make it harder to compare values to other catchments, since their normalization will be based on different observed flows. The KGE introduced by Gupta, Kling *et al.* (2009) aims to take the variability of flows into account. Furthermore, its components can be seen as multiple objectives, which take into account different characteristics of a hydrograph (Gupta, Kling *et al.* 2009; Pool *et al.* 2018). Pool *et al.* (2018) then argue that KGE is based on unrealistic assumptions: linear and normally distributed observations; hence, they modify KGE into a *non-parametric version KGE_{np}*. It is shown in Equation (2), where r_s is a dynamics, α_{np} a variability and β_{np} a volume component. r_s is shown in Equation (3), where i is index of the time step, N the total number of time steps in the series and μ the mean value. To calculate α , the time series are ranked. α is shown in Equation (4), where $I(k)$ and $J(k)$ are the indices of the time steps with the k th-largest flow, with $I(k)$ referencing simulations and $J(k)$ observations. Finally, β is shown in Equation (5). Equations (2) to (5) have been adapted from „Hydroeval“ (2023). Pool *et al.* (2018) conclude by highlighting the general improvement of calibration with the non-parametric version. Observations would fit reality better with the notable exception of high flows. Furthermore, they emphasize to avoid using a log-transform on the flow time series when computing the original KGE metric, since this would risk numerical errors for very low flows and a volume unit dependency ($L s^{-1}$ vs. $m^3 s^{-1}$), as shown by Santos *et al.* (2018). The non-parametric KGE metric is presented as an alternative to this dilemma, obviating the need for log-transformations (Pool *et al.* 2018). Therefore, in this thesis, calibration with KGE_{np} is carried out without time series transformation. For consistency, untransformed time series are also used when computing the metrics introduced below. As is the case for NSE, KGE and its variants go from $-\infty$ to 1, where a value of 1 indicates perfect reproduction of observed values by the model (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970; Gupta, Kling *et al.* 2009; Pool *et al.* 2018). Although it is possible to put emphasis on components by introducing scaling factors (see Gupta, Kling *et al.* (2009, eq. 10)), this is omitted in the present thesis. Dynamics (r_s), variability (α) and volume (β) components thus all have the same weight.

$$KGE_{np} = 1 - \sqrt{[r_s - 1]^2 + [\alpha_{np} - 1]^2 + [\beta - 1]^2} \quad (2)$$

$$r_s = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N [Obs_i - \mu_{Obs}] [Sim_i - \mu_{Sim}]}{\sqrt{[\sum_{i=1}^N [Obs_i - \mu_{Obs}]^2] [\sum_{i=1}^N [Sim_i - \mu_{Sim}]^2]}} \quad (3)$$

$$\alpha_{np} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \left| \frac{Sim_{I(k)}}{N \cdot \mu_{Sim}} - \frac{Obs_{J(k)}}{N \cdot \mu_{Obs}} \right| \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = \frac{\mu_{Sim}}{\mu_{Obs}} \quad (5)$$

Another metric, the *Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)* is scale-dependent, i.e. tends to be larger for larger flows (Hyndman and Koehler, 2006; Althoff and Rodrigues, 2021). Squaring the errors binds this measure from zero to positive infinity. Equation (6) shows the RMSE in its basic form (adapted from „Hydroeval“ (2023)); other variations can include normalizations (Althoff and Rodrigues, 2021). Furthermore, log-transformation of hydrographs is often applied to mitigate the influence of outliers (Hyndman and Koehler, 2006; Jackson *et al.* 2019). This would require that no values are below zero. On the other hand, Mai (2023b, p. 6) recommends that „data should always be fitted in the transformation the fit is assessed in“. Though parameter optimization in this study is performed utilizing only KGE_{np} , this advice is nonetheless heeded for all metrics in this thesis and no transformations of the results are applied. This metric is hence in the same unit as the hydrographs, i.e. $m^3 s^{-1}$ (Althoff and Rodrigues, 2021). It has to be emphasized, however, that comparisons across catchments should not be made, as values are not independent of catchment characteristics (Althoff and Rodrigues, 2021).

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [Obs_i - Sim_i]^2} \quad (6)$$

The *Percent Bias (PBias)* in Equation (7) (adapted from „Hydroeval“ (2023)) is unbound and centred around zero. Negative values indicate a tendency for a model to underestimate the hydrograph compared to observations; positive value indicate overestimation thereof (Althoff and Rodrigues, 2021). PBias can be expressed as the bias between observations and simulations normalized with the mean of observations, as in Equation (8), where $Bias = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (Obs_i - Sim_i)$ (adapted from Althoff and Rodrigues (2021)).

$$PBias = 100 \times \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (Obs_i - Sim_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N Obs_i} \quad (7)$$

$$PBias = 100 \times \frac{Bias}{\mu_{Obs}} \quad (8)$$

The *Volumetric Efficiency (VE)*, as proposed by Criss and Winston (2008) in reply to Schaeffli and Gupta (2007)'s critique of NSE, deals with the timing of a simulated hydrograph. It is shown in Equation (9) (adapted from Roberts *et al.* (2018)). Higher VE values indicate a higher fraction of the total water volume, which in the simulated hydrograph arrives at the same time as in the observations. Lower VE values therefore mean worse timing. It ranges from 0 to 1 for unbiased simulations, whose total volume has been scaled to the total observation volume (Criss and Winston, 2008). In that case, a VE of 1 indicates 100% of simulated volume being timed right (Jackson *et al.* 2019). Volumetric efficiencies cannot be compared across catchments (Criss and Winston, 2008).

$$VE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N |Sim_i - Obs_i|}{\sum_{i=1}^N Obs_i} \quad (9)$$

As Raven outputs hydrograph time series as "time-average flows for the preceding time step" (Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b, p. 206), observations and simulations are shifted by one day compared to the input data and thus have to be advanced by one day prior to further analysis. Summarizing, after each Raven run, the resulting time series are read by a Python script and shifted one day ahead to correspond with input dating. No further transformations are applied. KGE_{np} , RMSE, PBias and VE are then calculated for calibration and validation periods separately and written to a text file. Only the KGE_{np} value for the calibration period is read by OSTRICH for its minimization of the cost function. OSTRICH finally generates a new parameter set, writes it to the model configuration files and starts the next Raven run.

2.4 Study area and data

2.4.1 Catchment characteristics

For this study, eleven catchments in Switzerland are selected. They are listed in Table 8, along with key characteristics. Catchment id is in accordance with Schwanbeck, Kan *et al.* (2018). Catchments vary in a range of characteristics, most of which are determined by topography. They have a high heterogeneity in terms of area, mean altitude and glaciation ratio. Areas range from

39.4 km² for the alpine Rhône catchment to 415.9 km² for the Broye catchment. Mean elevations cover a range of more than 2000 meters, from the glacier-free Venoge catchment at 694 m up to the Massa catchment at 2929 m, whose glaciers cover 56.4 % of its area. Finally, the steep valleys of the Weisse Lütschine catchment, creating a mean slope of 31° stand in sharp contrast with the 6° slope in the Venoge catchment. A further catchment not listed above, Ticino at gauge Piotta, has been excluded, since it experienced too strong an influence from a man-made reservoir. While this is invariably true for the Massa catchment – the main stream, Massa, is captured by the *Gibidum* reservoir – , it is still included, since it directly borders to two catchments where water is not retained in reservoirs and may thus provide a valuable comparison. In none of the other investigated catchments are streams retained in reservoirs; electrical power is generated in continuous and diversion power plants, though (Federal Office of Energy (SFOE), 2023). For an overview of the catchment locations used in the present study, see Figure 1.

Table 8: Overview of catchment characteristics. Ids are unique (Schwanbeck and Bühlmann, 2018); streams are unique in this thesis. Source: ID (Schwanbeck and Bühlmann, 2018); Characteristics (Höge *et al.* 2023b).

Stream	Gauge	ID	Area (km ²)	Elev. m	Glaciation %	Aspect °	Slope °
Broye	Payerne, Caserne d'aviation	CH-0057	415.9	724	-	217°	7°
Dischmabach	Davos, Kriegsmatte	CH-0159	42.9	2372	0.7	239°	25°
Lonza	Blatten	CH-0140	77.4	2617	24.3	201°	29°
Massa	Blatten bei Naters	CH-0105	195.5	2929	56.4	160°	23°
Rhone	Gletsch	CH-0139	39.4	2703	42.8	210°	22°
Saltina	Brig	CH-0161	76.5	2017	2.5	281°	27°
Sitter	Appenzell	CH-0083	74.4	1254	0.0	300°	21°
Thur	Andelfingen	CH-0058	1702	773	0.0	223°	10°
Ticino	Bellinzona	CH-0053	1518	1679	0.15	169°	29°
Venoge	Ecublens, Les Bois	CH-0198	227.6	694	-	132°	6°
Weisse Lütschine	Zweilütschinen	CH-0118	164.9	2149	13.0	3°	31°

Figure 1: Map of catchment locations. Sources: Catchment delineations - Höge *et al.* (2023b); administrative units, rivers, lakes - Bundesamt für Landestopografie swisstopo (2023); background - European Environment Agency (2016). Own illustration.

2.4.2 Hydro-meteorological data

Meteo forcings from MeteoSwiss are gridded files in netCDF format with a cell size of 1x1 km that contain daily values (Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss, 2021b; Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss, 2021a). Forcing files are cropped to the respective catchment extent for efficiency. In the present study, daily minimum, maximum and average temperature files are used, as well as daily precipitation. For an overview of meteo data nomenclature and sources, see Table 9. Daily mean runoff observations are taken from the CAMELS-CH dataset (Höge *et al.* 2023a). Mean altitude is calculated using digital elevation data from the swissALTI3D model (Federal Office of Topography swisstopo, 2023). These DEM files have also been used to calculate mean aspect and slope. Grid weights are generated using shape files from the CAMELS-CH dataset. Aspects and slopes are calculated using GDAL and saved to GeoTIFF files that are further processed with *Raven-Tools*. For all the models with glaciated parts, two HRUs are described and their characteristics written to the respective Raven input files, one for the glaciated area and one for the rest. Glacier extent is downloaded from the Swiss Glacier Inventory SGI2016, published by Linsbauer *et al.* (2021) and hosted on GLAMOS (Linsbauer *et al.* 2020). A further goal would have been to implement HBV-EC’s capability to run in semi-distributed mode using elevation bands as HRUs. Due to a bug in pre-processing, which could not be resolved within time constraints, this part had to be abandoned. Catchment characteristics are downloaded from HYDROmaps and two attributes are used in Raven input files (Bühlmann and Schwanbeck, 2018; Schwanbeck and Bühlmann, 2018): *a0418_clc18_5_afrtv1_0* (forest cover) and *a0425_clc18_5_aurbv1_0* (urbanization); these have been assigned to the RAVEN land use attributes FOREST_COV and IMPERM, respectively. They had originally been derived from satellite monitoring as part of the Corine Land Cover CLC project (Bühlmann and Schwanbeck, 2018; Schwanbeck and Bühlmann, 2018; European Environment Agency, 2019). The cell size and the respective boundary coordinates of the netCDF grids are extracted with the Python library GeoPandas (Geopandas/Geopandas 2023) to generate a grid, which is overlaid with the extent of each HRU and each cell is given a weight that is relative to the total HRU area. For each HRU, cell weights sum up to 1. Grid weight calculation is carried out overlaying both non-glaciated and glaciated parts of catchment shape files separately. Grid weights are written to Raven-compatible text files.

Table 9: Overview of hydro-meteorological data. References: [1] Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss (2021b); [2] Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss (2021a); [3] Höge *et al.* (2023b); [4] Bundesamt für Landestopografie swisstopo (2022); [5] Linsbauer *et al.* (2020); [6] Schwanbeck and Bühlmann (2018).

Data	Name	References
Precipitation	RhiresD	1
Average Temperature	TabSD	2
Max. Temperature	TmaxD	2
Min. Temperature	TminD	2
Discharge	CAMELS-CH	3
Elevation	swissALTI3D	4
Glaciers	SGI2016	5
Catchment delineations	CAMELS-CH	5
Land use	HYDROmaps	6

2.5 Pre-Processing

There already are a number of software products available to process data for Raven or run models: *ravenpy* is a set of Python methods to generate Raven input files, run hydrological models in Raven and analyse the results (Arsenault, Huard *et al.* 2023; Huard *et al.* 2023). It supports eight of the models Raven is able to emulate, currently missing HMETS and HYMOD, however. *ravenpy* contains four pre-processing scripts, that are designed for Canadian data (Huard, 2023); the Python-based function collection *BasinMaker* is able to delineate watersheds, generate HRUs and produce routing networks (Han, Mai *et al.* 2020; Han, Shen, Tolson, Craig *et al.* 2023). It is designed to support Canadian settings (Han, Shen, Tolson and Metcalfe, 2022); *RavenR* provides functions for pre-processing, model input file generation and result analysis in an R package

(Chlumsky, Craig *et al.* 2022); *GridWeightsGenerator.py* is a Python script which does grid weight generation for Raven, it is based on sub-basins in Canada produced by BasinMaker (Mai, 2023a); tutorial files for Raven are hosted on the Raven homepage (Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2022); model configuration templates can be generated with Raven or are available in the Raven manual (Craig and the Raven Development Team, 2023b); several models are also published with their respective toolsets, such as GUIs or pre-processing functions, albeit not specifically designed to work with Raven. Furthermore, the Raven homepage lists several online tools to visualize simulation results, such as *RavenView* or *HydroGlyph* (Craig, 2023).

To the best of my knowledge, there is currently no toolbox or set of functions to facilitate pre-processing, generation of input files and analysis of results produced by Raven and additionally offering support of OSTRICH file generation, while being easy to apply in a Swiss context. While each software item listed above is able to do some of those steps, they are either too constrained in their area of application or limited to files generated specifically for a Canadian context. Therefore, I coded a Python library for the present thesis, *Raven-Tools*.

2.5.1 Raven-Tools Python library

In order to facilitate pre-processing of the data required by Raven, as well as Raven file generation and visualization of the results, a Python library was written. Many parts of the code are designed to be compatible with data from the sources listed in Table 9; thus, they are limited to the file formats and data descriptions used therein. While there may exist code snippets or algorithms that could also be used in other settings, this was not the focus taken into consideration during the creation of *Raven-Tools*. Users are hence advised to consider these limitations and to check the source code before using it. The entire source code has been published on GitHub as *Raven Tools* repository and is freely available (Zweifel, 2023). *Raven-Tools* is broadly structured into five parts: 1. *Raven_Model (RM)* provides the *RavenModel* class that can be used to create model instances or be extended. *RM* is designed object-oriented; 2. *Raven_Preprocess (RPE)* contains methods that pre-process data to be read by Raven. This may include manipulation of forcing data files, file conversion, coordinate transformations and so on; 3. *Raven_Run (RR)* provides methods that produce Raven model configuration files containing general model structure, parameter values and connections to forcing files. Default parameter ranges used in this thesis (see Tables 2 to 6) can be read from external text files; 4. *Raven_Postprocess (RPO)* can be used to analyse hydrographs or visualize results after a Raven model run; 5. *Raven_Diag (RDI)* contains functions that can be executed after an OSTRICH optimization run to calculate performance metrics on resulting hydrographs to be fed into the next OSTRICH run.

RM is the only one of the five parts, which does not provide methods that can be used outside the *Raven-Tools* Python library; rather, it allows user-friendly access to methods in the other parts. This part is aimed to be used in scripts that are repeatedly called, e.g. in the case of model file generation with a number of different parameter sets.

The general workflow in *Raven-Tools* is pre-processing of data, generation of the input files needed to describe the Raven model and analysis of the results. Thus, *RPE*, *RR* and *RPO* are designed to be used in this order, although any of their methods can also be used independently. Finally, *RDI* is designed to be copied into the folder containing Raven model and executable files. For this thesis, it was done by a Linux Bash script, which subsequently started the OSTRICH executable. Furthermore, a set of structured text files contain default parameter values for the conceptual models used in this thesis as well as settings specific to the user's setup. *RDI* additionally provides methods that are loaded by *RPO* to generate performance metrics, plots and tables. A few of the methods in *RPE* call Bash scripts to use their computational efficiency. This, however, may make them dependent on Linux based operating systems. As computations for the present thesis were carried out on Linux systems, the *Raven-Tools* Python library currently works best for those environments. Moreover, usage of the *Raven-Tools* library is limited to a specific structure in the input files, as they are used in this thesis. Data in other formats, from different sources or for other locations than those mentioned in Table 9 can currently not be used without extending the library. An abridged overview of the library structure is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: UML diagram of Raven-Tools Python library structure. Some methods were renamed for clarity, helper functions were left out.

3 Results

This section is structured as follows. First, a visual presentation of the hydrographs created by using 20 random seeds in Ostrich. For each model, the hydrograph with the highest $KG_{E_{np}}$ was selected for further analysis. They are presented in their full length for the calibration and validation period and also for a selection of peak flow events as well as low flow conditions. To investigate a model's capability to reproduce seasonal characteristics, regime plots are then shown. Finally, all performance metrics are summarized and compared graphically.

3.1 Random Seeds

Figures 3 to 7 show the mean daily runoff observations during a period of ten days prior up to ten days after the dates with maximum values in the calibration period along with the 20 simulations generated with varying the random seeds used in Ostrich for each model and catchment. Furthermore, they depict the same time series for events with the lowest observed mean daily discharge during the calibration period, for a time range selected so as to include the recession of the hydrograph leading to the low flood event.

It is noteworthy that GR4J, MOHYSE and, to a lesser extent, HMETS have less widely spread seeds, while those of HBV and HYMOD are comparatively wider. GR4J especially exhibits nearly no differences among the 20 hydrographs for all eleven catchments, both for the maximum and minimum events (see Figures 3a and 3b). HBV, on the other hand, has considerable variation in the peak discharges (see Figure 4a). Variation visibly increases, where simulated hydrographs are able to mimic peak events, such as for HBV, HMETS and HYMOD (see Figures 4a, 5a and 6a); although this is less true for HYMOD, since it tends to vastly underestimate peaks for every catchment and additionally exhibits a lag. While MOHYSE also shows an underestimation of peaks, variation between seeds is small.

Both HBV's and HYMOD's 20 random seeds can visually be grouped into a *peaking* and a *missing* band. Comparing the Saltina peak hydrographs for both models, for example (see Figures 4a and 6a), a number of hydrographs closely follow the best seed, while a smaller group remains nearly flat. Neither model has this behaviour in all the catchments; but in those that do, there are no more than two distinct groups (not taking into account single outliers). There is also variation in HMETS' seeds, though a grouping pattern can not be clearly established (see Figure 5a). HBV and HYMOD have groups in the Ticino, Broye, Rhône, Dischmabach, Saltina and Venoge catchments; HBV additionally in the Thur, Sitter and Lonza catchments; HYMOD also in the Weisse Lütchine catchment. Some grouping is visible in minimal events, though their differences are less pronounced due to smaller discharges. For example, HYMOD/Saltina or MOHYSE/Ticino show groups (see Figures 6b and 7b). In HYMOD/Saltina, however, the groups do not actually differ in discharge, but rather in the hydrograph ascent subsequent to the minimal event. While one group mimics the slight dampening before the more pronounced ascent, a second group of seeds misses these characteristics entirely and exhibits only a weak climb. The recognition of a grouping pattern in the 20 random seeds is to some extent subjective, since it has only been carried out visually. More groups may be present at other zoom levels and different times.

For all following calculations and analyses, the hydrograph with the highest $KG_{E_{np}}$ during the calibration period is selected among the 20 random seeds for each catchment. Therefore, each catchment is assigned a time series of streamflow observations and one simulation hydrograph per model, resulting in six hydrographs per catchment. The optimal parameter sets for all 20 random seeds are listed in Tables 18 to 72 in Appendix B.

3.2 Hydrographs

The observed and simulated hydrographs for the calibration and validation periods are depicted in their entirety in Figures 8 and 9, respectively, both aggregated to monthly means. In the Broye catchment, HBV's first monthly mean surpasses that of the observation's more than three-fold, being far higher than those of any other month for that catchment. Up to 1991, the performance of the other four models seems to degrade slowly in the Massa catchment and from 1992 on neither

(a) Maximum runoff events.

(b) Minimum runoff events.

Figure 3: Hydrographs for events with highest and lowest runoff during calibration period for GR4J. Observation (—), seed with highest calibration KGE (---) and other seeds (.....).

(a) Peak runoff events.

(b) Low runoff events.

Figure 4: Hydrographs for events with highest and lowest runoff during calibration period for HBV. Observation (—), seed with highest calibration KGE (---) and other seeds (.....).

(a) Maximum runoff events.

(b) Minimum runoff events.

Figure 5: Hydrographs for events with highest and lowest runoff during calibration period for HMETS. Observation (—), seed with highest calibration KGE (---) and other seeds (···).

(a) Maximum runoff events.

(b) Minimum runoff events.

Figure 6: Hydrographs for events with highest and lowest runoff during calibration period for HYMOD. Observation (—), seed with highest calibration KGE (---) and other seeds (.....).

(a) Maximum runoff events.

(b) Minimum runoff events.

Figure 7: Hydrographs for events with highest and lowest runoff during calibration period for MOHYSE. Observation (—), seed with highest calibration KGE (---) and other seeds (····).

of them is able to at least somewhat approach peak discharges. Compared to the observations, simulations over these later years remain more or less flat. HBV, on the other hand, mimics the hydrographs very closely during calibration and only starts to grossly overestimate peaks after two years of validation. All five models perform poorly in these conditions.

HBV and, to a lesser extent, GR4J both deal well with hydrographs that have very low winter flows compared to summer peaks. HYMOD exhibits a tendency to require around one year until it reaches its optimum in terms of being able to mimic the hydrograph pattern. While it has a general tendency to underestimate peak volumes and timing, this is more pronounced during the entirety of 1981. Figures 10a and 10b show observations along with simulations for each catchment within a 20-day period around the dates of maximal discharge in the calibration and validation period, respectively. Figures 11a and 11b show the same for the minimal discharges during these periods.

Figure 8: Hydrographs for calibration period; monthly means. Observation (—) and simulations of GR4J (- - -), HBV (· · · · ·), HMETs (- · - · -), HYMOD (- - - -) and MOHYSE (- - - -).

Figure 8: (cont.) Hydrographs for calibration period; monthly means. Observation (—) and simulations of GR4J (- - -), HBV (· · · · ·), HMETs (- · - · -), HYMOD (---) and MOHYSE (- · - · -).

Figure 9: Hydrographs for validation period; monthly means. Observation (—) and simulations of GR4J (- - -), HBV (· · ·), HMETs (- · - ·), HYMOD (— — —) and MOHYSE (- - - -).

Figure 9: (cont.) Hydrographs for validation period; monthly means. Observation (—) and simulations of GR4J (- - -), HBV (· · ·), HMET5 (- · - ·), HYMOD (— — —) and MOHYSE (- - - -).

A visual comparison of the peak events and the daily mean runoff values prior to and after that date for each catchment, as depicted in Figure 10a for the minimum flows during calibration and Figure 10b during validation follows. For the peak event in the Massa catchment during calibration, only HBV is able to generate a hydrograph that to some extent mirrors observations. None of the other models produce similar results. HBV, however, not only is able to approach the absolute value of peak discharge, but also represents the dynamics prior to and after the event. The same observation can be made for the peak event during validation, albeit with the caveat that from August 17th 2003 onwards, HBV grossly overestimates discharge.

The peak discharge of the Broye catchment during calibration is closely followed by a second, albeit smaller peak a few days later. While all 5 models realize the beginning of the hydrograph ascent, they each conflate the two distinct peaks into a single one, whose timing all but HYMOD get about right. The subsequent minor peak on the descending end, all five models simulate as a dampening of the decline. A similar situation during calibration presents itself at the peak of the Sitter, Thur and, to a lesser extent, the Dischmabach catchments: peak discharge for the period is either preceded or followed by a second peak with a time difference of a few days. In stark contrast to the Broye catchment, however, these second peaks are replicated as such, albeit with time lags (especially HYMOD) or a mismatch between simulated and observed absolute discharge. In these three catchments (not including Broye), GR4J has to be mentioned as mimicking both timing and extent of minor and major peaks well. The minor peaks following the major one in the same catchments during validation are replicated well for the Thur, Ticino and Sitter catchments. In the Dischmabach and Rhône catchments, on the other hand, no model is able to recreate observation dynamics.

The following visual inspection of the hydrographs during low flow conditions and the recession from the peaks prior to that is carried out using Figure 11a for the minimum flow in the calibration period and Figure 11b for the validation period, respectively. It is evident that GR4J has a general tendency to overestimate the lowest daily mean runoffs during both calibration and validation. Only in the Saltina and Sitter catchments is this not the case. The other four models, in contrast, have no clear tendency for over- or underestimation. In the Broye, Thur and Venoge catchments, HYMOD overestimates the slight peaks interrupting recession periods leading up to the date of lowest runoff, a behaviour somewhat shared with GR4J, HBV and HMETS, though the former's extent of overestimation stands out. MOHYSE's ability to mimic low flow conditions during calibration has to be highlighted; during validation, though, it overestimates low flows in the Lonza and Weisse Lütschine catchments. HBV's hydrographs in the days surrounding the date of lowest flow exhibit a pattern of quick reaction, which is often more pronounced than actual observations (see for example Broye and Weisse Lütschine for both periods). During validation, HBV produces major peaks prior to the low flow dates, which are followed by extremely sharp drops of up to roughly $150 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ within a few days (HBV/Massa).

Taking the means of monthly averaged flows separately for each month allows for a comparison of the abilities to reproduce regime characteristics, as depicted in Figure 12. There are two catchments that are dominated by winter discharge, i.e. where there is a significant drop in monthly mean runoff in summer: Broye and Venoge. Compared to the Ticino or Weisse Lütschine (where summer discharge dominates), the differences are less pronounced, however. Venoge, for example, has the highest mean runoffs in April with a little more than $6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, dropping to roughly $1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in August. The Weisse Lütschine, on the other hand, has a ten-fold increase from the winter low of around $2 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $22 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ during calibration and $18 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the validation period. For both the Broye and Venoge catchment, only HBV and MOHYSE are able to mimic observations, although they both place the highest mean monthly runoffs in January instead of spring. While GR4J, HMETS and HYMOD realise the dent representing the summer minimum during calibration, they completely miss the characteristics in validation, inverting it in the Broye catchment and flattening it for the Venoge. It is evident that all models are able to simulate the summer dominated hydrographs for the Weisse Lütschine and other similar catchments (see e.g. Dischmabach or Ticino) fairly well, they even reproduce Ticino's dampening in summer (August for calibration, September for validation). Lonza and Rhône have very similar observation hydrographs that are well replicated in form, though not in extent of mean monthly runoffs. Only HBV excels for both catchment in calibration and validation; GR4J performs well during Lonza's calibration and HMETS, HYMOD and MOHYSE all underestimate the extent of peak discharge. All models struggle somewhat with the Thur catchment, as they do not simulate the less pronounced difference between summer and winter well, though HBV and MOHYSE

(a) Calibration period.

(b) Validation period.

Figure 10: Hydrographs for events with highest runoff during calibration and validation period. Observation (—) and simulations of GR4J (- - -), HBV (· · · · ·), HMETS (- · - · -), HYMOD (- · - · -) and MOHYSE (- · - · -).

(a) Calibration period.

(b) Validation period.

Figure 11: Hydrographs for events with lowest runoff during calibration and validation period. Observation (—) and simulations of GR4J (- - -), HBV (· · · · ·), HMETS (- · - · -), HYMOD (- - - -) and MOHYSE (- · - · -).

follow the observations slightly better. GR4J, HMETS and HYMOD create too high a distinction between the two seasons. For example, HMETS' difference between winter low and summer peak flows for the validation period in the Thur catchment more than triples mean monthly runoff (from $22 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $76 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), while the observations only increase from $37 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in November to $59 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in March. Finally, none of the five models tested are able to mimic Massa's regime during the validation period, though HBV is able to follow observations well during calibration. In both periods GR4J, HMETS, HYMOD and MOHYSE underestimate the summer peak flows, while all but GR4J during calibration exhibit near-perfect approach of winter low flow conditions.

It has to be mentioned that HMETS has no internal routine to guarantee that discharge values are not negative. This has indeed led to several mean daily runoff values being simulated as below zero by HMETS. All negative values have been assessed individually and judged to be of minor significance (all smaller than $-10^{-12} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$).

3.3 Performance Metrics

For each catchment and conceptual model, the model run with the highest KGE_{np} during the calibration period was chosen out of 20 runs with different random seeds. Metrics for the validation period were then computed with this set of parameters. Figures 13 to 16 show the KGE_{np} values plus their dynamics (R_s), variability (α) and volume (β) components, respectively, for each catchment and conceptual model during calibration and validation period; corresponding data values are found in Tables 10 to 13. Additionally, RMSE, Percent Bias and Volumetric Efficiency are depicted in Figures 17 to 19, with data listed in Tables 14 to 16.

Comparing the KGE_{np} values in Table 10 (see Figure 13 for a visual comparison), HBV's performance stands out, with only the HBV/Massa model performing below 0.75 during validation; its heavy drop from 0.92 during calibration to -0.39 is the strongest of all models. Generally, KGE_{np} values in the Massa catchment do not exceed 0.33 during validation (Massa/HMETS). While GR4J does not perform as well as HBV, its validation results (except GR4J/Massa) are above 0.5, showing a robustness that is lacking in HMETS, HYMOD and MOHYSE, which all have validation score ranges from -0.01 (HYMOD/Broye) to values around 0.75 (MOHYSE/Weisse Lüttschine) up to 0.89 for HMETS/Weisse Lüttschine. In the two catchments, where summer runoffs are considerably lower than winter runoffs – Broye and Venoge – HYMOD produces KGE_{np} scores around zero, in both cases dropping around 0.5 counts from calibration to validation. No other performance is nearly as low. Not considering the already mentioned Massa catchment, HMETS/Venoge scores third lowest with a validation score of 0.34 (from 0.66 in calibration). In a number of catchments, KGE_{np} values drop more from calibration to validation than in others, such as in Broye, Lonza, Saltina, Sitter and Venoge as well as, though to a lesser extent, in the Thur catchment. Massa was not included in this list, as its calibration metrics are already fairly low. Moreover, HBV's drops are not nearly as significant as those of the other models' (not considering Massa). Its heaviest losses are in the Ticino, where its KGE_{np} is reduced from 0.83 to 0.75. Finally, the numbers in Table 10 highlight clearly that HBV generally performs best, having more performances where it compares better within a catchment. Distinctions between GR4J and MOHYSE are somewhat more blurred; both have better and worse performances. However, behind them HMETS seems to follow, with HYMOD placing 5th, due in large parts to its bad scores in Broye and Venoge.

Considering that KGE_{np} can be decomposed into its three parts α , β and R_s , it is worth having a closer look at the respective results: As the first component, R_s values are summarized in Table 11 and depicted in Figure 14. They do not exceed 1, with HMETS and MOYHSE being nearest in the Dischmabach catchment during calibration (both 0.94) and HBV/Lonza, as well as HBV/Weisse Lüttschine during validation (0.93). GR4J only has a single catchment, where its R_s scores exceed 0.9 (Dischmabach), the other four models all have several. HBV generally exhibits the most robust behaviour, with only the Ticino catchment being below 0.8 (0.77 during validation). HYMOD shows the lowest values for validation with 0.54 in Venoge, but it also performs below 0.6 in the Broye (0.58) and the Lonza (0.58), a value shared by HMETS/Venoge, all in the validation period. HYMOD/Lonza's drop of 0.34 from 0.92 to 0.58 is the sharpest of all models. No catchment scores consistently near 1 in either period, which is in contrast to α and β . Dynamics in Broye and Venoge is not mimicked too well.

(a) Calibration period.

(b) Validation period.

Figure 12: Hydrological Regimes. Observation (—) and simulations of GR4J (---), HBV (.....), HMETS (-.-.-), HYMOD (-.-.-.-) and MOHYSE (-.-.-.-).

GR4J/Massa has the lowest α performance with 0.59 (see Table 12 and Figure 15) during its validation period of Massa, where MOHYSE also scores below 0.7 (0.66). No other model configuration has landed below 0.7 in either period. HBV again exhibits the highest consistency, though HMETS also performs consistently above 0.8. Two models reach near-perfect scores during validation: GR4J/Sitter and MOHYSE/Ticino; Their 0.98 values are only slightly below the optimum of 1. Although Massa has the lowest α values of the eleven tested catchments, this is not the case for the HBV and HMETS models (both above 0.8). There are only five validation scores below 0.8 (HYMOD and MOHYSE, both in Lonza and Massa; GR4J also Massa), indicating a higher ability of the models to represent the variability of the observation hydrographs.

β values, however, spread much more widely below and above 1 (see Table 13 and Figure 16). The three highest surpass the fourth (HMETS/Venoge with 1.50) by a margin of at least 0.36 (HYMOD/Venoge with 1.86) up to 0.87 (HBV/Massa with 2.37). In their middle lies HYMOD/Broye with 1.92. These three models also show the starkest contrasts between calibration and validation with a jump of +0.85, +1.36 and +0.92, respectively. The lowest values are shared among HMETS, HYMOD and MOHYSE for the Massa catchment (all 0.34 in validation). They also perform below 0.5 for the Rhône catchment. At Massa, none of the models perform well, with GR4J having a metric score of 0.45. Calibration and validation β values in the Ticino catchment for all models are very near 1, with HYMOD being the farthest away (1.09). The same is true for the Broye, Saltina, Sitter, Thur and Venoge catchments, albeit only during calibration.

Furthermore, the Root Mean Squared Errors listed in Table 14 and visualized in Figure 17, which are all in the same dimension as observations and simulations, range from $0.95 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for HMETS/Dischmabach (validation) to $60.07 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for HBV/Massa (validation), the latter thus exhibiting the starkest contrast between calibration and validation, adding an RMSE of $50.04 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ between the two periods. Of the total 55 model/catchment configurations, 22 (40 %) improve their RMSE from calibration to validation, the biggest change being HBV/Broye with $-2.51 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Additionally, Percent Bias values listed in Table 15 and visualized in Figure 18 mimic the trends presented by β (see Table 13): HBV/Massa has the strongest bias with -137.28% (down from -1% during calibration), followed by HYMOD/Broye and HYMOD/Venoge with -91.51% (down from 0.49%) and -86.00% (down from -1.19%), respectively. With the Massa catchment as an exception, HBV does not exhibit as strong PBias values as the other models (from -16.27% for Lütshine to 9.88% for Venoge; both validation). The Massa catchment has the lowest values, as it did for β . HYMOD tends to do worse than HMETS and MOHYSE.

Finally, looking at Volumetric Efficiencies in Table 16 and Figure 19, the results indicate that Massa has the lowest values from 0.11 (GR4J/Massa) to 0.21 (HYMOD/Massa), with the notable exception of HMETS/Massa (0.60), which increases its skill score by 0.11 points from calibration to validation. However, as noted above, the comparison is only valid within catchments. HBV consistently performs better than the other four models, except in Massa. Furthermore, MOHYSE also scores higher than GR4J in most catchments during validation (only in Lonza and Saltina are its values lower). The difference between GR4J/Massa and HMETS/Massa is the strongest with 0.49 (0.11 vs. 0.60, respectively).

Table 10: KG_{np} for calibration and validation period for each catchment, based on model run with highest calibration KG_{np} value of 20 runs.

		GR4J	HBV	HMETS	HYMOD	MOHYSE
Broye	Calibration	0.69	0.86	0.67	0.53	0.81
	Validation	0.57	0.84	0.55	-0.01	0.83
Dischma	Calibration	0.91	0.88	0.76	0.72	0.74
	Validation	0.90	0.84	0.78	0.77	0.76
Lonza	Calibration	0.82	0.90	0.60	0.58	0.59
	Validation	0.57	0.85	0.49	0.37	0.43
Lütschine	Calibration	0.78	0.89	0.84	0.80	0.81
	Validation	0.68	0.81	0.89	0.77	0.75
Massa	Calibration	0.48	0.92	0.40	0.35	0.36
	Validation	0.28	-0.39	0.33	0.26	0.22
Rhône	Calibration	0.74	0.88	0.49	0.47	0.48
	Validation	0.69	0.82	0.44	0.44	0.44
Saltina	Calibration	0.80	0.87	0.79	0.83	0.87
	Validation	0.52	0.80	0.46	0.59	0.55
Sitter	Calibration	0.86	0.85	0.85	0.78	0.84
	Validation	0.59	0.82	0.60	0.63	0.60
Thur	Calibration	0.73	0.87	0.77	0.67	0.83
	Validation	0.66	0.84	0.69	0.50	0.80
Ticino	Calibration	0.70	0.83	0.80	0.77	0.82
	Validation	0.65	0.75	0.74	0.72	0.76
Venoge	Calibration	0.72	0.86	0.66	0.50	0.83
	Validation	0.58	0.84	0.34	0.02	0.82

Table 11: Dynamics (r_s) component for calibration and validation period for each catchment, based on model run with highest calibration KG_{np} value of 20 runs.

		GR4J	HBV	HMETS	HYMOD	MOHYSE
Broye	Calibration	0.69	0.87	0.68	0.54	0.88
	Validation	0.62	0.86	0.61	0.58	0.88
Dischma	Calibration	0.92	0.93	0.93	0.91	0.94
	Validation	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.92
Lonza	Calibration	0.86	0.92	0.93	0.92	0.92
	Validation	0.80	0.93	0.86	0.58	0.70
Lütschine	Calibration	0.79	0.92	0.86	0.84	0.86
	Validation	0.76	0.93	0.91	0.82	0.81
Massa	Calibration	0.79	0.92	0.87	0.80	0.82
	Validation	0.80	0.89	0.91	0.82	0.75
Rhône	Calibration	0.85	0.89	0.92	0.91	0.92
	Validation	0.83	0.90	0.89	0.88	0.89
Saltina	Calibration	0.81	0.90	0.85	0.85	0.88
	Validation	0.66	0.85	0.60	0.69	0.67
Sitter	Calibration	0.86	0.86	0.87	0.80	0.86
	Validation	0.61	0.82	0.65	0.65	0.66
Thur	Calibration	0.74	0.88	0.79	0.68	0.84
	Validation	0.66	0.85	0.71	0.72	0.81
Ticino	Calibration	0.71	0.84	0.82	0.78	0.82
	Validation	0.65	0.77	0.75	0.74	0.76
Venoge	Calibration	0.73	0.88	0.66	0.50	0.86
	Validation	0.64	0.89	0.58	0.54	0.88

Table 12: Variability (α) component for calibration and validation period for each catchment, based on model run with highest calibration $KG_{E_{np}}$ value of 20 runs.

		GR4J	HBV	HMETS	HYMOD	MOHYSE
Broye	Calibration	0.97	0.96	0.92	0.91	0.86
	Validation	0.96	0.95	0.92	0.89	0.88
Dischma	Calibration	0.96	0.91	0.94	0.94	0.95
	Validation	0.97	0.89	0.92	0.92	0.94
Lonza	Calibration	0.90	0.94	0.95	0.97	0.97
	Validation	0.86	0.95	0.82	0.73	0.74
Lütschine	Calibration	0.91	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.92
	Validation	0.93	0.92	0.94	0.85	0.83
Massa	Calibration	0.67	0.98	0.94	0.83	0.81
	Validation	0.59	0.83	0.92	0.70	0.66
Rhône	Calibration	0.83	0.94	0.95	0.95	0.95
	Validation	0.80	0.92	0.94	0.94	0.94
Saltina	Calibration	0.95	0.91	0.86	0.93	0.95
	Validation	0.90	0.88	0.84	0.92	0.95
Sitter	Calibration	0.98	0.96	0.94	0.91	0.92
	Validation	0.98	0.95	0.94	0.91	0.92
Thur	Calibration	0.93	0.98	0.91	0.92	0.94
	Validation	0.93	0.97	0.91	0.93	0.94
Ticino	Calibration	0.95	0.96	0.93	0.96	0.98
	Validation	0.96	0.94	0.94	0.97	0.98
Venoge	Calibration	0.93	0.94	0.97	0.95	0.90
	Validation	0.89	0.95	0.93	0.89	0.89

Table 13: Volume (β) component for calibration and validation period for each catchment, based on model run with highest calibration $KG_{E_{np}}$ value of 20 runs.

		GR4J	HBV	HMETS	HYMOD	MOHYSE
Broye	Calibration	1.02	0.97	1.01	1.00	0.98
	Validation	1.21	0.93	1.22	1.92	1.00
Dischma	Calibration	1.00	0.99	0.78	0.74	0.75
	Validation	1.04	1.06	0.81	0.81	0.78
Lonza	Calibration	0.98	1.01	0.61	0.59	0.60
	Validation	0.64	1.12	0.55	0.61	0.60
Lütschine	Calibration	1.00	1.04	0.94	0.90	0.91
	Validation	0.80	1.16	1.02	1.03	1.01
Massa	Calibration	0.65	1.01	0.41	0.41	0.41
	Validation	0.45	2.37	0.34	0.34	0.34
Rhône	Calibration	0.86	1.02	0.49	0.48	0.49
	Validation	0.84	1.13	0.46	0.46	0.46
Saltina	Calibration	0.95	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Validation	0.68	1.04	0.67	0.75	0.69
Sitter	Calibration	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.01	1.01
	Validation	0.87	1.00	1.19	1.03	0.81
Thur	Calibration	1.01	1.00	1.02	1.02	1.00
	Validation	1.02	0.96	1.08	1.41	0.97
Ticino	Calibration	1.00	0.97	1.00	1.04	1.00
	Validation	1.02	0.94	1.04	1.09	0.99
Venoge	Calibration	1.03	0.98	1.06	1.01	0.99
	Validation	1.18	0.90	1.50	1.86	0.91

Table 14: Root mean squared error (RMSE) for calibration and validation period for each catchment, based on model run with highest calibration KGE_{np} value of 20 runs.

		GR4J	HBV	HMETS	HYMOD	MOHYSE
Broye	Calibration	7.75	8.54	8.51	10.57	7.05
	Validation	7.62	6.03	8.30	12.93	5.95
Dischma	Calibration	1.08	1.05	0.88	1.04	0.90
	Validation	1.16	1.11	0.95	0.97	0.97
Lonza	Calibration	4.29	3.51	3.50	3.91	3.78
	Validation	4.41	3.70	4.66	4.82	4.67
Lütschine	Calibration	7.48	4.26	5.83	5.32	5.03
	Validation	5.69	4.18	3.53	5.28	4.87
Massa	Calibration	15.66	8.03	15.41	17.30	16.85
	Validation	20.89	60.07	18.85	21.58	21.54
Rhône	Calibration	2.32	1.84	2.62	2.77	2.69
	Validation	2.55	1.79	2.77	2.88	2.84
Saltina	Calibration	1.95	1.63	1.77	1.92	1.44
	Validation	2.04	1.67	2.14	2.00	1.98
Sitter	Calibration	2.20	2.18	2.31	3.52	2.54
	Validation	2.49	2.09	2.70	3.38	2.52
Thur	Calibration	36.45	29.34	35.71	44.00	31.85
	Validation	35.32	28.11	36.17	45.83	29.74
Ticino	Calibration	40.38	32.67	33.08	43.67	31.31
	Validation	38.33	35.21	32.12	39.99	30.55
Venoge	Calibration	2.94	2.92	3.95	4.72	2.74
	Validation	3.15	2.79	4.49	5.93	2.79

Table 15: Percent Bias (PBias) for calibration and validation period for each catchment, based on model run with highest calibration KGE_{np} value of 20 runs.

		GR4J	HBV	HMETS	HYMOD	MOHYSE
Broye	Calibration	-2.24	2.84	-0.85	0.49	1.82
	Validation	-20.63	6.72	-21.77	-91.51	0.45
Dischma	Calibration	-0.04	0.66	22.27	26.00	24.90
	Validation	-3.69	-5.71	19.17	19.43	22.15
Lonza	Calibration	2.29	-0.62	39.18	41.02	40.25
	Validation	35.72	-12.28	45.22	38.97	40.35
Lütschine	Calibration	-0.46	-4.19	6.29	10.12	9.10
	Validation	19.92	-16.27	-2.38	-2.75	-0.55
Massa	Calibration	34.95	-1.00	58.53	59.47	58.87
	Validation	55.12	-137.28	66.02	65.57	66.03
Rhône	Calibration	13.91	-1.67	50.67	51.90	51.18
	Validation	16.25	-13.13	54.21	54.31	54.38
Saltina	Calibration	4.60	0.43	-0.28	0.36	0.41
	Validation	31.70	-4.19	33.35	25.40	30.69
Sitter	Calibration	0.10	0.54	0.38	-0.56	-0.79
	Validation	13.35	-0.13	-18.77	-2.51	19.44
Thur	Calibration	-0.84	0.38	-2.06	-1.77	0.21
	Validation	-2.05	4.19	-7.98	-41.05	3.00
Ticino	Calibration	-0.28	2.86	-0.04	-4.31	-0.34
	Validation	-1.68	6.10	-4.28	-8.73	0.91
Venoge	Calibration	-2.53	1.96	-5.75	-1.19	1.18
	Validation	-18.05	9.88	-49.55	-86.00	8.66

Table 16: Volumetric Efficiency (VE) for calibration and validation period for each catchment, based on model run with highest calibration KG_{np} value of 20 runs.

		GR4J	HBV	HMETS	HYMOD	MOHYSE
Broye	Calibration	0.51	0.56	0.42	0.29	0.59
	Validation	0.46	0.57	0.39	0.36	0.59
Dischma	Calibration	0.67	0.59	0.68	0.62	0.70
	Validation	0.64	0.58	0.64	0.65	0.66
Lonza	Calibration	0.46	0.61	0.61	0.59	0.61
	Validation	0.40	0.64	0.41	0.30	0.36
Lütschine	Calibration	0.47	0.67	0.55	0.56	0.59
	Validation	0.50	0.68	0.69	0.52	0.53
Massa	Calibration	0.24	0.65	0.49	0.35	0.41
	Validation	0.11	0.15	0.60	0.21	0.19
Rhône	Calibration	0.50	0.64	0.67	0.61	0.65
	Validation	0.41	0.66	0.61	0.55	0.58
Saltina	Calibration	0.55	0.68	0.51	0.57	0.66
	Validation	0.48	0.62	0.24	0.43	0.45
Sitter	Calibration	0.67	0.64	0.63	0.45	0.61
	Validation	0.51	0.62	0.52	0.37	0.51
Thur	Calibration	0.55	0.68	0.53	0.44	0.64
	Validation	0.54	0.66	0.51	0.53	0.63
Ticino	Calibration	0.62	0.69	0.67	0.64	0.72
	Validation	0.61	0.65	0.66	0.64	0.69
Venoge	Calibration	0.56	0.61	0.45	0.31	0.60
	Validation	0.47	0.60	0.41	0.37	0.60

Figure 13: KG_{np} values for calibration (+) and validation (x) period of each catchment and model.

Figure 14: Dynamics (r_s) components of KGE_{np} values for calibration (+) and validation (x) of each catchment and model.

Figure 15: Variability (α) components of KGE_{np} values for calibration (+) and validation (x) of each catchment and model.

Figure 16: Volume (β) components of KGE_{np} values for calibration (+) and validation (x) of each catchment and model.

Figure 17: RMSE values for calibration (+) and validation (x) of each catchment and model.

Figure 18: Percent Bias values for calibration (+) and validation (x) of each catchment and model.

Figure 19: Volumetric Efficiency values for calibration (+) and validation (x) of each catchment and model.

4 Discussion

4.1 Random Seeds

GR4J has very little deviation among the hydrographs for all 20 random seeds for every catchment, resulting in a high degree of equifinality among random seeds, a finding in contrast to Troin, Arsenault and Brissette (2015) and Troin, Arsenault, Martel *et al.* (2018), who found higher uncertainty with GR4J than HMETs and MOHYSE. Comparing this with HYMOD, the second model with fewer than 10 parameters, GR4J's behaviour is noteworthy. HYMOD, on the other hand, not only exhibits greater variations between the seeds, but also shows grouping of them. To investigate further, it was ruled out that parameters might be confined too much within their upper and lower limits in the calibration phase by having a closer look at the evolution of parameter values over all iteration rounds. The chosen limits therefore are deemed reasonable. Perhaps they are an artefact of the DDS algorithm's method of gradually decreasing the number of parameters that are varied. This might finally result in a few groups of solutions. Testing this or alternative hypotheses about the grouping pattern, however, was outside the scope of this thesis, as only the result with the highest $KG_{E_{np}}$ was used for the following analysis, anyway. Future studies could examine this further by either increasing the number of random seeds to check whether the number of groups increases, utilizing different algorithms to rule out that DDS creates this pattern or analyse the results of a comprehensive pareto-informed approach in order to assess if such grouping also occurs with other multi-objective goals.

4.2 Hydrographs

HBV's initial peak in the Broye catchment (see Figure 8) can be explained with a precipitation event at the beginning of that month, whose observation peak HBV simulates twice as high as the observation and whose duration HBV drags at least into march, when the next event leads to an ascent. To better illustrate this behaviour, the daily mean runoff for the Broye catchment has been plotted up to the date with the next peak interrupting HBV's recession phase (see Figure 20), that is the peak runoff event in the observation on March 8th, 1981. Up to the minor peak a few days before, HBV vastly overestimates daily mean runoff values, receding from a major observation peak on January 3rd. This explains the extremely high monthly mean runoffs at the beginning of the calibration period. Perhaps this is also consistent with Parra *et al.* (2018), who pointed out that HBV exhibited a greater sensitivity to quick runoff processes than HYMOD, in the present case overemphasizing the ascent. The inclusion of a warm-up period might prove to be of value, though this would have to be examined in future studies.

Further investigation into HYMOD's performances in the two catchments with dry spells in summer is warranted, since both experienced significant drops in $KG_{E_{np}}$ and the metrics for the validation period especially stand out (see Table 10 and Figure 13), being around zero for both catchments (-0.01 for Broye; 0.02 for Venoge). This is only undermined by HBV/Massa with -0.39. A closer look at the components of $KG_{E_{np}}$ (see Tables 11 to 13) shows that HYMOD's variability (α) scores are comparable to those of other models in the same catchments (all around 0.9). In fact, it only falls below 0.85 in the Massa and Lonza catchments. Though its dynamics (r_s) values are lowest (0.58 and 0.54 for Broye and Venoge, respectively), HMETs' are only slightly higher (0.61 and 0.58, respectively). Therefore, its volume (β) components, which are 2nd- and 3rd-largest of all values, seem to be the major contributor to HYMOD's bad performance. Taking into account the huge negative biases of -91.51 % and -86.00 % for Broye and Venoge, respectively (see Table 15), as well as the low Volumetric Efficiencies of 0.36 and 0.37, respectively (see Table 16), additionally taking into consideration the visual hydrograph representations in Figures 8, 9, 11 and 20, it becomes clear that HYMOD vastly overestimates the minor peaks during the drier summer periods, resulting in high β components. Parra *et al.* (2018) highlight HYMOD's inaccuracy in representing peak flows. Furthermore, it has a tendency to be slow, i.e lag in the dating of its events, a finding which has also been confirmed by Parra *et al.* (2018). They recommend using a monthly timescale for HYMOD simulations. Moreover, they highlight larger performance drops from calibration to validation than in HBV, which has also been found in the present thesis.

In the Ticino catchment, the observations exhibit a repeating pattern for the events with the lowest runoffs (see Figure 11). Therefore, a plot with the hydrographs for the first three months of 1999 has been generated with Sundays labelled specifically. As is evident in Figure 20, Sundays stand out by their sharp drop in runoff, preceded by an only slightly higher value on

Saturdays. This may indicate influence of hydropower generation upstream (Gujer, 2007), with power consumption being higher on workdays. Indeed, there are a number of reservoirs within that catchment, among them *Lago di Luzzone*, *Lago di Lucendro*, *Lago di Sella* and *Lago Ritóm*. Indeed, in the station report for the hydrometric gauging station at the catchment outlet in Bellinzona, Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN), 2017 note the influence on the lowest of monthly mean runoffs, while the yearly maxima remain unaffected. Furthermore, Margot *et al.* (1992, own translation) highlight the corresponding river section as “strongly influenced by [hydropower] surges”.

As a fourth example, the performances of HMETS and GR4J shall be dissected for the Dischmabach catchment. There, all five models have good $KG_{E_{np}}$ values above 0.75 for the validation period, with HMETS, HYMOD and MOHYSE even improving their skill. GR4J has 0.9, while HMETS lands 0.78 (see Table 10). Furthermore, a visual inspection of the full hydrographs indicates good correspondence with a slight tendency to underestimate summer peaks (see Figures 8 and 9), while a comparison of the plots for peak and low flow events (see Figures 10 and 11) seems to indicate a tendency of GR4J to overemphasize ascents and descents of time series, or alternatively HMETS to under-represent the extents. Still, the regime plots in Figure 12 are quite similar, with HMETS having slightly lower agreement with the observations. Indeed, the dynamics (r_s) and variability (α) components are very similar between GR4J and HMETS: 0.91 for both (r_s , see Table 11) and 0.97 vs. 0.92, respectively (α , see Table 12). The volume (β) components, however, are somewhat different: 1.04 for GR4J and 0.81 for HMETS, indicating a disagreement in volume (see Table 13). As both models have the same Volumetric Efficiencies of 0.64 (see Table 16), suggesting a good timing, a comparison of Percent Biases is warranted (see Table 15). Indeed, HMETS’ Bias is considerably higher with +19.17%, compared with GR4J’s -3.69%. Thus, HMETS’s simulations of Dischmabach hydrographs seem to underestimate runoff, resulting in its slightly worse performance, a finding which could not have been achieved by a mere visual inspection of Figure 20.

4.3 Performance Metrics

As summarized in Table 10, HBV has consistently higher $KG_{E_{np}}$ scores than the other models, with only a few exceptions. Furthermore, it exhibits the highest robustness from calibration to validation. Perhaps, a part of this can be explained by HBV’s glacier routine (Moore, 1993). In the three catchments with the highest glaciation ratios, Massa with 56.4%, Rhône with 42.8% and Lonza with 24.3%, HBV excels during calibration. HBV/Massa’s drop in validation can be attributed to the aforementioned influence of hydropower. Therefore, HBV’s robustness in Rhône and Lonza might be due to its capability to deal with glaciation. A comparison with other studies also confirms HBV’s robustness, such as in Parra *et al.* (2018). Further analysis could shed a light on this.

HBV has its strongest drop in performance from the calibration to the validation period in the Massa catchment. While the strong influence of hydropower can explain the negative $KG_{E_{np}}$ for validation, its calibration skill of 0.92 stands out, as it is nearly twice as high as GR4J’s value. This could indicate an overfitting to the calibration observations with a correspondingly lower capability to simulate those events, for which the model has not been trained (Efstratiadis and Koutsoyiannis, 2010). This has generally to be expected to some degree. In this case, however, it seems clear that the strong hydropower influence in the catchment led to this performance. Since reservoir level statistics, however, are not available, this could not have been modelled differently.

Considering that time series have, for the sake of consistency, not been log-transformed prior to calculation of the performance metrics, the values in Table 14 have to be taken with a grain of salt. As outlined in Section 2.3.1 and evident from Equation (6), outliers have a higher influence toward total RMSE. Having a closer look at the peak flows of the Ticino and Dischmabach catchments during calibration for example shows a nearly 100-fold higher value for Ticino than Dischmabach. It is not surprising then, that Ticino’s RMSE ($32.67 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is much higher than Dischmabach’s ($1.05 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). This despite both of the catchments having comparable $KG_{E_{np}}$ values. Nonetheless, RMSE can be useful to complement the picture already painted by $KG_{E_{np}}$. Comparing validation RMSE of HBV and HYMOD in the Venoge catchment for example ($2.79 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ vs. $5.93 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively), confirms the analysis already made using the volume (β) component of $KG_{E_{np}}$: that HYMOD is much less able to approach the observation volumes. This finding is complemented by the Percent Biases to add information on the direction of bias, as done in Section 4.2.

Figure 20: Hydrographs of four selected periods. Observation (—) and simulations of GR4J (- - -), HBV (.....), HMETs (- · - ·), HYMOD (- · - · - ·) and MOHYSE (- · - · - ·).

To further analyse general tendencies of the five tested models in the change of performance metric values, the value differences have been plotted in Figure 21. For the sake of the following analysis, it was assumed that catchment characteristics and forcing pattern do not change significantly between calibration and validation, allowing us to compare metrics changes for a catchment. This means that the influence of outliers does not change significantly, as could be the case for RMSE, for example, with an increase in extreme flows. There is a general tendency for performances to degrade from calibration to validation. Some models improve their scores in a few catchments (such as HYMOD's R_s and β values), while others tend not to do so (such as MOHYSE). Performances in the Dischmabach and Rhône catchments tend to be among the most robust ones. On the other hand, Massa has the highest changes, due to HBV's sharp metric drop.

When performance metrics for each catchment's validation period are ranked, as is shown in Figure 22, this allows for an easier visual comparison. For each metric, 55 total ranks had to be filled (5 models x 11 catchments). As an example, HBV ranked 1st in the Broye catchment and HYMOD 5th (KGE_{np} of 0.84 vs. -0.01, respectively. See Table 10). For KGE_{np} , HBV thus has seven first, three second and a single fifth rank. Therefore, comparing the rankings of KGE_{np} , $RMSE$, $PBias$ and VE shows that HBV tends to amass the most first ranks, while HYMOD does not do so once.

Figure 21: Performance metrics changes from calibration to validation of each catchment for GR4J (●), HBV (●), HMETs (●), HYMOD (●) and MOHYSE (●).

Aggregating the ranks to a single rank for each metric, the spider plots in Figure 23 were produced. They are created and interpreted as follows. Since HBV had the highest mean rank for KGE_{np} when comparing the eleven catchments, as done above (see Figure 22), it scored first on the aggregated KGE_{np} ranking in Figure 23b. Its seven first, three second and one fifth rank resulted in a mean rank of 1.6; HYMOD's mean rank, on the other hand, is 3.9. Hence, HBV ranked first in Figure 23b and HYMOD ranked last. Overall, HBV ranks first in all metrics for the validation period, improving one rank for β and VE, at the cost of GR4J. HYMOD, on the other hand is consistent in its low ranks. Furthermore, GR4J's comparative strengths seem to be the variability and volume representation, as assessed by α and β as well as the Volumetric Efficiency (VE). GR4J's good performance was also found in Perrin *et al.* (2003), Pagano *et al.* (2010) and Pushpalatha *et al.* (2011). Where GR4J ranks lower (dynamics R_s , PBIAS and RMSE), MOHYSE steps in and ranks second, a tendency not found by Martel *et al.* (2017, p. 1312), who note that HMETs was „significantly“ better than MOHYSE in their study. What has been discussed above is summarized in these spider plots: HBV's performances tend to be better and more robust than those of the other four models. Depending on the focus of the calibration, the second-best choice would be either GR4J (for volume and variability) or MOHYSE (for dynamics). There are limitations to the ranking approach, of course: 1. If a modeller wanted to work with monthly mean runoff time series, HYMOD might be a better candidate, as recommended by Parra *et*

Figure 22: Rank distribution of GR4J, HBV, HMETs, HYMOD and MOHYSE for performance metrics: (a) KGE_{np} , (b) RMSE, (c) PBias and (d) VE. Ranking for validation period. 1st (dark green), 2nd (light green), 3rd (yellow), 4th (orange) and 5th rank (red).

al. (2018). Indeed, this study also observed a somewhat slower response of HYMOD, though investigating this behaviour in more detail would have been beyond the scope of this thesis and would need to be the focus of additional research; 2. the of ranking performance metrics into five categories is useful to reduce complexity, but also loses important information. For example, the KGE_{np} values of HBV, HMETs, HYMOD and MOHYSE for Ticino's validation period are all within 0.04 counts (0.72 for HYMOD to 0.76 for MOHYSE). Nonetheless, ranking gives MOHYSE the first place and HYMOD the fourth. Contrasting this to the metric range between the first and fourth rank for Venoge's validation period (from HBV's 0.84 to HMETs' 0.34) highlights that large differences in metric value ranges may still result in the same kind of statement, that some model ranks first and another model ranks fourth, regardless of the way these ranks were produced. Therefore, one should not write HYMOD off entirely, based on the ranks in Figure 23, but rather assess its individual strengths and weaknesses and whether they might be compatible with the scope of the investigation. Furthermore, catchments cannot be compared directly, since calculation of the metrics is dependent on catchment characteristics (Schaeffli and Gupta, 2007; Criss and Winston, 2008; Althoff and Rodrigues, 2021). Ranking rather serves to give a simple visual comparison rather than a detailed comparison of the metrics.

Figure 23: Overall ranking of HBV (●), GR4J (●), HYMOD (●), MOHYSE (●) and HMETS (●) for performance metrics KGE_{np} , its variability (α), volume (β) and dynamics (R_s) components, PBias, RMSE, as well as VE. (a) Calibration period and (b) Validation period. Ranks are based on mean rank of 11 catchments. Where more than one model had the same value, each was assigned the higher rank.

4.4 Study limitations

Raven’s emulation capabilities of the five tested conceptual models proved valuable in this study. Nonetheless, it has to be mentioned that taking these fixed model structures as they are templated (except minor changes) is also limiting, since it does not make use of Raven’s full modular capabilities. Testing the full set of features (e.g. offering to pick and choose model components) was clearly beyond the scope of this thesis. Futures studies, however, might want to deepen their investigation into that direction.

Optimization using a single objective can contain several sub-objectives, as is the case with the non-parametric KGE and its components in this study. However, optimization has been carried out using an aggregate of the three components α , β and R_s . Additionally, analysis of their respective values as well as other performance metrics has only been performed afterwards, not including them individually in the optimization process. Although the optimization runs in this study are hence limited to a single objective (KGE_{np}), this performance metric has been chosen to at least partially address the issue, as it consists of three components that can be used to analyse volume, variability and dynamics performance. A more thorough and comprehensive approach, however, might take into account multiple objectives, for example with a pareto-informed method, which would yield a *Pareto front* of optimal solutions instead of a single parameter set.

Since the focus of this thesis has not been on conducting a comprehensive investigation of the parameter space of each model and catchment combination, there is a chance that only a local optimum, but not the global optimum was found. While doing 20 runs with different random seeds for each model increases the chances of finding a global optimum, it is not guaranteed. Furthermore, the DDS algorithm was not designed to find global optima, but “good” solutions efficiently (Tolson and Shoemaker, 2007), which has been useful in this study. Therefore, no inference about the topography of the parameter spaces can be made; neither can any one solution be declared a global optimum.

This study compared the ability of five conceptual models emulated in Raven to generate hydrographs. Although some of the results have been promising, a comparison with physically-based hydrological models would be of particular interest. There might also be merit in the replacement of some of the process algorithms used in a particular conceptual model emulated in Raven with more physically-informed alternatives.

As all five models were run in lumped mode, no inference could be made on Raven’s capabilities to distribute parameters. Further investigation is warranted by, for example, running HBV in semi-distributed mode using elevation bands.

The parameters in this thesis have been assumed constant in time, as have some HRU characteristics. Glaciation ratio, for example, has been taken from the latest SGI2016 glacier inventory. In reality, however, glaciers are generally retreating in Switzerland; a fact, which future studies should reflect by implementing glaciation ratio in Raven input files as a time series, rather than a constant. This also extends to other data such as forestation.

Due to influence of hydropower generation, one catchment originally anticipated for testing had to be excluded from the study. The Massa catchment was included nonetheless, as it was deemed helpful to have a single disturbed catchment as comparison. Furthermore, analysis showed that the runoff in the Ticino catchment also experienced a regular pattern of upstream hydropower generation. This study did not take into account any reservoirs in the modelling process, it has to be noted. No general assumptions about Raven's or any of the tested models' capabilities to handle hydropower influence can be made. There might be potential to use Raven's reservoir module in future studies.

5 Conclusion

In the present study, hydrographs for eleven Swiss catchments were simulated using the five conceptual models GR4J, HBV, HMETs, HYMOD and MOHYSE. To facilitate input file generation, model calibration and analysis of the results, the Raven hydrological modelling framework was used, which is able to emulate the structure of the five conceptual models. Combining Raven, the Ostrich parameter optimization software and Python, hydrographs along with a number of performance metrics were generated.

So as to simplify pre-processing, Raven input file generation and analysis of the generated results, a Python library – Raven-Tools – was written, which contains several functions that complete these tasks. Raven-Tools is designed to be used with the files used in this study, but may also be useful in other cases. It is written in Python, open-source and hosted on a public GitHub repository. For each catchment, five Raven model descriptions with respective input files were set up for each of the five conceptual models, resulting in 55 unique configurations. Each model was run 20 times, using different random seeds. Parameter optimization was carried out with the Ostrich optimization software, using the dynamically dimensioned search (DDS) algorithm with a budget of 5000 runs. A split-sample approach was used, dividing the dataset into calibration and validation periods of equal length. For the hydrograph comparison, only the model run with the highest non-parametric Kling-Gupta efficiency during calibration was chosen.

The results showed the value of using Raven to compare the five conceptual models. They all were able to produce hydrographs similar to observations, though differing in their degree of similarity. GR4J exhibited the highest degree of equifinality between the 20 runs with different random seeds. HBV's performances were the robustest, it only had one significant struggle during the validation period in the Massa catchment, whose runoff characteristics are highly influenced by a large hydropower production reservoir. Contrasting GR4J and HYMOD showed how the former had a tendency to overemphasize ascents and descents of time series and that the latter under-represented the very same. HYMOD in general fared worst of the five models. Its seemingly too slow reaction to precipitation events was also confirmed by other literature. Ranking the five conceptual models, finally, showed that HBV excelled in the four performance metrics KGE_{np} , RMSE, Percent Bias and Volumetric Efficiency. GR4J and MOHYSE ranked second, both being stronger in different metrics. The Python library developed to create Raven input files, pre-process data and analyse the results – Raven-Tools – proved to be valuable in a streamlining of these tasks, with a special merit of increased efficiency.

Since HBV was run in lumped mode in this thesis, Raven's ability to emulate the model in semi-distributed mode was not assessed. This was due to a bug in the pre-processing of elevation bands. Addressing this might be valuable in future research to be able to have a look at Raven's capabilities of distributing parameters. The Raven-Tools library could prove useful for this task.

The current discussions on the need for an update to the split-sample approach could be augmented with a systematic investigation of the optimal calibration/validation scheme. Work has been done by Arsenault, Brisette *et al.* (2018), Zheng *et al.* (2018) and Shen, Tolson *et al.* (2022), the latter of which also utilizing Raven for their analysis. Their study areas were in North America and Australia. Discussion are ongoing and more insights are needed for the development of alternative approaches. Raven is flexible enough to allow a systematic comparison of various splitting schemes or the implementation of new ones, as has been shown. For the Swiss context, Raven-Tools could be adapted to generate the required input files efficiently; with modifications it could also be used in different contexts. Thus, Raven's flexible working structure might prove very valuable to contribute to this ongoing research. Furthermore, this thesis focussed on five conceptual models, using a glacier (where applicable) and non-glacier hydrological unit for each catchment. Moreover, catchment characteristics were fed to Raven to the extent that was required for each of the conceptual models. Following studies could add to this by building more complex models. Raven is able to emulate HBV in semi-distributed mode, for example, through the use of elevation bands. Additionally, the UBC Watershed model is also available in semi-distributed fashion. Other models could be implemented, since Raven is open-source. The most promising aspect of increasing model complexity, however, might be Raven's capability of blending model components. In version 3.0, users could theoretically generate roughly 8×10^{12} model configurations (Mai, Craig and Tolson, 2020). Moreover, process representations can be blended with a weighted average. Thus, modellers are able to optimize *function spaces*, not merely *parameter spaces*, as Gharari *et al.* (2021) suggested. Spieler *et al.* (2020), Mai, Craig and Tolson

(2020) and Chlumsky, Mai *et al.* (2023) have conducted studies on model structure optimization using Raven, the latter two of which by blending structure components. This approach therefore switches from mutually exclusive process representation algorithms to a weighted combination of them, with a continuous range of weights allowed. However, much more work is needed on the exploration of the *function space* as an alternative to the *parameter space*. Furthermore, Raven-Tools provides methods to prepare data and input files for a Swiss context. Finally, the extended Sobol' sensitivity analysis *xSSA* performed by Mai, Craig and Tolson (2020) seems to be promising in the investigation of sensitivities of hydrologic processes, also varying with time. Their method is promising in the quest to learn more about the functioning of hydrologic processes, as it allows several categories of hypotheses to be tested simultaneously. It allows assessing the sensitivities of model parameters, process representations and hydrologic processes all at once. Raven has already be shown by Mai, Craig and Tolson (2020) to be up to this task and it could be employed in future research into these topics in Swiss contexts.

5.1 Code availability

The source code of the *Raven-Tools* Python library is hosted on GitHub as a public repository, along with limited documentation (Zweifel, 2023)

References

- Abbaspour, Karim C. *et al.* (Feb. 2007). „Modelling Hydrology and Water Quality in the Pre-Alpine/Alpine Thur Watershed Using Swat“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 333.2-4, pp. 413–430. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/cr487k. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169406004835> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Addor, Nans *et al.* (2014). „Robust Changes and Sources of Uncertainty in the Projected Hydrological Regimes of Swiss Catchments“. In: *Water Resources Research* 50.10, pp. 7541–7562. ISSN: 1944-7973. DOI: 10/f24tms. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/2014WR015549> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Althoff, Daniel and Lineu Neiva Rodrigues (Sept. 2021). „Goodness-of-Fit Criteria for Hydrological Models: Model Calibration and Performance Assessment“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 600.126674. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/gm7ppr. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169421007228> (visited on 07/12/2023).
- Andréassian, Vazken *et al.* (Oct. 2014). „Seeking Genericity in the Selection of Parameter Sets: Impact on Hydrological Model Efficiency“. In: *Water Resources Research* 50.10, pp. 8356–8366. ISSN: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/f6qqt4. URL: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1002/2013WR014761> (visited on 18/04/2022).
- Arsenault, Richard, Mélissa Breton-Dufour *et al.* (18th Aug. 2019). „Streamflow Prediction in Ungauged Basins: Analysis of Regionalization Methods in a Hydrologically Heterogeneous Region of Mexico“. In: *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 64.11, pp. 1297–1311. ISSN: 0262-6667, 2150-3435. DOI: 10/ggjddw. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02626667.2019.1639716> (visited on 28/04/2023).
- Arsenault, Richard, François Brissette and Jean-Luc Martel (Nov. 2018). „The Hazards of Split-Sample Validation in Hydrological Model Calibration“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 566, pp. 346–362. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/gfqj4k. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169418307145> (visited on 22/09/2023).
- Arsenault, Richard, Philippe Gatién *et al.* (Oct. 2015). „A Comparative Analysis of 9 Multi-Model Averaging Approaches in Hydrological Continuous Streamflow Simulation“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 529, pp. 754–767. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/f7x4nh. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169415006848> (visited on 20/05/2022).
- Arsenault, Richard, David Huard *et al.* (1st Oct. 2023). „The PAVICS-Hydro Platform: A Virtual Laboratory for Hydroclimatic Modelling and Forecasting Over North America“. In: *Environmental Modelling & Software* 168, p. 105808. ISSN: 1364-8152. DOI: 10/gs869z. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364815223001949> (visited on 26/09/2023).
- Arsenault, Richard, Annie Poulin *et al.* (July 2014). „A Comparison of Stochastic Optimization Algorithms in Hydrological Model Calibration“. In: *Journal of Hydrologic Engineering* 19.7, pp. 1374–1384. ISSN: 1084-0699, 1943-5584. DOI: 10/ghvvg. URL: <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/10.1061/%28ASCE%29HE.1943-5584.0000938> (visited on 12/10/2023).
- Bastola, Satish (2022). „The Regionalization of a Parameter of HYMOD, a Conceptual Hydrological Model, Using Data from Across the Globe“. In: *HydroResearch* 5, pp. 13–21. ISSN: 2589-7578. DOI: 10/gs8693. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2589757822000014> (visited on 19/10/2022).
- Bastola, Satish and Conor Murphy (1st June 2013). „Sensitivity of the Performance of a Conceptual Rainfall–Runoff Model to the Temporal Sampling of Calibration Data“. In: *Hydrology Research* 44.3, pp. 484–494. ISSN: 1998-9563, 2224-7955. DOI: 10/f43ng9. URL: <https://iwaponline.com/hr/article/44/3/484/31071/Sensitivity-of-the-performance-of-a-conceptual> (visited on 13/07/2023).
- Bavay, Mathias *et al.* (Jan. 2009). „Simulations of Future Snow Cover and Discharge in Alpine Headwater Catchments“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 23.1, pp. 95–108. ISSN: 0885-6087, 1099-1085. DOI: 10/fxhwk2. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hyp.7195> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Bergström, Sten (Aug. 1976). *SMHI Rep. RHO 7 - Development and Application of a Conceptual Runoff Model for Scandinavian Catchments*. Sveriges Meteorologiska och Hydrologiska Institut, p. 154. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/255274162_Development_and_Application_of_a_Conceptual_Runoff_Model_for_Scandinavian_Catchments (visited on 02/10/2023).
- (1992). *The HBV Model: Its Structure and Applications*. SMIH Reports Hydrology 4. Norrköping: Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute. 35 pp. URL: https://www.smhi.se/polopoly_fs/1.83592!/Menu/general/extGroup/attachmentColHold/mainCol1/file/RH_4.pdf.

- Beven, Keith (1989). „Changing Ideas in Hydrology - the Case of Physically-Based Models“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 105.1-2, pp. 157–172. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/c8wt7q. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/0022169489901017>.
- (8th Oct. 2002a). „Towards a Coherent Philosophy for Modelling the Environment“. In: *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* 458.2026, pp. 2465–2484. ISSN: 1364-5021, 1471-2946. DOI: 10/cq9dtr. URL: <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rspa.2002.0986> (visited on 26/10/2023).
- (15th Feb. 2002b). „Towards an Alternative Blueprint for a Physically Based Digitally Simulated Hydrologic Response Modelling System“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 16.2, pp. 189–206. ISSN: 0885-6087, 1099-1085. DOI: 10/d5h3b9. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hyp.343> (visited on 26/10/2023).
- (Mar. 2006). „A Manifesto for the Equifinality Thesis“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 320.1-2, pp. 18–36. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/ccx2ks. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S002216940500332X> (visited on 26/10/2023).
- Beven, Keith J. (2000). „Uniqueness of Place and Process Representations in Hydrological Modelling“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 4.2, pp. 203–213. ISSN: 1027-5606. DOI: 10/cm4ffg. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/4/203/2000/>.
- Boyle, Douglas P. (2001). „Multicriteria Calibration of Hydrologic Models“. PhD thesis. Washington, D. C.: University of Arizona. 138 pp. URL: <http://hdl.handle.net/10150/290657> (visited on 08/11/2023).
- Brubaker, Kaye, Albert Rango and William Kustas (Jan. 1996). „Incorporating Radiation Inputs into the Snowmelt Runoff Model“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 10.10, pp. 1329–1343. ISSN: 0885-6087, 1099-1085. DOI: 10/cjsmp4. URL: [https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1085\(199610\)10:10%3C1329::AID-HYP464%3E3.0.CO;2-W](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1085(199610)10:10%3C1329::AID-HYP464%3E3.0.CO;2-W) (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Brunner, Manuela I., Daniel Farinotti *et al.* (30th Oct. 2019). „Future Shifts in Extreme Flow Regimes in Alpine Regions“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 23.11, pp. 4471–4489. ISSN: 1607-7938. DOI: 10/ggdr7. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/23/4471/2019/> (visited on 26/09/2023).
- Brunner, Manuela Irene, Anna E. Sikorska and Jan Seibert (Mar. 2018). „Bivariate Analysis of Floods in Climate Impact Assessments“. In: *Science of The Total Environment* 616–617, pp. 1392–1403. ISSN: 0048-9697. DOI: 10/gc8v7g. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048969717328875> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Bühlmann, Alain and Jan Schwanbeck (2018). „Catchment Characteristics – Interactive Map A04, Hydrological Atlas of Switzerland - Explanatory Text Accompanying the Map“. In: *Hydrological Atlas of Switzerland*. DOI: 10/g8694. URL: <https://boris.unibe.ch/141606/> (visited on 10/11/2023).
- Bundesamt für Landestopografie swisstopo (2022). *swissALTI3D*. GeoTIFF. Version 2022. swisstopo. URL: <https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/de/geodata/height/alti3d.html> (visited on 24/10/2023).
- (8th Mar. 2023). *swissTLM3D*. vector. Version 2.1. 73856ca2-f21d-4cc9-90f6-f3e8375555df@bundesamt-fur-landestopografie-swisstopo. URL: <https://opendata.swiss/en/dataset/swisstlm3d> (visited on 19/12/2023).
- Canadian Hydraulics Centre, National Research Council (9th Dec. 2008). *EnSim Hydrologic Reference Manual*. Canadian Hydraulics Centre, National Research Council. URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20081209094653/http://chc.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca/files/Kenue/Green/GreenKenueManual.pdf> (visited on 18/11/2022).
- Castaneda-Gonzalez, Mariana *et al.* (Oct. 2019). „Sensitivity of Seasonal Flood Simulations to Regional Climate Model Spatial Resolution“. In: *Climate Dynamics* 53.7-8, pp. 4337–4354. ISSN: 0930-7575, 1432-0894. DOI: 10/ggb5f7. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00382-019-04789-y> (visited on 28/04/2023).
- Chen, Jie, François P. Brissette and Robert Leconte (May 2011). „Uncertainty of Downscaling Method in Quantifying the Impact of Climate Change on Hydrology“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 401.3-4, pp. 190–202. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/d6krzx. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169411001351> (visited on 22/09/2023).
- Chlumsky, Robert, James R. Craig *et al.* (16th Sept. 2022). „RavenR V2.1.4: An Open-Source R Package to Support Flexible Hydrologic Modelling“. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 15.18, pp. 7017–7030. ISSN: 1991-9603. DOI: 10/g8697. URL: <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/15/7017/2022/> (visited on 05/10/2023).

- [SW] Chlumsky, Robert, Juliane Mai *et al.* *Rchlumsk/BMSC: BMSC v1.0 Release* version 1.0, 24th Mar. 2021. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4635309, URL: <https://zenodo.org/record/4635309>(visited on 12/10/2023).
- Chlumsky, Robert, Juliane Mai *et al.* (2021b). „Simultaneous Calibration of Hydrologic Model Structure and Parameters Using a Blended Model“. In: *Water Resources Research* 57.5. issn: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/gm4nw2. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2020WR029229>. — (23rd Mar. 2023). *Advancement of a Blended Hydrologic Model for Robust Model Performance*. DOI: 10.5194/hess-2023-69. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/preprints/hess-2023-69/> (visited on 26/09/2023). preprint.
- Clark, Martyn P., Dmitri Kavetski and Fabrizio Fenicia (2011). „Pursuing the Method of Multiple Working Hypotheses for Hydrological Modeling“. In: *Water Resources Research* 47.9. issn: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/fjbjpp. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2010WR009827>.
- Clark, Martyn P., Bart Nijssen *et al.* (2015). „A Unified Approach for Process-Based Hydrologic Modeling: 1. Modeling Concept“. In: *Water Resources Research* 51.4, pp. 2498–2514. issn: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/f7db99. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/2015WR017198>.
- Clark, Martyn P., Bettina Schaefli *et al.* (2016). „Improving the Theoretical Underpinnings of Process-Based Hydrologic Models“. In: *Water Resources Research* 52.3, pp. 2350–2365. issn: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/gg3nc5. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/2015WR017910>.
- Clark, Martyn P., Andrew G. Slater *et al.* (2008). „Framework for Understanding Structural Errors (FUSE): A Modular Framework to Diagnose Differences Between Hydrological Models“. In: *Water Resources Research* 44.12. DOI: 10/chvc6k. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2007WR006735>.
- Coxon, Gemma *et al.* (2019). „DECIPHeR v1: Dynamic fluxEs and Connectivity for Predictions of Hydrology“. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 12.6, pp. 2285–2306. issn: 1991-959X. DOI: 10/ghhwb6. URL: <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/12/2285/2019/>.
- Craig, James R. (2023). *The Raven Hydrological Framework - Utilities*. The Raven Hydrological Framework - Utilities. URL: <http://raven.uwaterloo.ca/Utilities.html> (visited on 12/11/2023).
- Craig, James R., Genevieve Brown *et al.* (July 2020). „Flexible Watershed Simulation with the Raven Hydrological Modelling Framework“. In: *Environmental Modelling & Software* 129.104728. issn: 1364-8152. DOI: 10/gh8jkt. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S136481521931165X?via%3Dihub> (visited on 10/03/2022).
- [SW] Craig, James R. and the Raven Development Team, *The Raven Hydrological Framework* version 3.5, Jan. 2022. UWaterloo. URL: http://raven.uwaterloo.ca/files/v3.5/RavenSource_v3.5.zip(visited on 12/11/2023).
- Craig, James R. and the Raven Development Team (May 2023a). *The Raven Hydrological Framework - Downloads*. the Raven Hydrological Framework - Downloads. URL: <http://raven.uwaterloo.ca/Downloads.html> (visited on 18/12/2023).
- (2023b). *Raven User's and Developer's Manual (Version 3.5)*. URL: <http://raven.uwaterloo.ca> (visited on 14/09/2023).
- Criss, Robert E. and William E. Winston (1st July 2008). „Do Nash Values Have Value? Discussion and Alternate Proposals“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 22.14, pp. 2723–2725. issn: 0885-6087, 1099-1085. DOI: 10/bddpc4. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hyp.7072> (visited on 05/03/2023).
- Dal Molin, Marco, Dmitri Kavetski, Carlo Albert *et al.* (July 2023). „Exploring Signature-Based Model Calibration for Streamflow Prediction in Ungauged Basins“. In: *Water Resources Research* 59.7, e2022WR031929. issn: 0043-1397, 1944-7973. DOI: 10/g8699. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2022WR031929> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Dal Molin, Marco, Dmitri Kavetski and Fabrizio Fenicia (2021). „SuperflexPy 1.3.0: An Open-Source Python Framework for Building, Testing, and Improving Conceptual Hydrological Models“. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 14.11, pp. 7047–7072. issn: 1991-959X. DOI: 10/g87bb. URL: <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/14/7047/2021/>.
- Dal Molin, Marco, Mario Schirmer *et al.* (20th Mar. 2020). „Understanding Dominant Controls on Streamflow Spatial Variability to Set up a Semi-Distributed Hydrological Model: The Case Study of the Thur Catchment“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 24.3, pp. 1319–1345. issn: 1607-7938. DOI: 10/gnkmpm. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/24/1319/2020/> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Dingman, S. Lawrence (2015). *Physical Hydrology*. Third edition. Long Grove, Illinois, USA: Waveland Press, Inc. 643 pp. ISBN: 978-1-4786-1118-9.

- Edijatno and C. Michel (1st Apr. 1989). „Un modèle pluie-débit journalier à trois paramètres“. In: *La Houille Blanche* 75.2, pp. 113–122. ISSN: 0018-6368, 1958-5551. DOI: 10/ddvmm. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1051/lhb/1989007> (visited on 22/09/2023).
- Efstratiadis, Andreas and Demetris Koutsoyiannis (10th Mar. 2010). „One Decade of Multi-Objective Calibration Approaches in Hydrological Modelling: A Review“. In: *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 55.1, pp. 58–78. ISSN: 0262-6667. DOI: 10/fxhmd6. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02626660903526292> (visited on 20/10/2022).
- European Environment Agency (19th Apr. 2016). *EU-DEM*. raster. Version 1.1. 3473589f-0854-4601-919e-2e7dd172ff50. EEA Geospatial Data Catalogue. URL: <https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/3473589f-0854-4601-919e-2e7dd172ff50> (visited on 19/12/2023).
- (2019). *CORINE Land Cover 2012 (Raster 100 m), Europe, 6-Yearly - Version 2020_20u1, May 2020*. GeoTIFF. Version 20.01. European Environment Agency. DOI: 10.2909/A84AE124-C5C5-4577-8E10-511BFE55CC0D. URL: <https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/copernicus/api/records/a84ae124-c5c5-4577-8e10-511bfe55cc0d?language=all> (visited on 10/11/2023).
- eWater Ltd (2020). *GR4J - SRG - Source User Guide 5.4 - eWater Wiki*. GR4J - SRG. URL: <https://wiki.ewater.org.au/display/SD54/GR4J+-+SRG> (visited on 05/10/2023).
- Exercise 5 (2023). *Exercise 5: Parameter Uncertainty*. Exercise 5: Parameter Uncertainty. URL: <http://www.geo.uzh.ch/en/units/h2k/Services/HBV-Model/Exercise-5.html> (visited on 04/05/2023).
- Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) (23rd Nov. 2017). *Ticino - Bellinzona: Rapporto Della Stazione*. Rapporto Della Stazione. Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN). URL: https://www.hydrodaten.admin.ch/documents/Hochwasserstatistikberichte/2020_hq_Bericht.pdf (visited on 12/12/2023).
- Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) (6th Nov. 2023). *Electricity Production Plants*. Web Map Service WMS. ch.bfe.eletrizitaetsproduktionsanlagen. e5a00bdb-5022-4856-ad4a-d1afe7bf38b0: geocat.ch. URL: <https://www.geocat.ch/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/e5a00bdb-5022-4856-ad4a-d1afe7bf38b0> (visited on 01/12/2023).
- Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss (Sept. 2021a). *Documentation of MeteoSwiss Grid-Data Products - Daily Mean, Minimum and Maximum Temperature: TabsD, TminD, TmaxD*. Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss. URL: https://www.meteoswiss.admin.ch/dam/jcr:818a4d17-cb0c-4e8b-92c6-1a1bdf5348b7/ProdDoc_TabsD.pdf (visited on 24/10/2023).
- (Sept. 2021b). *Documentation of MeteoSwiss Grid-Data Products - Daily Precipitation (Final Analysis): RhiresD*. Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss. URL: https://www.meteoswiss.admin.ch/dam/jcr:4f51f0f1-0fe3-48b5-9de0-15666327e63c/ProdDoc_RhiresD.pdf (visited on 24/10/2023).
- Federal Office of Topography swisstopo (2023). *swissALTI3D*. swissALTI3D. URL: <https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/de/geodata/height/alti3d.html> (visited on 06/10/2023).
- Fenicia, F., H. H. G. Savenije *et al.* (2006). „Is the Groundwater Reservoir Linear? Learning from Data in Hydrological Modelling“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 10.1, pp. 139–150. DOI: 10/d94z43. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/10/139/2006/hess-10-139-2006.html> (visited on 12/12/2023).
- Fenicia, Fabrizio, Dmitri Kavetski and Hubert H. G. Savenije (2011). „Elements of a Flexible Approach for Conceptual Hydrological Modeling: 1. Motivation and Theoretical Development“. In: *Water Resources Research* 47.W11510. ISSN: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/cwq96b. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1029/2010WR010174> (visited on 05/10/2023).
- Fenicia, Fabrizio, Hubert H. G. Savenije *et al.* (2008). „Understanding Catchment Behavior Through Stepwise Model Concept Improvement“. In: *Water Resources Research* 44.1. ISSN: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/fprb5x. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2006WR005563>.
- Ferguson, R. I. (June 1999). „Snowmelt Runoff Models“. In: *Progress in Physical Geography: Earth and Environment* 23.2, pp. 205–227. ISSN: 0309-1333, 1477-0296. DOI: 10/czb2zv. URL: <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/030913339902300203> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Fortin, Vincent and Richard Turcotte (10th Jan. 2007). „Le modèle hydrologique MOHYSE“. Notes de cours pour SCA7420. Université du Québec à Montréal: Département des sciences de la terre et de l’atmosphère. URL: <https://docplayer.fr/69668879-Le-modele-hydrologique-mohyse.html> (visited on 05/10/2023).

- [SW] Francois Brissette, *HMETS Hydrological Model* version 1.3.0.0, 25th Sept. 2023. URL: <https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/48069-hmets-hydrological-model>(visited on 25/09/2023).
- Freeze, R.Allan and R.L. Harlan (Nov. 1969). „Blueprint for a Physically-Based, Digitally-Simulated Hydrologic Response Model“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 9.3, pp. 237–258. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/fvxml6. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0022169469900201> (visited on 26/10/2023).
- Fuhrer, Jürg and Karsten Jasper (2012). „Demand and Supply of Water for Agriculture: Influence of Topography and Climate in Pre-Alpine, Mesoscale Catchments“. In: *Natural Resources* 03.03, pp. 145–155. ISSN: 2158-706X, 2158-7086. DOI: 10/g87bf. URL: <http://www.scirp.org/journal/doi.aspx?DOI=10.4236/nr.2012.33019> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Fundel, Felix and Massimiliano Zappa (Sept. 2011). „Hydrological Ensemble Forecasting in Mesoscale Catchments: Sensitivity to Initial Conditions and Value of Reforecasts“. In: *Water Resources Research* 47.9, 2010WR009996. ISSN: 0043-1397, 1944-7973. DOI: 10/fct6dz. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2010WR009996> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Gannon, JP (9th Feb. 2023). *Hydroinformatics at VT*. URL: <https://vt-hydroinformatics.github.io/Hydroinformatics.Bookdown.pdf> (visited on 12/09/2023).
- [SW], *Geopandas/Geopandas* 18th Dec. 2023. GeoPandas. URL: <https://github.com/geopandas/geopandas>(visited on 19/12/2023).
- Gharari, Shervan *et al.* (2021). „Understanding the Information Content in the Hierarchy of Model Development Decisions: Learning from Data“. In: *Water Resources Research* 57.6, e2020WR027948. ISSN: 1944-7973. DOI: 10/gn8dtg. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2020WR027948> (visited on 26/09/2023).
- Girons Lopez, Marc and Jan Seibert (Oct. 2016). „Influence of Hydro-Meteorological Data Spatial Aggregation on Streamflow Modelling“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 541, pp. 1212–1220. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/f3r2sd. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169416305170> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Griessinger, Nena *et al.* (22nd Sept. 2016). „Assessing the Benefit of Snow Data Assimilation for Runoff Modeling in Alpine Catchments“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 20.9, pp. 3895–3905. ISSN: 1607-7938. DOI: 10/f85mn7. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/20/3895/2016/> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Gujer, Willi (2007). *Siedlungswasserwirtschaft. 3.*, bearb. Aufl. Berlin: Springer. 431 pp. ISBN: 978-3-540-34330-1.
- Gupta, Hoshin V., Martyn P. Clark *et al.* (Aug. 2012). „Towards a Comprehensive Assessment of Model Structural Adequacy“. In: *Water Resources Research* 48.8, 2011WR011044. ISSN: 0043-1397, 1944-7973. DOI: 10/g87bg. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2011WR011044> (visited on 20/10/2023).
- Gupta, Hoshin V., Harald Kling *et al.* (Oct. 2009). „Decomposition of the Mean Squared Error and NSE Performance Criteria: Implications for Improving Hydrological Modelling“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 377.1-2, pp. 80–91. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/c2hqxw. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169409004843> (visited on 19/10/2022).
- Gurtz, Joachim *et al.* (15th Feb. 2003). „A Comparative Study in Modelling Runoff and Its Components in Two Mountainous Catchments“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 17.2, pp. 297–311. ISSN: 0885-6087, 1099-1085. DOI: 10/brhwtm. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hyp.1125> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Hakala, Kirsti, Nans Addor and Jan Seibert (1st Aug. 2018). „Hydrological Modeling to Evaluate Climate Model Simulations and Their Bias Correction“. In: *Journal of Hydrometeorology* 19.8, pp. 1321–1337. ISSN: 1525-755X, 1525-7541. DOI: 10/ggfsj4. URL: <http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/JHM-D-17-0189.1> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Hamaoui, Mustapha (2019). „Étude statistique et comparative de modèles conceptuels hydrologiques pour des bassins versants de la province du Québec, Canada“. MA thesis. Chicoutimi, Canada: Université du Québec à Chicoutimi. 155 pp. URL: <https://constellation.uqac.ca/id/eprint/5403/> (visited on 06/10/2023).
- Hamilton, A.S., D.G. Hutchinson and R.D. Moore (2000). „Estimating Winter Streamflow Using Conceptual Streamflow Model“. In: *Journal of Cold Regions Engineering* 14.4, pp. 158–175. ISSN: 0887381X (ISSN). DOI: 10/d4bft2. URL: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-0034554792&doi=10.1061%2f%28ASCE%290887-381X%282000%2914%3a4%28158%29&partnerID=40&md5=e66da4469cd99a832e09a980ad6171d4>.

- Han, Ming, Juliane Mai *et al.* (2020). „Subwatershed-Based Lake and River Routing Products for Hydrologic and Land Surface Models Applied Over Canada“. In: *Canadian Water Resources Journal* 45.3, pp. 237–251. ISSN: 0701-1784. DOI: 10/gp9t4s. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/07011784.2020.1772116>.
- Han, Ming, Hongren Shen, Bryan A. Tolson, James R. Craig *et al.* (June 2023). „Basinmaker 3.0: A GIS Toolbox for Distributed Watershed Delineation of Complex Lake-River Routing Networks“. In: *Environmental Modelling & Software* 164, p. 105688. ISSN: 1364-8152. DOI: 10/gs87bj. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1364815223000749> (visited on 26/09/2023).
- Han, Ming, Hongren Shen, Bryan A. Tolson and Robert A. Metcalfe (10th May 2022). *Ontario Lake-River Routing Product Version 1.0*. Version v1.0. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.6536085. URL: <https://zenodo.org/record/6536085> (visited on 12/11/2023).
- Herath, Herath Mudiyansele Viraj Vidura, Jayashree Chadalawada and Vladan Babovic (11th Aug. 2021). „Hydrologically Informed Machine Learning for Rainfall–Runoff Modelling: Towards Distributed Modelling“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 25.8, pp. 4373–4401. ISSN: 1607-7938. DOI: 10/gn96xg. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/25/4373/2021/> (visited on 19/10/2022).
- Herman, J. D., P. M. Reed and T. Wagener (Mar. 2013). „Time-Varying Sensitivity Analysis Clarifies the Effects of Watershed Model Formulation on Model Behavior“. In: *Water Resources Research* 49.3, pp. 1400–1414. ISSN: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/gn8dx9. URL: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1002/wrcr.20124> (visited on 19/10/2022).
- High Performance Computing (HPC)* (1st Mar. 2016). Portal. URL: https://www.unibe.ch/universitaet/campus_und_infrastruktur/rund_um_computer/soft_und_hardware/hardware/hochleistungsrechner_hpc_grid/index_ger.html (visited on 12/11/2023).
- Höge, Marvin *et al.* (15th June 2023a). *CAMELS-CH: Hydro-Meteorological Time Series and Landscape Attributes for 331 Catchments in Hydrologic Switzerland*. preprint. ESSD – Land/Hydrology. DOI: 10.5194/essd-2023-127. URL: <https://essd.copernicus.org/preprints/essd-2023-127/> (visited on 10/11/2023).
- (16th Oct. 2023b). *Catchment Attributes and Hydro-Meteorological Time Series for Large-Sample Studies Across Hydrologic Switzerland (CAMELS-CH)*. Version 0.7. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.7784632. URL: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7784632> (visited on 24/10/2023).
- Horton, Pascal, Bettina Schaefli and Martina Kauzlaric (2022). „Why Do We Have so Many Different Hydrological Models? A Review Based on the Case of Switzerland“. In: *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Water* 9.1. ISSN: 2049-1948. DOI: 10/gn5zhg. URL: <https://wires.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/wat2.1574>.
- Horton, Pascal, Bettina Schaefli, Abdelkader Mezghani *et al.* (30th June 2006). „Assessment of Climate-Change Impacts on Alpine Discharge Regimes with Climate Model Uncertainty“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 20.10, pp. 2091–2109. ISSN: 0885-6087, 1099-1085. DOI: 10/fxfc2p. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hyp.6197> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Huard, David (2023). *Utility Scripts - RavenPy 0.12.3 Documentation - Revision 79875188*. Utility Scripts - RavenPy 0.12.3 documentation. URL: <https://ravenpy.readthedocs.io/en/latest/scripts.html#> (visited on 12/11/2023).
- [SW] Huard, David *et al.* *Ouranosinc/Raven: V0.18.2 version v0.18.2*, 6th July 2023. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.8121695. URL: <https://zenodo.org/record/8121695> (visited on 12/11/2023).
- „Hydroeval“ (2023). „Hydroeval: An Evaluator for Streamflow Time Series in Python“. In: (). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4709652. URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/4709652> (visited on 01/12/2023).
- Hyndman, Rob J. and Anne B. Koehler (Oct. 2006). „Another Look at Measures of Forecast Accuracy“. In: *International Journal of Forecasting* 22.4, pp. 679–688. ISSN: 0169-2070. DOI: 10/dqmdbj. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0169207006000239> (visited on 01/12/2023).
- Ibarra Zavaleta, Sara Patricia *et al.* (Oct. 2015). „Global Model MOHYSE, a New Tool to Assess the Effect of Hydro-Meteorological Phenomena in the Tropics“. In: *2015 International Conference on Computing Systems and Telematics (ICCSAT)*. 2015 International Conference on Computing Systems and Telematics (ICCSAT). Xalapa, Mexico: IEEE, pp. 1–7. ISBN: 978-1-4799-7639-3. DOI: 10/gsttm2. URL: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7362957/> (visited on 20/05/2022).

- Jackson, Elise K. *et al.* (Sept. 2019). „Introductory Overview: Error Metrics for Hydrologic Modelling – a Review of Common Practices and an Open Source Library to Facilitate Use and Adoption“. In: *Environmental Modelling & Software* 119, pp. 32–48. ISSN: 1364-8152. DOI: 10/gg59bv. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S136481521930427X> (visited on 09/05/2023).
- Jasper, Karsten, Pierluigi Calanca and Jürg Fuhrer (Aug. 2006). „Changes in Summertime Soil Water Patterns in Complex Terrain Due to Climatic Change“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 327.3-4, pp. 550–563. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/ft7m9v. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169405006530> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Jasper, Karsten, Pierluigi Calanca, Dimitrios Gyalistras *et al.* (2004). „Differential Impacts of Climate Change on the Hydrology of Two Alpine River Basins“. In: *Climate Research* 26, pp. 113–129. ISSN: 0936-577X, 1616-1572. DOI: 10/c65x5s. URL: <http://www.int-res.com/abstracts/cr/v26/n2/p113-129/> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Jasper, Karsten, Joachim Gurtz and Herbert Lang (Oct. 2002). „Advanced Flood Forecasting in Alpine Watersheds by Coupling Meteorological Observations and Forecasts with a Distributed Hydrological Model“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 267.1-2, pp. 40–52. ISSN: 00221694. DOI: 10/dt6968. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169402001385> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Jenicek, Michal, Jan Seibert and Maria Staudinger (Jan. 2018). „Modeling of Future Changes in Seasonal Snowpack and Impacts on Summer Low Flows in Alpine Catchments“. In: *Water Resources Research* 54.1, pp. 538–556. ISSN: 0043-1397, 1944-7973. DOI: 10/gdb6ks. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/2017WR021648> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Kavetski, Dmitri, Fabrizio Fenicia and Martyn P. Clark (2011). „Impact of Temporal Data Resolution on Parameter Inference and Model Identification in Conceptual Hydrological Modeling: Insights from an Experimental Catchment“. In: *Water Resources Research* 47.5. ISSN: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/d725hz. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2010WR009525>.
- Klemeš, V. (Mar. 1986). „Operational Testing of Hydrological Simulation Models“. In: *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 31.1, pp. 13–24. ISSN: 0262-6667, 2150-3435. DOI: 10/fj6jj6. URL: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02626668609491024> (visited on 19/10/2023).
- Kneis, David (2015). „A Lightweight Framework for Rapid Development of Object-Based Hydrological Model Engines“. In: *Environmental Modelling and Software* 68, pp. 110–121. ISSN: 1364-8152. DOI: 10/f68wpq. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364815215000584>.
- Knoben, Wouter J. M. *et al.* (25th June 2019a). „Modular Assessment of Rainfall–Runoff Models Toolbox (MARRMoT) V1.2: An Open-Source, Extendable Framework Providing Implementations of 46 Conceptual Hydrologic Models as Continuous State-Space Formulations“. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 12.6, pp. 2463–2480. ISSN: 1991-9603. DOI: 10/gqj7p6. URL: <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/12/2463/2019/> (visited on 13/07/2023).
- (25th June 2019b). „Supplement: Modular Assessment of Rainfall–Runoff Models Toolbox (MARRMoT) V1.2: An Open-Source, Extendable Framework Providing Implementations of 46 Conceptual Hydrologic Models as Continuous State-Space Formulations“. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 12.6, pp. 2463–2480. ISSN: 1991-9603. DOI: 10/gs87bk. URL: <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/12/2463/2019/> (visited on 13/07/2023).
- Larocque, M. *et al.* (8th Oct. 2010). *Groundwater Contribution to River Flows – Using Hydrograph Separation, Hydrological and Hydrogeological Models in a Southern Quebec Aquifer*. DOI: 10.5194/hessd-7-7809-2010. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/preprints/7/7809/2010/> (visited on 10/11/2022). preprint.
- Lindström, Göran *et al.* (1997). „Development and Test of the Distributed HBV-96 Hydrological Model“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 201, pp. 272–288. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/bhhcmm. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022169497000413>.
- Linsbauer, Andreas *et al.* (2020). *The New Swiss Glacier Inventory SGI2016*. Dataset. GLAMOS. DOI: https://doi.glamos.ch/data/inventory/inventory_sgi2016_r2020.html. URL: https://doi.glamos.ch/data/inventory/inventory_sgi2016_r2020.zip.
- (20th Oct. 2021). „The New Swiss Glacier Inventory SGI2016: From a Topographical to a Glaciological Dataset“. In: *Frontiers in Earth Science* 9, p. 704189. ISSN: 2296-6463. DOI: 10/gspwqs. URL: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feart.2021.704189/full> (visited on 10/11/2023).
- [SW] Mai, Juliane, *Grid Weights Generator for Raven* 31st Aug. 2023. URL: <https://github.com/julemai/GridWeightsGenerator>(visited on 12/11/2023).

- Mai, Juliane (1st May 2023b). „Ten Strategies Towards Successful Calibration of Environmental Models“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 620, p. 129414. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/grz49k. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022169423003566> (visited on 26/09/2023).
- Mai, Juliane, James R. Craig and Bryan A. Tolson (2020). „Simultaneously Determining Global Sensitivities of Model Parameters and Model Structure“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 24.12, pp. 5835–5858. ISSN: 1027-5606. DOI: 10/gjbt4j. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/24/5835/2020/>.
- Mai, Juliane, James R. Craig, Bryan A. Tolson and Richard Arsenault (2022). „The Sensitivity of Simulated Streamflow to Individual Hydrologic Processes Across North America“. In: *Nature Communications* 13.1. ISSN: 2041-1723. DOI: 10/gr965s. URL: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-022-28010-7>.
- Margot, André *et al.* (1992). „Beeinfluss Der Fliessgewässer Durch Kraftwerke ($\geq 300\text{kW}$) Und Seeregulierungen“. In: *Hydrologischer Atlas Der Schweiz*. 1992nd ed., Tafel 5.3. URL: https://hydrologischeratlas.ch/downloads/01/content/Tafel_53.pdf (visited on 12/12/2023).
- Martel, Jean-Luc *et al.* (2017). „HMETS - A Simple and Efficient Hydrology Model for Teaching Hydrological Modelling, Flow Forecasting and Climate Change Impacts“. In: *International Journal of Engineering Education* 33.4, pp. 1307–1316. ISSN: 0949-149X. URL: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318582398> (visited on 06/10/2023).
- Matott, L. Shawn (2017a). *OSTRICH – An Optimization Software Toolkit for Research Involving Computational Heuristics Documentation and User’s Guide Version 17.12.19*. State University of New York at Buffalo Center for Computational Research. URL: <https://www.eng.buffalo.edu/~lsmatott/Ostrich/OstrichMain.html> (visited on 09/12/2022).
- [SW] Matott, L. Shawn, *OSTRICH Optimization Software Toolkit version 17.12.19*, 2017. University at Buffalo Center for Computational Research. URL: <https://www.civil.uwaterloo.ca/envmodellimg/Ostrich.html>(visited on 28/03/2022).
- Melsen, Lieke *et al.* (8th June 2016). „Representation of Spatial and Temporal Variability in Large-Domain Hydrological Models: Case Study for a Mesoscale Pre-Alpine Basin“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 20.6, pp. 2207–2226. ISSN: 1027-5606. DOI: 10/f8v8sm. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/20/2207/2016/> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Moore, R. J. (June 1985). „The Probability-Distributed Principle and Runoff Production at Point and Basin Scales“. In: *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 30.2, pp. 273–297. ISSN: 0262-6667, 2150-3435. DOI: 10/fmrtxb. URL: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02626668509490989> (visited on 26/09/2023).
- (1999). „Real-Time Flood Forecasting Systems: Perspectives and Prospects“. In: *Floods and Landslides: Integrated Risk Assessment*. Ed. by Riccardo Casale and Claudio Margottini. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 147–189. ISBN: 978-3-642-58609-5. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-58609-5_11. URL: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-642-58609-5_11 (visited on 26/09/2023).
- (17th Jan. 2007). „The PDM Rainfall-Runoff Model“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 11.1, pp. 483–499. ISSN: 1607-7938. DOI: 10/bh2ps2. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/11/483/2007/> (visited on 19/10/2022).
- Moore, R.D. (Sept. 1993). „Application of a Conceptual Streamflow Model in a Glacierized Drainage Basin“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 150.1, pp. 151–168. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/dx9v6p. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0022169493901597> (visited on 18/11/2022).
- Müller-Thomy, Hannes and Anna E. Sikorska-Senoner (10th Sept. 2019). „Does the Complexity in Temporal Precipitation Disaggregation Matter for a Lumped Hydrological Model?“ In: *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 64.12, pp. 1453–1471. ISSN: 0262-6667, 2150-3435. DOI: 10/gs87bp. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02626667.2019.1638926> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Nash, J.E. and J.V. Sutcliffe (Apr. 1970). „River Flow Forecasting Through Conceptual Models Part I — A Discussion of Principles“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 10.3, pp. 282–290. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/fbg9tm. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0022169470902556> (visited on 30/10/2023).
- Oudin, Ludovic *et al.* (Mar. 2005). „Which Potential Evapotranspiration Input for a Lumped Rainfall-Runoff Model?“ In: *Journal of Hydrology* 303.1-4, pp. 290–306. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/b7d4n8. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169404004056> (visited on 19/10/2022).

- Pagano, Thomas, Prasantha Hapuarachchi and Q. J. Wang (27th Jan. 2010). *Continuous Rainfall-Runoff Model Comparison and Short-Term Daily Streamflow Forecast Skill Evaluation*. Technical Report EP103545. CSIRO. DOI: 10.4225/08/58542c672dd2c. URL: <https://publications.csiro.au/publications/publication/PIcsiro:EP103545> (visited on 05/10/2023).
- Parra, Víctor, Patricio Fuentes-Aguilera and Enrique Muñoz (10th Sept. 2018). „Identifying Advantages and Drawbacks of Two Hydrological Models Based on a Sensitivity Analysis: A Study in Two Chilean Watersheds“. In: *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 63.12, pp. 1831–1843. ISSN: 0262-6667, 2150-3435. DOI: 10/g87bq. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/0262667.2018.1538593> (visited on 19/10/2022).
- Perrin, Charles (20th Oct. 2000). „Vers Une Amélioration D’un Modèle Global Pluie-Débit Au Travers D’une Approche Comparative“. PhD thesis. Antony, France: Institut National Polytechnique de Grenoble - INPG. 291 pp. URL: https://theses.hal.science/tel-00006216/file/Memoire_These.Perrin.2000.pdf (visited on 09/11/2023).
- Perrin, Charles, Claude Michel and Vazken Andréassian (2003). „Improvement of a Parsimonious Model for Streamflow Simulation“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 279.1-4, pp. 275–289. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/d22k8x. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0022169403002257>.
- [SW] Poncelet, Carine, *CemaNeige* version 99d008e, 24th Oct. 2018. URL: <https://github.com/cponc8/CemaNeige/blob/121eb5f2b1a8834fcb4422073f5526ae4c6461d1/CemaNeige.py>(visited on 04/05/2023).
- Pool, Sandra, Marc Vis and Jan Seibert (26th Oct. 2018). „Evaluating Model Performance: Towards a Non-Parametric Variant of the Kling-Gupta Efficiency“. In: *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 63.13-14, pp. 1941–1953. ISSN: 0262-6667, 2150-3435. DOI: 10/gjcq9z. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02626667.2018.1552002> (visited on 19/10/2022).
- Pushpalatha, Raji (2012). „A Review of Efficiency Criteria Suitable for Evaluating Low-Flow Simulations“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 420–421, pp. 171–182. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/bf5px2. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022169411008407>.
- Pushpalatha, Raji *et al.* (Dec. 2011). „A Downward Structural Sensitivity Analysis of Hydrological Models to Improve Low-Flow Simulation“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 411.1-2, pp. 66–76. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/ffg78n. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169411006846> (visited on 27/04/2023).
- Rahman, Kazi *et al.* (Jan. 2013). „Streamflow Modeling in a Highly Managed Mountainous Glacier Watershed Using SWAT: The Upper Rhone River Watershed Case in Switzerland“. In: *Water Resources Management* 27.2, pp. 323–339. ISSN: 0920-4741, 1573-1650. DOI: 10/f4jfdw. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11269-012-0188-9> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- [SW], *RavenHydroFramework* 11th Nov. 2023. Canadian Society for Hydrological Sciences. URL: <https://github.com/CSHS-CWRA/RavenHydroFramework>(visited on 15/12/2023).
- Refsgaard, Jens Christian and Hans Jørgen Henriksen (Jan. 2004). „Modelling Guidelines—Terminology and Guiding Principles“. In: *Advances in Water Resources* 27.1, pp. 71–82. ISSN: 0309-1708. DOI: 10/dc4634. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0309170803001489> (visited on 29/09/2023).
- Refsgaard, Jens Christian, Simon Stisen and Julian Koch (2022). „Hydrological Process Knowledge in Catchment Modelling – Lessons and Perspectives from 60 Years Development“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 36.1. ISSN: 0885-6087. DOI: 10/gn8s23. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hyp.14463>.
- Roberts, Wade *et al.* (2nd Dec. 2018). „Hydrostats: A Python Package for Characterizing Errors between Observed and Predicted Time Series“. In: *Hydrology* 5.4, p. 66. ISSN: 2306-5338. DOI: 10/gg59cv. URL: <http://www.mdpi.com/2306-5338/5/4/66> (visited on 16/12/2023).
- Rößler, Ole and Jörg Löffler (15th July 2010). „Potentials and Limitations of Modelling Spatio-Temporal Patterns of Soil Moisture in a High Mountain Catchment Using WaSiS-ETH“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 24.15, pp. 2182–2196. ISSN: 0885-6087, 1099-1085. DOI: 10/fmw5wt. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hyp.7663> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Rössler, O., P. Froidevaux *et al.* (19th June 2014). „Retrospective Analysis of a Nonforecasted Rain-on-Snow Flood in the Alps – a Matter of Model Limitations or Unpredictable Nature?“ In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 18.6, pp. 2265–2285. ISSN: 1607-7938. DOI: 10/gb9nht. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/18/2265/2014/> (visited on 15/12/2023).

- Rössler, Ole, Bernd Diekkrüger and Jörg Löffler (Apr. 2012). „Potential Drought Stress in a Swiss Mountain Catchment—Ensemble Forecasting of High Mountain Soil Moisture Reveals a Drastic Decrease, Despite Major Uncertainties“. In: *Water Resources Research* 48.4, 2011WR011188. ISSN: 0043-1397, 1944-7973. DOI: 10/gg2vwz. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2011WR011188> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Roy, Alexandre, Alain Royer and Richard Turcotte (Aug. 2010). „Improvement of Springtime Streamflow Simulations in a Boreal Environment by Incorporating Snow-Covered Area Derived from Remote Sensing Data“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 390.1-2, pp. 35–44. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/c6gnfn. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169410003628> (visited on 28/04/2023).
- Roy, Tirthankar, Hoshin V. Gupta *et al.* (2017). „Using Satellite-Based Evapotranspiration Estimates to Improve the Structure of a Simple Conceptual Rainfall–Runoff Model“. In: *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 21.2, pp. 879–896. DOI: 10/f9wpqv.
- Santos, Léonard, Guillaume Thirel and Charles Perrin (19th Apr. 2018). „Continuous State-Space Representation of a Bucket-Type Rainfall-Runoff Model: A Case Study with the GR4 Model Using State-Space Gr4 (Version 1.0)“. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 11.4, pp. 1591–1605. ISSN: 1991-959X. DOI: 10/gddvjv. URL: <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/11/1591/2018/> (visited on 04/05/2023).
- Schaefli, B. and E. Zehe (19th Oct. 2009). „Hydrological Model Performance and Parameter Estimation in the Wavelet-Domain“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 13.10, pp. 1921–1936. ISSN: 1027-5606. DOI: 10/bcw26t. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/13/1921/2009/> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Schaefli, Bettina (30th Oct. 2016). „Snow Hydrology Signatures for Model Identification Within a Limits-of-Acceptability Approach“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 30.22, pp. 4019–4035. ISSN: 0885-6087, 1099-1085. DOI: 10/f9csds. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hyp.10972> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Schaefli, Bettina and Hoshin V. Gupta (2007). „Do Nash Values Have Value?“ In: *Hydrological Processes* 21.15, pp. 2075–2080. ISSN: 1099-1085. DOI: 10/d6dbbj. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/hyp.6825> (visited on 19/10/2022).
- Schwanbeck, Jan and Alain Bühlmann (2018). „Catchment Characteristics“. In: *Data and Analysis Platform. Hydrological Atlas of Switzerland*. URL: [https://hydromaps.ch/#en/8/46.830/8.190/bl_hds--a04.a0401.eu.dem.v11.e40n20crp.chv1.0\\$0/NULL](https://hydromaps.ch/#en/8/46.830/8.190/bl_hds--a04.a0401.eu.dem.v11.e40n20crp.chv1.0$0/NULL).
- Schwanbeck, Jan, Caroline Kan *et al.* (2018). „Hydrometric Networks – Interactive Map A05: Hydrological Atlas of Switzerland - Explanatory Text Accompanying the Map“. In: *Hydrological Atlas of Switzerland*. DOI: 10/gs87bt. URL: <https://boris.unibe.ch/141629/> (visited on 05/10/2023).
- Seibert, Jan (1st Aug. 1997). „Estimation of Parameter Uncertainty in the HBV Model“. In: *Hydrology Research* 28.4-5, pp. 247–262. ISSN: 0029-1277, 2224-7955. DOI: 10/gjt3h7. URL: <https://iwaponline.com/hr/article/28/4-5/247/31640/Estimation-of-Parameter-Uncertainty-in-the-HBV> (visited on 09/11/2023).
- (Nov. 2005). *HBV Light Version 2 User's Manual*. Stockholm University. URL: https://www.geo.uzh.ch/dam/jcr:c8afa73c-ac90-478e-a8c7-929eed7b1b62/HBV_manual_2005.pdf (visited on 17/11/2022).
- Seibert, Jan and Sten Bergström (14th Mar. 2022). „A Retrospective on Hydrological Catchment Modelling Based on Half a Century with the HBV Model“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 26.5, pp. 1371–1388. ISSN: 1607-7938. DOI: 10/gq3c7p. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/26/1371/2022/> (visited on 26/09/2023).
- Seiller, G., F. Anctil and R. Roy (Sept. 2017). „Design and Experimentation of an Empirical Multistructure Framework for Accurate, Sharp and Reliable Hydrological Ensembles“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 552, pp. 313–340. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/gbz876. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169417304535> (visited on 12/10/2023).
- Shafii, Mahyar, Nandita Basu *et al.* (Apr. 2017). „A Diagnostic Approach to Constraining Flow Partitioning in Hydrologic Models Using a Multiobjective Optimization Framework“. In: *Water Resources Research* 53.4, pp. 3279–3301. ISSN: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/f99brk. URL: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1002/2016WR019736> (visited on 19/10/2022).
- Shafii, Mahyar and Bryan A. Tolson (2015). „Optimizing Hydrological Consistency by Incorporating Hydrological Signatures into Model Calibration Objectives“. In: *Water Resources Research* 51.5, pp. 3796–3814. ISSN: 1944-7973. DOI: 10/f7jvnb. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/2014WR016520> (visited on 12/10/2023).

- Shen, Hongren, Bryan A. Tolson and Juliane Mai (2022). „Time to Update the Split-Sample Approach in Hydrological Model Calibration“. In: *Water Resources Research* 58.3, e2021WR031523. ISSN: 1944-7973. DOI: 10/gqgndg. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1029/2021WR031523> (visited on 27/10/2022).
- Shen, Mingxi, Jie Chen *et al.* (Jan. 2018). „Estimating Uncertainty and Its Temporal Variation Related to Global Climate Models in Quantifying Climate Change Impacts on Hydrology“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 556, pp. 10–24. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/gcnzpx. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169417307588> (visited on 10/12/2023).
- Simmons, Craig T. *et al.* (2019). „Commemorating the 50th Anniversary of the Freeze and Harlan (1969) Blueprint for a Physically-Based, Digitally-Simulated Hydrologic Response Model“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 584, p. 124309. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/ggdhrr. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169419310443> (visited on 26/10/2023).
- Spieler, Diana *et al.* (2020). „Automatic Model Structure Identification for Conceptual Hydrologic Models“. In: *Water Resources Research* 56.9. ISSN: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/ghd6bz. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2019WR027009>.
- Staudinger, M., M. Weiler and J. Seibert (12th Mar. 2015). „Quantifying Sensitivity to Droughts – an Experimental Modeling Approach“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 19.3, pp. 1371–1384. ISSN: 1607-7938. DOI: 10/f3nzt. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/19/1371/2015/> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Staudinger, Maria, Michael Stoelzle *et al.* (30th May 2017). „Catchment Water Storage Variation with Elevation“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 31.11, pp. 2000–2015. ISSN: 0885-6087. DOI: 10/gbjf3s. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hyp.11158> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Sun, W. C., H. Ishidaira and S. Bastola (22nd Oct. 2010). „Towards Improving River Discharge Estimation in Ungauged Basins: Calibration of Rainfall-Runoff Models Based on Satellite Observations of River Flow Width at Basin Outlet“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 14.10, pp. 2011–2022. ISSN: 1027-5606. DOI: 10/bh4s8d. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/14/2011/2010/> (visited on 10/12/2023).
- Tarek, Mostafa, François P. Brissette and Richard Arsenault (14th May 2020). „Evaluation of the ERA5 Reanalysis as a Potential Reference Dataset for Hydrological Modelling Over North America“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 24.5, pp. 2527–2544. ISSN: 1027-5606. DOI: 10/gh2sq. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/24/2527/2020/> (visited on 22/09/2023).
- Tolson, Bryan A. and Christine A. Shoemaker (2007). „Dynamically Dimensioned Search Algorithm for Computationally Efficient Watershed Model Calibration“. In: *Water Resources Research* 43.1. ISSN: 1944-7973. DOI: 10/dn538b. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1029/2005WR004723> (visited on 26/09/2023).
- Tolson, Bryan A., Sharma Vimal and David A. Swayne (2014). „Parallel Implementations of the Dynamically Dimensioned (DDS) Search Algorithm“. In: 7th International Symposium on Environmental Software Systems. Vol. 7. Environmental Software Systems. Prague: International Federation for Information Processing, p. 630. ISBN: 978-3-901882-22-7. DOI: 10/gs87bv. URL: <http://rgdoi.net/10.13140/2.1.3773.6001> (visited on 12/10/2023).
- Troin, Magali, Richard Arsenault and François Brissette (27th Nov. 2015). „Performance and Uncertainty Evaluation of Snow Models on Snowmelt Flow Simulations over a Nordic Catchment (Mistassibi, Canada)“. In: *Hydrology* 2.4, pp. 289–317. ISSN: 2306-5338. DOI: 10/gs87bw. URL: <http://www.mdpi.com/2306-5338/2/4/289> (visited on 10/11/2022).
- Troin, Magali, Richard Arsenault, Jean-Luc Martel *et al.* (1st Jan. 2018). „Uncertainty of Hydrological Model Components in Climate Change Studies over Two Nordic Quebec Catchments“. In: *Journal of Hydrometeorology* 19.1, pp. 27–46. ISSN: 1525-7541, 1525-755X. DOI: 10/gc89t2. URL: <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/hydr/19/1/jhm-d-17-0002.1.xml> (visited on 10/12/2023).
- Turcotte, Richard *et al.* (23rd Aug. 2010). „Simulation Hydrologique Des Derniers Jours De La Crue De Printemps: Le Problème De La Neige Manquante“. In: *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 55.6, pp. 872–882. ISSN: 0262-6667, 2150-3435. DOI: 10/bn5nc5. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02626667.2010.503933> (visited on 24/03/2023).
- Valéry, Audrey (23rd Feb. 2010). „Modélisation Précipitations – Débit Sous Influence Nivale Elaboration D’un Module Neige Et Évaluation Sur 380 Bassins Versants“. PhD thesis. Antony, France: AgroParisTech - Cemagref. URL: <https://webgr.inrae.fr/wp-content/uploads/2012/07/2010-VALERY-THESE.pdf> (visited on 14/09/2023).

- Valéry, Audrey, Vazken Andréassian and Charles Perrin (Sept. 2014a). „‘As Simple as Possible but Not Simpler’: What Is Useful in a Temperature-Based Snow-Accounting Routine? Part 1 – Comparison of Six Snow Accounting Routines on 380 Catchments“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 517, pp. 1166–1175. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/f6gb2h. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169414003333> (visited on 18/04/2022).
- (Sept. 2014b). „‘As Simple as Possible but Not Simpler’: What Is Useful in a Temperature-Based Snow-Accounting Routine? Part 2 – Sensitivity Analysis of the Cemaneige Snow Accounting Routine on 380 Catchments“. In: *Journal of Hydrology* 517, pp. 1176–1187. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/gsttpk. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169414003321> (visited on 18/04/2022).
- Vehviläinen, Bertel (1992). „Snow Cover Models in Operational Watershed Forecasting“. PhD thesis. Helsinki 1992: National Board of Waters and the Environment, Finland. 114 pp. URL: <https://helda.helsinki.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/c7a274ee-28d4-4c4d-96e1-94f1930dd985/content> (visited on 10/12/2023).
- Viviroli, Daniel and Jan Seibert (Oct. 2015). „Can a Regionalized Model Parameterisation Be Improved with a Limited Number of Runoff Measurements?“ In: *Journal of Hydrology* 529, pp. 49–61. ISSN: 0022-1694. DOI: 10/f3rrzj. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022169415005041> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Vrugt, Jasper A., Cees G. H. Diks *et al.* (2005). „Improved Treatment of Uncertainty in Hydrologic Modeling: Combining the Strengths of Global Optimization and Data Assimilation“. In: *Water Resources Research* 41.1. ISSN: 1944-7973. DOI: 10/btffxz. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1029/2004WR003059> (visited on 10/12/2023).
- Vrugt, Jasper A., Hoshin V. Gupta *et al.* (Aug. 2003). „A Shuffled Complex Evolution Metropolis Algorithm for Optimization and Uncertainty Assessment of Hydrologic Model Parameters“. In: *Water Resources Research* 39.8. ISSN: 0043-1397. DOI: 10/fbff2d. eprint: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1029/2002WR001642>. URL: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1029/2002WR001642> (visited on 13/07/2023).
- Wagener, T., N. McIntyre *et al.* (2003). „Towards Reduced Uncertainty in Conceptual Rainfall-Runoff Modelling: Dynamic Identifiability Analysis“. In: *Hydrological Processes* 17.2, pp. 455–476. ISSN: 0885-6087. DOI: 10/b2h2k3. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hyp.1135>.
- Wagener, Thorsten, Douglas P. Boyle *et al.* (2001). „A Framework for Development and Application of Hydrological Models“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 5.1, pp. 13–26. ISSN: 1027-5606. DOI: 10/bm4ssb. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/5/13/2001/>.
- Wagener, Thorsten, Robert Reinecke and Francesca Pianosi (May 2022). „On the Evaluation of Climate Change Impact Models“. In: *WIREs Climate Change* 13.3, e772. ISSN: 1757-7780, 1757-7799. DOI: 10/gp9x7t. URL: <https://wires.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/wcc.772> (visited on 19/10/2023).
- Wang, Anqi and Dimitri P. Solomatine (22nd May 2019). „Practical Experience of Sensitivity Analysis: Comparing Six Methods, on Three Hydrological Models, with Three Performance Criteria“. In: *Water* 11.5, p. 1062. ISSN: 2073-4441. DOI: 10/gn95r7. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/11/5/1062> (visited on 19/10/2022).
- Wever, Nander *et al.* (14th Aug. 2017). „Simulating the Influence of Snow Surface Processes on Soil Moisture Dynamics and Streamflow Generation in an Alpine Catchment“. In: *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 21.8, pp. 4053–4071. ISSN: 1607-7938. DOI: 10/gbs2fs. URL: <https://hess.copernicus.org/articles/21/4053/2017/> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Yen, Haw *et al.* (July 2015). „Computational Procedure for Evaluating Sampling Techniques on Watershed Model Calibration“. In: *Journal of Hydrologic Engineering* 20.7, p. 04014080. ISSN: 1084-0699, 1943-5584. DOI: 10/f7f3z9. URL: <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/10.1061/%28ASCE%29HE.1943-5584.0001095> (visited on 12/10/2023).
- Zappa, M. and C. Kan (7th June 2007). „Extreme Heat and Runoff Extremes in the Swiss Alps“. In: *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences* 7.3, pp. 375–389. ISSN: 1684-9981. DOI: 10/bvgxkg. URL: <https://nhess.copernicus.org/articles/7/375/2007/> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Zarrineh, Nina, Karim C. Abbaspour and Annelie Holzkämper (Mar. 2020). „Integrated Assessment of Climate Change Impacts on Multiple Ecosystem Services in Western Switzerland“. In: *Science of The Total Environment* 708, p. 135212. ISSN: 00489697. DOI: 10/gg787k. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048969719352040> (visited on 15/12/2023).

- Zarrineh, Nina, Karim C. Abbaspour, Ann Van Griensven *et al.* (Nov. 2018). „Model-Based Evaluation of Land Management Strategies with Regard to Multiple Ecosystem Services“. In: *Sustainability* 10.11 (11), p. 3844. ISSN: 2071-1050. DOI: 10/gfr23r. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/10/11/3844> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Zheng, Feifei *et al.* (Feb. 2018). „On Lack of Robustness in Hydrological Model Development Due to Absence of Guidelines for Selecting Calibration and Evaluation Data: Demonstration for Data-Driven Models“. In: *Water Resources Research* 54.2, pp. 1013–1030. ISSN: 0043-1397, 1944-7973. DOI: 10/gdbqnw. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/2017WR021470> (visited on 28/11/2023).
- Zierl, Bärbel and Harald Bugmann (Feb. 2005). „Global Change Impacts on Hydrological Processes in Alpine Catchments“. In: *Water Resources Research* 41.2, 2004WR003447. ISSN: 0043-1397, 1944-7973. DOI: 10/c9pddj. URL: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2004WR003447> (visited on 15/12/2023).
- Zink, Matthias *et al.* (2018). „Conditioning a Hydrologic Model Using Patterns of Remotely Sensed Land Surface Temperature“. In: *Water Resources Research* 54.4, pp. 2976–2998. ISSN: 1944-7973. DOI: 10/gdq36k. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/2017WR021346> (visited on 12/10/2023).
- [SW] Zweifel, Peter, *Raven Tools* 29th Aug. 2023. URL: <https://github.com/networkscientist/raven-tools> (visited on 23/10/2023).

A Model Setup

A.1 Random Seeds

Table 17: Random seed numbers used in Ostrich optimization

GR4J	HBV	HMETS	HYMOD	MOHYSE
1699349089	1699349089	1699354089	1699349089	1699349089
1699349090	1699349090	1699354090	1699349090	1699349090
1699349091	1699349091	1699354091	1699349091	1699349091
1699349092	1699349092	1699354092	1699349092	1699349092
1699349093	1699349093	1699354093	1699349093	1699349093
1699349094	1699349094	1699354094	1699349094	1699349094
1699349095	1699349095	1699354095	1699349095	1699349095
1699349096	1699349096	1699354096	1699349096	1699349096
1699349097	1699349097	1699354097	1699349097	1699349097
1699349098	1699349098	1699354098	1699349098	1699349098
1699349099	1699349099	1699354099	1699349099	1699349099
1699349100	1699349100	1699354100	1699349100	1699349100
1699349101	1699349101	1699354101	1699349101	1699349101
1699349102	1699349102	1699354102	1699349102	1699349102
1699349103	1699349103	1699354103	1699349103	1699349103
1699349104	1699349104	1699354104	1699349104	1699349104
1699349105	1699349105	1699354105	1699349105	1699349105
1699349106	1699349106	1699354106	1699349106	1699349106
1699349107	1699349107	1699354107	1699349107	1699349107
1699349108	1699349108	1699354108	1699349108	1699349108

A.2 Model Configuration Files

A.2.1 GR4J

Listing 1: CH-0053_GR4J.rvi.tpl

```
# ----Model Organisation-----
:StartDate      1981-01-01 00:00:00
:EndDate        2021-01-01 00:00:00
:TimeStep       1.0
:Method         ORDERED_SERIES
:RunName        CH-0053_GR4J

# ----Model Options-----
:SoilModel      SOIL_MULTILAYER 4
:Routing        ROUTE_NONE
:CatchmentRoute ROUTE_DUMP
:Evaporation    PET_HAMON
:RainSnowFraction RAINSNOW_DINGMAN
:PotentialMeltMethod POTMELT_DEGREE_DAY
:OroTempCorrect OROCORR_SIMPLELAPSE
:OroPrecipCorrect OROCORR_SIMPLELAPSE
:EvaluationPeriod CALIBRATION 1981-01-01 2000-12-31
:EvaluationPeriod VALIDATION 2001-01-01 2020-12-31

# ----Soil Layer Alias Definitions-----
:Alias PRODUCT_STORE SOIL[0]
:Alias ROUTING_STORE SOIL[1]
:Alias TEMP_STORE     SOIL[2]
:Alias GW_STORE       SOIL[3]

# ----Hydrologic Process Order-----
:HydrologicProcesses
```

```

:Precipitation          PRECIP_RAVEN  ATMOS_PRECIP MULTIPLE
:SnowTempEvolve        SNOTEMP_NEWTONS SNOW_TEMP
:SnowBalance           SNOBAL_CEMA_NIEGE SNOW  PONDED_WATER
:OpenWaterEvaporation OPEN_WATER_EVAP PONDED_WATER ATMOSPHERE
: Infiltration          INF_GR4J           PONDED_WATER MULTIPLE
:SoilEvaporation       SOILEVAP_GR4J  PRODUCT_STORE ATMOSPHERE
:Percolation           PERC_GR4J           PRODUCT_STORE TEMP_STORE
:Flush                 RAVEN_DEFAULT SURFACE_WATER TEMP_STORE
:Split                 RAVEN_DEFAULT TEMP_STORE  CONVOLUTION[0]
                        CONVOLUTION[1] 0.9
:Convolve               CONVOL_GR4J_1  CONVOLUTION[0] ROUTING_STORE
:Convolve               CONVOL_GR4J_2  CONVOLUTION[1] TEMP_STORE
:Percolation           PERC_GR4JEXCH  ROUTING_STORE GW_STORE
:Percolation           PERC_GR4JEXCH2 TEMP_STORE  GW_STORE
:Flush                 RAVEN_DEFAULT TEMP_STORE  SURFACE_WATER
:Baseflow              BASE_GR4J           ROUTING_STORE SURFACE_WATER
:EndHydrologicProcesses

```

Listing 2: CH-0053.GR4J.rvh.tpl

```

# ----Subbasins-----
:SubBasins
:Attributes,      NAME, DOWNSTREAM_ID,PROFILE,REACH_LENGTH, GAUGED
:Units      ,      none,      none,  none,      km,      none
              1,      CH-0053,      -1,  NONE,      _AUTO,  1
:EndSubBasins

# ----HRUs-----
:HRUs
:Attributes,  AREA, ELEVATION, LATITUDE, LONGITUDE, BASIN_ID,LAND_USE_CLASS
              ,  VEG_CLASS, SOIL_PROFILE, AQUIFER_PROFILE, TERRAIN_CLASS, SLOPE, ASPECT
:Units      ,  km2,      m,      deg,      deg,      none,      none,      none,
              none,      none,      none,  deg,      deg
              1, 1513.760677262317, 1671.7437744140625, 8.960015136416795, 46.40868158290083,
              1, LU_ALL, VEG_ALL, DEFAULT_P, [NONE], [NONE], 32.29808044433594,
              172.98121643066406
              2, 2.3653035306182244, 2867.020751953125, 8.869017006860698, 46.49804924907984,
              1, GLACIER, GLACIER, GLACIER, [NONE], [NONE], 22.55500602722168,
              200.29884338378903
:EndHRUs

```

Listing 3: CH-0053.GR4J.rvp.tpl

```

# -----Soil Classes-----
:SoilClasses
  :Attributes
  :Units
    SOIL_PROD
    SOIL_ROUT
    SOIL_TEMP
    SOIL_GW
:EndSoilClasses

# -----Soil Profiles-----
:SoilProfiles
  GLACIER, 0
  DEFAULT_P, 4, SOIL_PROD, GR4J_x1, SOIL_ROUT, 0.300, SOIL_TEMP, 1.000, SOIL_GW,
  1.000,
:EndSoilProfiles

# -----Vegetation Classes-----
:VegetationClasses
  :Attributes, MAX_HT, MAX_LAI, MAX_LEAF_COND
  :Units, m, none, mm_per_s
  VEG_ALL, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0
  GLACIER, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0
:EndVegetationClasses

# -----Land Use Classes-----
:LandUseClasses
  :Attributes, IMPERM, FOREST_COV
  :Units, frac, frac
  LU_ALL, 0.02, 0.44
  GLACIER, 0.0, 0.0
:EndLandUseClasses

# -----Global Parameters-----
:GlobalParameter RAINSNOW_TEMP 0.0
:GlobalParameter RAINSNOW_DELTA 1.0
:GlobalParameter AIRSNOW_COEFF Airsnow_Coeff
#CN_X2 = Cemaneige_x2
:GlobalParameter AVG_ANNUAL_SNOW Cemaneige_x1

# -----Soil Parameters-----
:SoilParameterList
  :Parameters, POROSITY, GR4J_X3, GR4J_X2
  :Units, none, mm, mm / d
  [DEFAULT], 1.0, GR4J_x3, GR4J_x2
:EndSoilParameterList

# -----Land Use Parameters-----
:LandUseParameterList
  :Parameters, GR4J_X4, MELT_FACTOR
  :Units, d, mm / d / C
  [DEFAULT], GR4J_x4, 3.5
:EndLandUseParameterList

```

Listing 4: CH-0053-GR4J.rvt.tpl

```
# meteorological forcings
:GriddedForcing      Precipitation
  :ForcingType        PRECIP
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          RhiresD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Average Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_AVE
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TabsD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TabsD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TabsD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Maximum Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_MAX
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TmaxD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TmaxD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TmaxD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Minimum Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_MIN
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TminD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TminD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TminD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing

# observed streamflow
:RedirectToFile data_obs/TicBel.Q.2020_daily.rvt
```

Listing 5: CH-0053-GR4J.rvc.tpl

```
# ----Soil Profiles-----  
# SOIL[0] = GR4J_X1 * 1000. / 2.0 ( initialize to 1/2 full)  
# SOIL[1] = 0.3m * 1000. / 2.0 ( initialize to 1/2 full)  
  
# ----HRU States-----  
:HRUStateVariableTable  
  :Attributes SOIL[0] SOIL[1]  
  :Units      mm      mm  
  1          Soil_0,  15.0  
:EndHRUStateVariableTable
```

Listing 6: ostIn_GR4j.txt

```

# ----Model Info-----
# Catchment Name: Ticino
# Catchment ID: CH-0053

# ----General Options-----
ProgramType      ParallelDDS
ObjectiveFunction GCOP
ModelExecutable  ./Ost-RAVEN.sh
PreserveBestModel ./save_best.sh
ModelSubdir processor_

# ----Extra Directories-----
BeginExtraDirs
model
EndExtraDirs

# ----File Pairs-----
BeginFilePairs
CH-0053_GR4J.rvp.tpl; CH-0053_GR4J.rvp
CH-0053_GR4J.rvc.tpl; CH-0053_GR4J.rvc
EndFilePairs

# ----Parameter Specification-----
BeginParams
#parameter      init .      low      high      tx_in  tx_ost  tx_out
GR4J_x1         random    0.1      1.2      none   none   none
GR4J_x2         random    -5.0     3        none   none   none
GR4J_x3         random    1        500     none   none   none
GR4J_x4         random    0.5      4.0     none   none   none
Cemaneige_x1    random    0.0      100     none   none   none
Cemaneige_x2    random    0.0      1.0     none   none   none
EndParams

# ----Tied Parameters-----
BeginTiedParams
Soil_0  1 GR4J_x1 linear 500 0.00 free # SOIL[0]
Airsnow_Coeff 1 Cemaneige_x2 linear -1.00 0.00 free #Airsnow_Coeff
EndTiedParams

# ----Response Variables-----
BeginResponseVars
#name filename keyword line col token augmented?
KGE_NP_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_GR4J_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 2 '' yes
PBIAS_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_GR4J_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 3 '' yes
RMSE_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_GR4J_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 4 '' yes
VE_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_GR4J_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 5 '' yes
KGE_NP_Cost ./model/output/CH-0053_GR4J_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 6 '' no
PBIAS_Cost ./model/output/CH-0053_GR4J_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 7 '' no
KGE_NP_VALI ./model/output/CH-0053_GR4J_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 2 '' yes

```

```

PBIAS_VALI  ./model/output/CH-0053_GR4J_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 3  '' yes
RMSE_VALI   ./model/output/CH-0053_GR4J_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 4  '' yes
VE_VALI     ./model/output/CH-0053_GR4J_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 5  '' yes
EndResponseVars

# ----GCOP Options-----
BeginGCOP
CostFunction KGE_NP_Cost
PenaltyFunction APM
EndGCOP

# ----Random Seed Control-----
# Randomseed is replaced at runtime
RandomSeed 3333

# ----Algorithm Settings-----
BeginParallelDDSAIg
PerturbationValue 0.20
MaxIterations 5000
UseRandomParamValues
EndParallelDDSAIg

```

A.2.2 HBV

Listing 7: CH-0053_HBV.rvi.tpl

```
# ----Model Organisation-----
:StartDate      1981-01-01 00:00:00
:EndDate        2021-01-01 00:00:00
:TimeStep       1.0
:RunName        CH-0053_HBV

# ----Model Options-----
:Routing         ROUTE_NONE
:CatchmentRoute  TRIANGULAR_UH
:Evaporation     PET_HAMON
:OW_Evaporation  PET_HAMON
:SWRadiationMethod SW_RAD_DEFAULT
:SWCloudCorrect  SW_CLOUD_CORR_NONE
:SWCanopyCorrect SW_CANOPY_CORR_NONE
:LWRadiationMethod LW_RAD_DEFAULT
:RainSnowFraction RAINSNOW_HBV
:PotentialMeltMethod POTMELT_HBV
:OroTempCorrect  OROCORR_HBV
:OroPrecipCorrect OROCORR_HBV
:OroPETCorrect   OROCORR_HBV
:CloudCoverMethod CLOUDCOV_NONE
:PrecipIceptFract PRECIP_ICEPT_USER
:MonthlyInterpolationMethod MONTHINT_LINEAR_21
:SoilModel       SOIL_MULTILAYER 3
:EvaluationPeriod CALIBRATION 1981-01-01 2000-12-31
:EvaluationPeriod VALIDATION 2001-01-01 2020-12-31

# ----Soil Alias Layer Definitions-----
:Alias          FAST_RESERVOIR SOIL[1]
:Alias          SLOW_RESERVOIR SOIL[2]
:LakeStorage    SLOW_RESERVOIR

# ----Hydrologic Process Order-----
:HydrologicProcesses
:SnowRefreeze  FREEZE_DEGREE.DAY SNOW_LIQ SNOW
:Precipitation PRECIP_RAVEN  ATMOS_PRECIP MULTIPLE
:CanopyEvaporation CANEVP_ALL  CANOPY      ATMOSPHERE
:CanopySnowEvap  CANEVP_ALL  CANOPY_SNOW ATMOSPHERE
:SnowBalance     SNOBAL_SIMPLE.MELT SNOW  SNOW_LIQ
:-->Overflow     RAVEN_DEFAULT SNOW_LIQ  PONDED_WATER
:Flush           RAVEN_DEFAULT PONDED_WATER GLACIER
:-->Conditional HRU_TYPE IS GLACIER
:GlacierMelt     GMELT_HBV    GLACIER_ICE GLACIER
:GlacierRelease  GRELEASE_HBV_EC GLACIER  SURFACE_WATER
:Infiltration    INF_HBV      PONDED_WATER MULTIPLE
:Flush           RAVEN_DEFAULT SURFACE_WATER FAST_RESERVOIR
:-->Conditional HRU_TYPE IS NOT GLACIER
:SoilEvaporation SOILEVAP_HBV  SOIL[0]    ATMOSPHERE
:CapillaryRise   RISE_HBV    FAST_RESERVOIR  SOIL[0]
:LakeEvaporation LAKE_EVAP_BASIC SLOW_RESERVOIR ATMOSPHERE
:Percolation     PERC_CONSTANT FAST_RESERVOIR  SLOW_RESERVOIR
:Baseflow        BASE_POWER_LAW FAST_RESERVOIR SURFACE_WATER
:Baseflow        BASE_LINEAR   SLOW_RESERVOIR SURFACE_WATER
:EndHydrologicProcesses
```

Listing 8: CH-0053_HBV.rvh.tpl

```

# -----Subbasins-----
:SubBasins
:Attributes, NAME, DOWNSTREAM_ID,PROFILE,REACH_LENGTH, GAUGED
:Units      , none, none, none, km, none
              1, CH-0053, -1, NONE, _AUTO, 1
:EndSubBasins

# -----HRUs-----
:HRUs
:Attributes, AREA, ELEVATION, LATITUDE, LONGITUDE, BASIN_ID,LAND_USE_CLASS
              , VEG_CLASS, SOIL_PROFILE, AQUIFER_PROFILE, TERRAIN_CLASS, SLOPE, ASPECT
:Units      , km2,      m,      deg,      deg,      none,      none,      none,
              none,      none,      none, deg,      deg
              1, 1513.760677262317, 1671.7437744140625, 8.960015136416795, 46.40868158290083,
              1, LU_ALL, VEG_ALL, DEFAULT_P, [NONE], [NONE], 32.29808044433594,
              172.98121643066406
              2, 2.3653035306182244, 2867.020751953125, 8.869017006860698, 46.49804924907984,
              1, GLACIER, GLACIER, GLACIER, [NONE], [NONE], 22.55500602722168,
              200.29884338378903
:EndHRUs

# -----Subbasin Properties-----
:SubBasinProperties
#           HBV_PARA_11, DERIVED FROM HBV_PARA_11,
#           MAXBAS,           MAXBAS/2,
:Parameters, TIME_CONC,           TIME_TO_PEAK,
:Units,      d,           d,
              1, HBV_T_Conc_Max_Bas, HBV_Time_To_Peak,
:EndSubBasinProperties

```

Listing 9: CH-0053_HBV.rvp.tpl

```

# -----Soil Classes-----
:SoilClasses
  :Attributes,
  :Units,
    TOPSOIL, 1.0, 0.0, 0
    SLOW_RES, 1.0, 0.0, 0
    FAST_RES, 1.0, 0.0, 0
:EndSoilClasses

# -----Soil Profiles-----
:SoilProfiles
  GLACIER, 0
  DEFAULT_P, 3, TOPSOIL, HBV_Thickness_Topsoil, FAST_RES, 100.0,
  SLOW_RES, 100.0
:EndSoilProfiles

# -----Vegetation Classes-----
:VegetationClasses
  :Attributes, MAX_HT, MAX_LAI, MAX_LEAF_COND
  :Units, m, none, mm_per_s
  VEG_ALL, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0
  GLACIER, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0
:EndVegetationClasses

# -----Vegetation Parameters-----
:VegetationParameterList
  :Parameters, MAX_CAPACITY, MAX_SNOW_CAPACITY, TFRAIN, TFSNOW,
  :Units, mm, mm, frac, frac,
  VEG_ALL, 10000, 10000, 0.88, 0.88,
:EndVegetationParameterList

# -----Land Use Classes-----
:LandUseClasses
  :Attributes, IMPERM, FOREST_COV
  :Units, frac, frac
  LU_ALL, 0.02, 0.44
  GLACIER, 0.0, 0.0
:EndLandUseClasses

# -----Global Parameters-----
:GlobalParameter RAINSNOW_TEMP HBV_RainSnow_Temp
:GlobalParameter RAINSNOW_DELTA 1.0
:GlobalParameter PRECIP_LAPSE HBV_Prec_Lapse_PCALT
:GlobalParameter ADIABATIC_LAPSE HBV_Adiab_Lapse_TCALT
:GlobalParameter SNOW_SWI HBV_Snow_SWI

# -----Land Use Parameters-----
:LandUseParameterList
  :Parameters, MELT_FACTOR, MIN_MELT_FACTOR, HBV_MELT_FOR_CORR,
  REFREEZE_FACTOR, HBV_MELT_ASP_CORR
  :Units, mm/d/K, mm/d/K, none, mm/d/K,
  none
  [DEFAULT], HBV_Melt_Fact, 2.2, HBV_Melt_For_Corr,
  HBV_Refreeze_Fact, 0.48
:EndLandUseParameterList

:LandUseParameterList

```

```

:Parameters, HBV_MELT_GLACIER_CORR, HBV_GLACIER_KMIN, GLAC_STORAGE_COEFF,
  HBV_GLACIER_AG
:Units      ,          none,          1/d,          1/d,          1/mm
  [DEFAULT],          1.64,          0.05,          HBV_Glac_Storage_Effect,
          0.05
:EndLandUseParameterList

```

```

# ----Soil Parameters-----
#For Ostrich:HBV_Alpha= HBV_Alpha
:SoilParameterList
:Parameters,          POROSITY, FIELD_CAPACITY, SAT_WILT, HBV_BETA,
  MAX_CAP_RISE_RATE, MAX_PERC_RATE, BASEFLOW_COEFF, BASEFLOW_N
:Units      ,          none,          none,          none,          none,
          mm/d,          mm/d,          1/d,          none
  [DEFAULT],          HBV_Porosity, HBV_Field_Cap, HBV_Sat_Wilt, HBV_Beta,
  HBV_Max_Cap_Rise_Rate,          0.0,          0.0,          0.0
  FAST_RES,          _DEFAULT,          _DEFAULT,          0.0,          _DEFAULT,
  _DEFAULT, HBV_Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res, HBV_BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res,
  HBV_Baseflow_N
  SLOW_RES,          _DEFAULT,          _DEFAULT,          0.0,          _DEFAULT,
  _DEFAULT,          _DEFAULT, HBV_BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res,          1.0
:EndSoilParameterList

```

Listing 10: CH-0053_HBV.rvt.tpl

```
# meteorological forcings
:GriddedForcing      Precipitation
  :ForcingType        PRECIP
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.
                       lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          RhiresD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Average Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_DAILY_AVE
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TabsD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TabsD.v2.0_swiss.
                       lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TabsD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Maximum Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_MAX
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TmaxD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TmaxD.v2.0_swiss.
                       lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TmaxD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Minimum Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_MIN
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TminD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TminD.v2.0_swiss.
                       lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TminD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing

# observed streamflow
:RedirectToFile data_obs/TicBel.Q_2020_daily.rvt
```

Listing 11: CH-0053.HBV.rvc.tpl

```
# ----Basin-----  
:BasinInitialConditions  
:Attributes, ID, Q  
:Units, none, m3/s  
1, 1.0  
:EndBasinInitialConditions  
  
# ----Lower Groundwater Storage-----  
  
:InitialConditions SOIL[2]  
HBV_Initial_Thickness_Topsoil  
:EndInitialConditions
```

Listing 12: ostIn_HBV.txt

```

#-----
# ---Model Info-----
#-----
# Catchment Name: Ticino
# Catchment ID: CH-0053

# ---General Options-----
ProgramType      ParallelDDS
ObjectiveFunction GCOP
ModelExecutable  ./Ost-RAVEN.sh
PreserveBestModel ./save_best.sh
ModelSubdir processor_

# ---Extra Directories-----
BeginExtraDirs
model
EndExtraDirs

# ---File Pairs-----
BeginFilePairs
CH-0053_HBV.rvp.tpl; CH-0053_HBV.rvp
CH-0053_HBV.rvc.tpl; CH-0053_HBV.rvc
CH-0053_HBV.rvh.tpl; CH-0053_HBV.rvh
CH-0053_HBV.rvt.tpl; CH-0053_HBV.rvt
EndFilePairs

# ---Parameter Specification-----
BeginParams
#parameter      init .      low      high      tx_in  tx_ost  tx_out
HBV_RainSnow_Temp      random      -3      3      none  none
none
HBV_Melt_Fact          random      1      10      none  none  none
HBV_Refreeze_Fact     random      0      3.5      none  none
none
HBV_Snow_SWI          random      0.04      0.07      none  none
none
HBV_Porosity          random      0.1      0.6      none  none  none
HBV_Field_Cap         random      0.0      1.0      none  none  none
HBV_Beta              random      0.0      7.0      none  none  none
HBV_Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res      random      0.01      1000      none
none  none
HBV_BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res      random      0.01      0.6      none
none  none
HBV_BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res      random      0.01      0.6      none
none  none
HBV_T_Conc_Max_Bas    random      1.0      3.0      none  none
none
HBV_Prec_Lapse_PCALT  random      0.0      100      none  none
none
HBV_Adiab_Lapse_TCALT random      0.0      7.0      none  none
none
HBV_Sat_Wilt          random      0.0      0.9      none  none  none
HBV_Alpha             random      0      9      none  none  none
HBV_Max_Cap_Rise_Rate random      0      1      none  none
none
HBV_Thickness_Topsoil random      0.1      10      none  none
none

```

```

HBV_Melt_For_Corr      random      0.01      0.99      none none
  none
HBV_Glac_Storage_Effect random      0.1      2      none none
  none
EndParams

```

```

# ----Tied Parameters-----
BeginTiedParams
HBV_Time_To_Peak 1 HBV_T_Conc_Max_Bas linear 0.5 0.00 free
HBV_Initial_Thickness_Topsoil 1 HBV_Thickness_Topsoil linear 500 0.00 free
HBV_Baseflow_N 1 HBV_Alpha linear 1.0 1.0 free
EndTiedParams

```

```

# ----Response Variables-----
BeginResponseVars
#name filename keyword line col token augmented?
KGE_NP_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HBV_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 2 '' yes
PBIAS_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HBV_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 3 '' yes
RMSE_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HBV_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 4 '' yes
VE_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HBV_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 5 '' yes
KGE_NP_Cost ./model/output/CH-0053_HBV_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 6 '' no
PBIAS_Cost ./model/output/CH-0053_HBV_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 7 '' no
KGE_NP_VALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HBV_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 2 '' yes
PBIAS_VALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HBV_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 3 '' yes
RMSE_VALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HBV_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 4 '' yes
VE_VALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HBV_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 5 '' yes
EndResponseVars

```

```

# ----GCOP Options-----
BeginGCOP
CostFunction KGE_NP_Cost
PenaltyFunction APM
EndGCOP

```

```

# ----Random Seed Control-----
# Randomseed is replaced at runtime
RandomSeed 3333

```

```

# ----Algorithm Settings-----
BeginParallelDDSAAlg
PerturbationValue 0.20
MaxIterations 5000
UseRandomParamValues
EndParallelDDSAAlg

```

A.2.3 HMETS

Listing 13: CH-0053.HMETS.rvi.tpl

```
# ----Model Organisation-----
:StartDate 1981-01-01 00:00:00
:EndDate 2021-01-01 00:00:00
:TimeStep 1.0
:Method ORDERED_SERIES
:RunName CH-0053_HMETS

# ----Model Options-----
:PotentialMeltMethod POTMELT_HMETS
:RainSnowFraction RAINSNOW_THRESHOLD
#:Evaporation PET_DATA
:Evaporation PET_OUDIN
:CatchmentRoute ROUTE_DUMP
:Routing ROUTE_NONE
:SoilModel SOIL_TWO_LAYER
:EvaluationPeriod CALIBRATION 1981-01-01 2000-12-31
:EvaluationPeriod VALIDATION 2001-01-01 2020-12-31

# ----Alias Definitions-----
:Alias DELAYED_RUNOFF CONVOLUTION[1]

# ----Hydrologic Process Order-----
:HydrologicProcesses
:SnowBalance SNOBAL_HMETS MULTIPLE MULTIPLE
:Precipitation RAVEN_DEFAULT ATMOS_PRECIP MULTIPLE
:Infiltration INF_HMETS PONDED_WATER MULTIPLE
:Overflow OVERFLOW_RAVEN SOIL[0] DELAYED_RUNOFF
:Baseflow BASE_LINEAR SOIL[0] SURFACE_WATER
:Percolation PERC_LINEAR SOIL[0] SOIL[1]
:Overflow OVERFLOW_RAVEN SOIL[1] DELAYED_RUNOFF
:SoilEvaporation SOILEVAP_ALL SOIL[0] ATMOSPHERE
:Convolve CONVOL_GAMMA CONVOLUTION[0] SURFACE_WATER
:Convolve CONVOL_GAMMA_2 DELAYED_RUNOFF SURFACE_WATER
:Baseflow BASE_LINEAR SOIL[1] SURFACE_WATER
:EndHydrologicProcesses
```

Listing 14: CH-0053_HMETS.rvh.tpl

```
# ----Subbasins-----
:SubBasins
:Attributes, NAME, DOWNSTREAM_ID,PROFILE,REACH_LENGTH, GAUGED
:Units , none, none, none, km, none
      1, CH-0053, -1, NONE, _AUTO, 1
:EndSubBasins

# ----HRUs-----
:HRUs
:Attributes, AREA, ELEVATION, LATITUDE, LONGITUDE, BASIN_ID,LAND_USE_CLASS,
      VEG_CLASS, SOIL_PROFILE, AQUIFER_PROFILE, TERRAIN_CLASS, SLOPE, ASPECT
:Units , km2, m, deg, deg, none, none, none, none, none, deg, deg
      1, 1513.760677262317, 1671.7437744140625, 8.960015136416795, 46.40868158290083,
      1, LU_ALL, VEG_ALL, DEFAULT_P, [NONE], [NONE], 32.29808044433594,
      172.98121643066406
      2, 2.3653035306182244, 2867.020751953125, 8.869017006860698, 46.49804924907984,
      1, GLACIER, GLACIER, GLACIER, [NONE], [NONE], 22.55500602722168,
      200.29884338378903

:EndHRUs
```

Listing 15: CH-0053_HMETS.rvp.tpl

```

# ----Soil Classes-----
:SoilClasses
  :Attributes,
  :Units,
    TOPSOIL,
    PHREATIC,
:EndSoilClasses

# ----Soil Profiles-----
:SoilProfiles
  LAKE, 0
  ROCK, 0
  GLACIER, 0
  # DEFAULT_P, 2, TOPSOIL, x(20)/1000, PHREATIC, x(21)/1000,
  DEFAULT_P, 2, TOPSOIL, HMETS_Thick.TOP, PHREATIC, HMETS_Thick.PHREATIC,
:EndSoilProfiles

# ----Vegetation Classes-----
:VegetationClasses
  :Attributes, MAX_HT, MAX_LAI, MAX_LEAF_COND
  :Units, m, none, mm_per_s
  VEG_ALL, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0
  GLACIER, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0
:EndVegetationClasses

# ----Land Use Classes-----
:LandUseClasses
  :Attributes, IMPERM, FOREST_COV
  :Units, frac, frac
  LU_ALL, 0.02, 0.44
  GLACIER, 0.0, 0.0
:EndLandUseClasses

# ----Global Parameters-----
:GlobalParameter SNOW_SWI_MIN HMETS_fc_min
:GlobalParameter SNOW_SWI_MAX HMETS_fc_max
:GlobalParameter SWI_REDUCT_COEFF HMETS_C_cum
:GlobalParameter SNOW_SWI 0.05

# ----Vegetation Parameters-----
:VegetationParameterList
  :Parameters, RAIN_ICEPT_PCT, SNOW_ICEPT_PCT,
  :Units, -, -,
  [DEFAULT], 0.0, 0.0,
:EndVegetationParameterList

# ----Land Use Parameters-----
:LandUseParameterList
  :Parameters, MIN_MELT_FACTOR, MAX_MELT_FACTOR, DD_MELT_TEMP,
  DD_AGGRADATION, REFREEZE_FACTOR, REFREEZE_EXP, DD_REFREEZE_TEMP,
  HMETS_RUNOFF_COEFF,
  :Units, mm/d/C, mm/d/C, C, 1/mm, mm/d/C, -, C, -,
  [DEFAULT], HMETS_ddf_min, HMETS_ddf_max, HMETS_T_bm, HMETS_K_cum,
  HMETS_K_f, HMETS_F_e, HMETS_T_bf, HMETS_c_r,
:EndLandUseParameterList

:LandUseParameterList

```

```
:Parameters, GAMMA_SHAPE, GAMMA_SCALE, GAMMA_SHAPE2, GAMMA_SCALE2,  
:Units, -, 1/d, -, 1/d,  
  [DEFAULT], HMETS.alpha1, HMETS.beta1, HMETS.alpha2, HMETS.beta2,  
:EndLandUseParameterList
```

```
# ----Soil Parameters-----  
:SoilParameterList  
:Parameters, POROSITY, PERC_COEFF, PET_CORRECTION, BASEFLOW_COEFF  
:Units, -, 1/d, -, 1/d  
  TOPSOIL, 1.0, HMETS.c_vp, HMETS.ET_eff, HMETS.c_va  
  PHREATIC, 1.0, 0.0, 0.0, HMETS.c_p  
:EndSoilParameterList
```

Listing 16: CH-0053.HMETS.rvt.tpl

```
# meteorological forcings
:GriddedForcing Precipitation
  :ForcingType PRECIP
  :FileNameNC data_obs/RhiresD_v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/RhiresD_v2.0_swiss.
    lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC RhiresD
  :DimNamesNC E N time # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile data_obs/RhiresD_v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing Average Temperature
  :ForcingType TEMP_AVE
  :FileNameNC data_obs/TabsD_v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TabsD_v2.0_swiss.
    lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC TabsD
  :DimNamesNC E N time # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile data_obs/RhiresD_v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing Maximum Temperature
  :ForcingType TEMP_MAX
  :FileNameNC data_obs/TmaxD_v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TmaxD_v2.0_swiss.
    lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC TmaxD
  :DimNamesNC E N time # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile data_obs/RhiresD_v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing Minimum Temperature
  :ForcingType TEMP_MIN
  :FileNameNC data_obs/TminD_v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TminD_v2.0_swiss.
    lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC TminD
  :DimNamesNC E N time # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile data_obs/RhiresD_v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing

# observed streamflow
:RedirectToFile data_obs/TicBel_Q_2020_daily.rvt
```

Listing 17: CH-0053.HMETS.rvc.tpl

```
# ----HRUs-----  
:HRUStateVariableTable # (according to rchlumsk-BMSC-cf9a83c, modelname.rvc.tpl: formerly  
  :InitialConditionsTable)  
:Attributes SOIL[0] SOIL[1]  
:Units mm mm  
1 HMETS_half_Thick_TOP HMETS_half_Thick_PHREATIC  
:EndHRUStateVariableTable
```

Listing 18: ostln_HMETS.txt

```

# ----Model Info-----
# Catchment Name: Ticino
# Catchment ID: CH-0053

# ----General Options-----
ProgramType      ParallelDDS
ObjectiveFunction GCOP
ModelExecutable  ./Ost-RAVEN.sh
PreserveBestModel ./save_best.sh
ModelSubdir processor_

# ----Extra Directories-----
BeginExtraDirs
model
EndExtraDirs

# ----File Pairs-----
BeginFilePairs
CH-0053_HMETS.rvp.tpl; CH-0053_HMETS.rvp
CH-0053_HMETS.rvc.tpl; CH-0053_HMETS.rvc
EndFilePairs

# ----Parameter Specification-----
BeginParams
#parameter      init      low      high      tx_in  tx_ost  tx_out
HMETS_alpha1    random    0.3      20.0     none   none    none
HMETS_beta1     random    0.01     5.0      none   none    none
HMETS_alpha2    random    0.5      13.0     none   none    none
HMETS_beta2     random    0.15     1.5      none   none    none
HMETS_ddf_min   random    1.5      3.0      none   none    none
HMETS_ddf_plus  random    0.0      20.0     none   none    none
HMETS_T_bm      random    -1.0     1.0      none   none    none
HMETS_K_cum     random    0.01     0.2      none   none    none
HMETS_fc_min    random    0.0      0.1      none   none    none
HMETS_fc_plus   random    0.01     0.2      none   none    none
HMETS_C_cum     random    0.005    0.1      none   none    none
HMETS_T_bf      random    -5.0     2.0      none   none    none
HMETS_K_f       random    0.0      5.0      none   none    none
HMETS_F_e       random    0.0      1.0      none   none    none
HMETS_ET_eff    random    0.0      3.0      none   none    none
HMETS_c_r       random    0.0      1.0      none   none    none
HMETS_c_vp      random    0.00001  0.02     none   none    none
HMETS_c_va      random    -5.0     -1.0     none   none    none
HMETS_c_p       random    -5.0     -2.0     none   none    none
HMETS_Thick_TOP random    0.0      0.5      none   none    none
HMETS_Thick_PHREATIC random 0.0      2.0      none   none    none
EndParams

# ----Tied Parameters-----
BeginTiedParams
# 1-parameter linear (TLIN = 2*XVAL)
HMETS_ddf_max 2 HMETS_ddf_min HMETS_ddf_plus linear 0.00 1.00 1.00 0.00 free
HMETS_fc_max 2 HMETS_fc_min HMETS_fc_plus linear 0.00 1.00 1.00 0.00 free
HMETS_half_Thick_TOP 1 HMETS_Thick_TOP linear 500 0.00 free
HMETS_half_Thick_PHREATIC 1 HMETS_Thick_PHREATIC linear 500 0.00 free
EndTiedParams

```

```

# ----Response Variables-----
BeginResponseVars
#name filename keyword line col token augmented?
KGE_NP_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HMETS_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 2 ';' yes
PBIAS_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HMETS_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 3 ';' yes
RMSE_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HMETS_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 4 ';' yes
VE_CALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HMETS_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 5 ';' yes
KGE_NP_Cost ./model/output/CH-0053_HMETS_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 6 ';' no
PBIAS_Cost ./model/output/CH-0053_HMETS_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 7 ';' no
KGE_NP_VALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HMETS_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 2 ';' yes
PBIAS_VALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HMETS_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 3 ';' yes
RMSE_VALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HMETS_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 4 ';' yes
VE_VALI ./model/output/CH-0053_HMETS_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 5 ';' yes
EndResponseVars

# ----GCOP Options-----
BeginGCOP
CostFunction KGE_NP_Cost
PenaltyFunction APM
EndGCOP

# ----Random Seed Control-----
# Randomseed is replaced at runtime
RandomSeed 3333

# ----Algorithm Settings-----
BeginParallelDDSAIlg
PerturbationValue 0.20
MaxIterations 5000
UseRandomParamValues
EndParallelDDSAIlg

```

A.2.4 HYMOD

Listing 19: CH-0053_HYMOD.rvi.tpl

```
# ----Model Organisation-----
:StartDate      1981-01-01 00:00:00
:EndDate        2021-01-01 00:00:00
:TimeStep       1.0
:Method         ORDERED_SERIES
:RunName        CH-0053_HYMOD

# ----Model Options-----
:Routing        ROUTE_NONE
:CatchmentRoute ROUTE_RESERVOIR_SERIES
:Evaporation    PET_HAMON
:OW_Evaporation PET_HAMON
:SWRadiationMethod SW_RAD_NONE
:LWRadiationMethod LW_RAD_NONE
:CloudCoverMethod CLOUDCOV_NONE
:RainSnowFraction RAINSNOW_THRESHOLD
:PotentialMeltMethod POTMELT_DEGREE_DAY
:PrecipIceptFract PRECIP_ICEPT_NONE
:SoilModel      SOIL_MULTILAYER 2
:EvaluationPeriod CALIBRATION 1981-01-01 2000-12-31
:EvaluationPeriod VALIDATION 2001-01-01 2020-12-31

# ----Hydrologic Process Order-----
:HydrologicProcesses
:Precipitation  PRECIP_RAVEN  ATMOS_PRECIP MULTIPLE
:SnowBalance    SNOBAL_SIMPLE_MELT SNOW  PONDED_WATER
:Infiltration   INF_PDM      PONDED_WATER MULTIPLE
:Flush         RAVEN_DEFAULT SURFACE_WATER SOIL[1]  HYMOD_Alpha
:SoilEvaporation SOILEVAP_PDM SOIL[0]    ATMOSPHERE
:Baseflow      BASE_LINEAR  SOIL[1]    SURFACE_WATER
:EndHydrologicProcesses
```

Listing 20: CH-0053_HYMOD.rvh.tpl

```

# -----Subbasins-----
:SubBasins
:Attributes,      NAME, DOWNSTREAM_ID,PROFILE,REACH_LENGTH, GAUGED
:Units           ,      none,      none,  none,      km,      none
                1,      CH-0053,      -1,  NONE,      _AUTO,  1
:EndSubBasins

# -----HRUs-----
:HRUs
:Attributes, AREA, ELEVATION, LATITUDE, LONGITUDE, BASIN_ID,LAND_USE_CLASS
, VEG_CLASS, SOIL_PROFILE, AQUIFER_PROFILE, TERRAIN_CLASS, SLOPE, ASPECT
:Units        , km2,      m,      deg,      deg,      none,      none,      none,
                none,      none,      none, deg,      deg
                1, 1513.760677262317, 1671.7437744140625, 8.960015136416795,
                46.40868158290083, 1, LU_ALL, VEG_ALL, DEFAULT_P,
                [NONE], [NONE], 32.29808044433594, 172.98121643066406
                2, 2.3653035306182244, 2867.020751953125, 8.869017006860698,
                46.49804924907984, 1, GLACIER, GLACIER, GLACIER, [NONE]
                ], [NONE], 22.55500602722168, 200.29884338378903
:EndHRUs

# -----Subbasin Properties-----
:SubBasinProperties
:Parameters, RES_CONSTANT, NUM_RESERVOIRS,
:Units,      1/d,      -,
                1,      HYMOD_K_q,      3,
:EndSubBasinProperties

```

Listing 21: CH-0053_HYMOD.rvp.tpl

```

# -----Soil Classes-----
:SoilClasses
  :Attributes
  :Units
    TOPSOIL
    GWSOIL
:EndSoilClasses

# -----Soil Profiles-----
: SoilProfiles
  LAKE, 0,
  ROCK, 0,
  GLACIER, 0,
  # DEFAULT_P, 2, TOPSOIL, HYMOD_PARA_2, GWSOIL, 10.0
  DEFAULT_P, 2, TOPSOIL, HYMOD_C_max, GWSOIL, 10.0
:EndSoilProfiles

# -----Land Use Classes-----
:LandUseClasses
  :Attributes, IMPERM, FOREST_COV
  :Units, frac, frac
  LU_ALL, 0.02, 0.44
  GLACIER, 0.0, 0.0
:EndLandUseClasses

# -----Vegetation Classes-----
:VegetationClasses
  :Attributes, MAX_HT, MAX_LAI, MAX_LEAF_COND
  :Units, m, none, mm_per_s
  VEG_ALL, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0
  GLACIER, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0
:EndVegetationClasses

# -----Global Parameters-----
:GlobalParameter RAINSNOW_TEMP HYMOD_T_zero

# -----Soil Parameters-----
:SoilParameterList
  :Parameters, POROSITY, PET_CORRECTION, BASEFLOW_COEFF,
  :Units, -, -, 1 / d,
    TOPSOIL, 1.0, HYMOD_PET_Corr, 0.0,
    GWSOIL, 1.0, 1.0, HYMOD_K_s,
:EndSoilParameterList

# -----Land Use Parameters-----
:LandUseParameterList
  :Parameters, MELT_FACTOR, DD_MELT_TEMP, PDM_B,
  :Units, mm / d / K, degC, -,
    [DEFAULT], HYMOD_C_melt, HYMOD_T_melt, HYMOD_B_exp,
:EndLandUseParameterList

```

Listing 22: CH-0053_HYMOD.rvt.tpl

```

# meteorological forcings
:GriddedForcing      Precipitation
  :ForcingType        PRECIP
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          RhiresD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time    # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Average Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_AVE
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TabsD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TabsD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TabsD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time    # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Maximum Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_MAX
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TmaxD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TmaxD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TmaxD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time    # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Minimum Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_MIN
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TminD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TminD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TminD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time    # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing

# observed streamflow
:RedirectToFile data_obs/TicBel.Q.2020_daily.rvt

```

Listing 23: CH-0053_HYMOD.rvc.tpl

```
#-----  
# ---Empty-----  
#-----  
# Nothing to set here.
```

Listing 24: ostIn_HYMOD.txt

```

# ----Model Info-----
# Catchment Name: Ticino
# Catchment ID: CH-0053

# ----General Options-----
ProgramType      ParallelDDS
ObjectiveFunction GCOP
ModelExecutable  ./Ost-RAVEN.sh
PreserveBestModel ./save_best.sh
ModelSubdir processor_

# ----Extra Directories-----
BeginExtraDirs
model
EndExtraDirs

# ----File Pairs-----
BeginFilePairs
CH-0053_HYMOD.rvh.tpl; CH-0053_HYMOD.rvh
CH-0053_HYMOD.rvp.tpl; CH-0053_HYMOD.rvp
CH-0053_HYMOD.rvi.tpl; CH-0053_HYMOD.rvi
EndFilePairs

# ----Parameter Specification-----
BeginParams
#parameter      init      low      high  tx_in  tx_ost  tx_out
HYMOD_K_q       random    0        1     none  none   none
HYMOD_C_max     random    1        2000  none  none   none
HYMOD_T_zero    random    -3       3     none  none   none
HYMOD_K_s       random    0        1     none  none   none
HYMOD_C_melt    random    0        20    none  none   none
HYMOD_T_melt    random    -3       3     none  none   none
HYMOD_B_exp     random    0        10    none  none   none
HYMOD_PET_Corr  random    0.0      1.0   none  none   none
HYMOD_Alpha     random    0        1     none  none   none
EndParams

# ----Response Variables-----
BeginResponseVars
#name  filename      keyword      line  col  token augmented?
KGE_NP_CALI  ./model/output/CH-0053_HYMOD_Diagnostics.csv;
            HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 2 ';' yes
PBIAS_CALI   ./model/output/CH-0053_HYMOD_Diagnostics.csv;
            HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 3 ';' yes
RMSE_CALI    ./model/output/CH-0053_HYMOD_Diagnostics.csv;
            HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 4 ';' yes
VE_CALI      ./model/output/CH-0053_HYMOD_Diagnostics.csv;
            HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 5 ';' yes
KGE_NP_Cost  ./model/output/CH-0053_HYMOD_Diagnostics.csv;
            HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 6 ';' no
PBIAS_Cost   ./model/output/CH-0053_HYMOD_Diagnostics.csv;
            HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 7 ';' no
KGE_NP_VALI  ./model/output/CH-0053_HYMOD_Diagnostics.csv;
            HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 2 ';' yes
PBIAS_VALI   ./model/output/CH-0053_HYMOD_Diagnostics.csv;
            HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 3 ';' yes

```

```

RMSE_VALI  ./model/output/CH-0053_HYMOD_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 4 ';' yes
VE_VALI    ./model/output/CH-0053_HYMOD_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 5 ';' yes
EndResponseVars

# ----GCOP Options-----
BeginGCOP
CostFunction KGE_NP_Cost
PenaltyFunction APM
EndGCOP

# ----Random Seed Control-----
# Randomseed is replaced at runtime
RandomSeed 3333

# ----Algorithm Settings-----
BeginParallelDDSAIlg
PerturbationValue 0.20
MaxIterations 5000
UseRandomParamValues
EndParallelDDSAIlg

```

A.2.5 MOHYSE

Listing 25: CH-0053_MOHYSE.rvi.tpl

```
# ----Model Organisation-----
:StartDate      1981-01-01 00:00:00
:EndDate        2021-01-01 00:00:00
:TimeStep       1.0
:Method         ORDERED_SERIES
:RunName        CH-0053_MOHYSE

# ----Model Options-----
:SoilModel      SOIL_TWO_LAYER
:PotentialMeltMethod POTMELT_DEGREE_DAY
:Routing        ROUTE_NONE
:CatchmentRoute ROUTE_GAMMA_CONVOLUTION
:Evaporation    PET_MOHYSE
:DirectEvaporation
:RainSnowFraction RAINSNOW_THRESHOLD
:EvaluationPeriod CALIBRATION 1981-01-01 2000-12-31
:EvaluationPeriod VALIDATION 2001-01-01 2020-12-31

# ----Hydrologic Process Order-----
:HydrologicProcesses
:SoilEvaporation SOILEVAP_LINEAR SOIL[0]      ATMOSPHERE
:SnowBalance     SNOBAL_SIMPLE_MELT SNOW PONDED_WATER
:Precipitation   RAVEN_DEFAULT ATMOS_PRECIP  MULTIPLE
:Infiltration    INF_HBV                PONDED_WATER SOIL[0]
:Baseflow        BASE_LINEAR            SOIL[0]      SURFACE_WATER
:Percolation     PERC_LINEAR            SOIL[0]      SOIL[1]
:Baseflow        BASE_LINEAR            SOIL[1]      SURFACE_WATER
:EndHydrologicProcesses
```

Listing 26: CH-0053.MOHYSE.rvh.tpl

```

# -----Subbasins-----
:SubBasins
:Attributes,      NAME, DOWNSTREAM_ID,PROFILE,REACH_LENGTH, GAUGED
:Units           ,      none,      none,  none,      km,      none
                1,      CH-0053,      -1,  NONE,      _AUTO,  1
:EndSubBasins

# -----HRUs-----
:HRUs
:Attributes, AREA, ELEVATION, LATITUDE, LONGITUDE, BASIN_ID,LAND_USE_CLASS
, VEG_CLASS, SOIL_PROFILE, AQUIFER_PROFILE, TERRAIN_CLASS, SLOPE, ASPECT
:Units        , km2,      m,      deg,      deg,      none,      none,      none,
                none,      none,      none, deg,      deg
                1, 1513.760677262317, 1671.7437744140625, 8.960015136416795,
                46.40868158290083, 1, LU_ALL, VEG_ALL, DEFAULT_P,
                [NONE], [NONE], 32.29808044433594, 172.98121643066406
                2, 2.3653035306182244, 2867.020751953125, 8.869017006860698,
                46.49804924907984, 1, GLACIER, GLACIER, GLACIER, [NONE]
                ], [NONE], 22.55500602722168, 200.29884338378903
:EndHRUs

# -----Subbasin Properties-----
:SubBasinProperties
:Parameters, GAMMA_SCALE, GAMMA_SHAPE,
:Units,      1/d,      -
                1,      MOHYSE_Gamma_Scale_Beta,
                MOHYSE_Gamma_Shape_Alpha,
:EndSubBasinProperties

```

Listing 27: CH-0053_MOHYSE.rvp.tpl

```

# -----Soil Classes-----
:SoilClasses
  :Attributes,
  :Units,
    TOPSOIL
    GWSOIL
:EndSoilClasses

# -----Soil Profiles-----
:SoilProfiles
  LAKE, 0
  ROCK, 0
  GLACIER, 0
  DEFAULT_P, 2, TOPSOIL, MOHYSE_Thickness_Topsoil, GWSOIL, 10.0
:EndSoilProfiles

# -----Vegetation Classes-----
:VegetationClasses
  :Attributes, MAX_HT, MAX_LAI, MAX_LEAF_COND
  :Units, m, none, mm_per_s
  VEG_ALL, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0
  GLACIER, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0
:EndVegetationClasses

# -----Vegetation Parameters-----
:VegetationParameterList
  :Parameters, SAIHT_RATIO, RAIN_ICEPT_PCT, SNOW_ICEPT_PCT,
  :Units, -, -, -,
  [DEFAULT], 0.0, 0.0, 0.0,
:EndVegetationParameterList

# -----Land Use Classes-----
:LandUseClasses
  :Attributes, IMPERM, FOREST_COV
  :Units, frac, frac
  LU_ALL, 0.02, 0.44
  GLACIER, 0.0, 0.0
:EndLandUseClasses

# -----Global Parameters-----
:GlobalParameter TOC_MULTIPLIER 1.0
:GlobalParameter MOHYSE_PET_COEFF MOHYSE_Pet.Coeff

# -----Land Use Parameters-----
:LandUseParameterList
  :Parameters, MELT_FACTOR, AET_COEFF, FOREST_SPARSENESS, DD_MELT_TEMP,
  :Units, mm/d/K, mm/d, -, degC,
  [DEFAULT], MOHYSE_Melt_Factor, MOHYSE_Aet_Coeff, 0.0,
  MOHYSE_DD_Melt_Temp,
:EndLandUseParameterList

# -----Soil Parameters-----
:SoilParameterList
  :Parameters, POROSITY, PET_CORRECTION, HBV_BETA, BASEFLOW_COEFF,
  PERC_COEFF,
  :Units, -, -, -, 1/d, 1/d
  ,

```

```
TOPSOIL,          1.0 ,          1.0,          1.0,
  MOHYSE_Baseflow_Coeff_Topsoil, MOHYSE_Perc_Coeff_Topsoil,
GWSOIL,          1.0 ,          1.0,          1.0,
  MOHYSE_Baseflow_Coeff_Gwsoil,    0.0,
:EndSoilParameterList
```

Listing 28: CH-0053_MOHYSE.rvt.tpl

```

# meteorological forcings
:GriddedForcing      Precipitation
  :ForcingType        PRECIP
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          RhiresD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time    # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Average Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_AVE
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TabsD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TabsD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TabsD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time    # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Maximum Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_MAX
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TmaxD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TmaxD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TmaxD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time    # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing
:GriddedForcing      Minimum Temperature
  :ForcingType        TEMP_MIN
  :FileNameNC         data_obs/TminD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/TminD.v2.0_swiss.
                      lv95_198101010000_202012310000_CH-0053_clipped.nc
  :VarNameNC          TminD
  :DimNamesNC         E N time    # must be in the order of (x,y,t)
  :RedirectToFile     data_obs/RhiresD.v2.0_swiss.lv95/out/grid_weights_CH-0053.txt
:EndGriddedForcing

# observed streamflow
:RedirectToFile data_obs/TicBel.Q.2020_daily.rvt

```

Listing 29: CH-0053_MOHYSE.rvc.tpl

```
#-----  
# ---Empty-----  
#-----  
# Nothing to set here.
```

Listing 30: ostIn_MOHYSE.txt

```

# ----Model Info-----
# Catchment Name: Ticino
# Catchment ID: CH-0053

# ----General Options-----
ProgramType      ParallelDDS
ObjectiveFunction GCOP
ModelExecutable  ./Ost-RAVEN.sh
PreserveBestModel ./save_best.sh
ModelSubdir processor_

# ----Extra Directories-----
BeginExtraDirs
model
EndExtraDirs

# ----File Pairs-----
BeginFilePairs
CH-0053_MOHYSE.rvp.tpl; CH-0053_MOHYSE.rvp
CH-0053_MOHYSE.rvh.tpl; CH-0053_MOHYSE.rvh
EndFilePairs

# ----Parameter Specification-----
BeginParams
#parameter      init      low      high      tx_in  tx_ost  tx_out
MOHYSE_Pet_Coeff      random      0.5      2      none  none
MOHYSE_Aet_Coeff      random      0.5      1      none  none
MOHYSE_Melt_Factor      random      2      4      none  none
MOHYSE_DD_Melt_Temp      random      -5      5      none  none
MOHYSE_Thickness_Topsoil      random      0.5      10      none  none
MOHYSE_Perc_Coeff_Topsoil      random      0.01      0.99  none  none
none
MOHYSE_Baseflow_Coeff_Topsoil      random      0.01      0.99  none  none
none
MOHYSE_Baseflow_Coeff_Gwsoil      random      0.01      0.99  none  none
none
MOHYSE_Gamma_Shape_Alpha      random      0.5      5      none  none
MOHYSE_Gamma_Scale_Beta      random      0.01      20     none  none
EndParams

# ----Response Variables-----
BeginResponseVars
#name  filename      keyword      line  col  token  augmented?
KGE_NP_CALI  ./model/output/CH-0053_MOHYSE_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 2 ';' yes
PBIAS_CALI  ./model/output/CH-0053_MOHYSE_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 3 ';' yes
RMSE_CALI  ./model/output/CH-0053_MOHYSE_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 4 ';' yes
VE_CALI  ./model/output/CH-0053_MOHYSE_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 5 ';' yes
KGE_NP_Cost  ./model/output/CH-0053_MOHYSE_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 6 ';' no
PBIAS_Cost  ./model/output/CH-0053_MOHYSE_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_CALIBRATION 0 7 ';' no
KGE_NP_VALI  ./model/output/CH-0053_MOHYSE_Diagnostics.csv;
HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 2 ';' yes

```

```

PBIAS_VALI    ./model/output/CH-0053_MOHYSE_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 3 ';' yes
RMSE_VALI    ./model/output/CH-0053_MOHYSE_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 4 ';' yes
VE_VALI      ./model/output/CH-0053_MOHYSE_Diagnostics.csv;
  HYDROGRAPH_VALIDATION 0 5    ';' yes
EndResponseVars

# ----GCOP Options-----
BeginGCOP
CostFunction KGE_NP_Cost
PenaltyFunction APM
EndGCOP

# ----Random Seed Control-----
# Randomseed is replaced at runtime
RandomSeed 3333

# ----Algorithm Settings-----
BeginParallelDDSAIg
PerturbationValue 0.20
MaxIterations 5000
UseRandomParamValues
EndParallelDDSAIg

```

B Calibrated Parameter Values

B.1 GR4J

Table 18: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Broye catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	0.28	0.28	0.29	0.30	0.30	0.23	0.29	0.28	0.28	0.32	0.25	0.28	0.25	0.24	0.25	0.33	0.27	0.27	0.26	0.26
x2	-0.22	-0.22	-0.19	-0.22	-0.19	-0.24	-0.22	-0.22	-0.23	-0.20	-0.23	-0.22	-0.23	-0.24	-0.23	-0.21	-0.21	-0.23	-0.22	-0.20
x3	32.15	30.95	25.80	31.92	25.16	35.21	31.45	30.78	34.02	27.49	34.09	30.78	33.00	35.48	33.60	30.63	27.92	33.50	30.11	27.14
x4	1.39	1.43	1.50	1.41	1.52	1.37	1.40	1.41	1.40	1.42	1.38	1.41	1.41	1.36	1.38	1.42	1.47	1.38	1.43	1.50
Cemaneige_x1	2.52	2.52	2.51	2.50	2.49	2.52	2.53	2.56	2.49	2.52	2.48	2.50	2.44	2.59	2.51	2.51	2.68	2.44	2.52	2.56
Cemaneige_x2	0.77	0.08	0.46	0.43	0.20	0.34	0.80	0.79	0.21	0.97	0.91	0.51	0.45	0.82	0.44	0.00	0.17	0.51	0.60	0.74

Table 19: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Dischma catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	0.47	0.43	0.43	0.39	0.46	0.44	0.42	0.46	0.42	0.45	0.41	0.42	0.46	0.43	0.44	0.46	0.43	0.40	0.45	0.45
x2	2.45	2.07	2.00	1.78	2.53	2.02	1.94	2.50	1.88	2.11	1.88	1.90	2.18	1.97	2.01	2.35	1.90	1.78	2.28	2.47
x3	42.91	31.86	30.26	24.17	45.05	31.15	28.70	44.07	27.02	33.24	26.91	27.44	35.18	29.45	30.63	39.91	27.89	24.48	37.72	43.03
x4	1.15	1.18	1.19	1.22	1.15	1.19	1.19	1.15	1.20	1.18	1.20	1.21	1.17	1.19	1.20	1.16	1.18	1.23	1.17	1.15
Cemaneige_x1	99.98	99.95	99.83	99.98	99.99	99.93	99.93	99.90	99.99	100.00	99.93	99.98	99.88	99.99	99.96	99.97	99.95	99.99	100.00	99.95
Cemaneige_x2	0.92	0.65	0.45	0.26	0.60	0.27	0.15	0.35	0.87	0.42	0.25	0.32	0.03	0.33	0.07	0.30	0.21	0.27	0.29	0.68

Table 20: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Lonza catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	0.10	0.16	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.16	0.10	0.19	0.23	0.27	0.23	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.16	0.22	0.26	0.10	0.10	0.22
x2	3.00	2.99	2.99	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.99	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.99	2.99	3.00	2.99	3.00
x3	19.94	21.90	23.26	23.38	23.41	21.61	20.05	22.64	23.23	24.17	23.34	19.96	20.13	20.23	21.90	23.17	24.18	20.05	19.87	23.06
x4	1.23	1.22	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.21	1.23	1.21	1.21	1.21	1.21	1.24	1.23	1.23	1.23	1.22	1.21	1.23	1.24	1.22
Cemaneige_x1	100.00	99.97	99.94	99.95	99.89	99.98	99.99	99.92	99.85	99.98	99.97	99.93	99.99	99.97	99.89	99.90	99.98	99.93	99.84	99.95
Cemaneige_x2	0.02	0.98	0.67	0.27	0.69	0.08	0.70	0.84	0.21	0.93	0.42	0.78	0.39	0.65	1.00	0.25	0.03	0.90	0.05	0.53

Table 21: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Lütshine catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	0.39	0.37	0.36	0.40	0.37	0.39	0.39	0.39	0.39	0.41	0.39	0.39	0.40	0.39	0.38	0.38	0.37	0.40	0.38	0.37
x2	2.27	2.16	2.03	2.30	2.11	2.20	2.22	2.20	2.24	2.40	2.22	2.21	2.31	2.18	2.16	2.36	2.18	2.34	2.18	2.17
x3	36.78	33.51	29.22	38.20	31.72	34.94	35.19	34.62	36.15	41.07	35.77	34.97	37.56	34.39	33.37	38.81	33.75	39.40	34.12	33.60
x4	1.12	1.13	1.13	1.11	1.13	1.12	1.12	1.13	1.12	1.11	1.12	1.12	1.10	1.12	1.13	1.11	1.13	1.12	1.12	1.13
Cemaneige_x1	99.97	99.91	99.98	99.96	99.97	99.96	99.94	100.00	99.91	99.86	99.90	99.97	99.95	99.99	99.96	99.97	99.98	99.99	99.93	99.99
Cemaneige_x2	0.52	0.77	0.28	0.61	0.09	0.22	0.17	0.12	0.69	0.40	0.22	0.63	0.93	0.72	0.55	0.91	0.43	0.05	0.73	0.26

Table 22: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Massa catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
x2	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.99	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.99	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
x3	4.67	5.05	4.76	4.89	4.56	4.73	4.95	4.76	4.46	4.70	4.64	3.55	4.91	4.87	4.52	4.61	4.41	4.83	5.04	4.58
x4	1.33	1.31	1.32	1.31	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.33	2.30	1.33	1.32	1.32	1.32	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.33
Cemaneige_x1	2.83	3.34	2.91	3.25	3.30	2.99	3.60	3.09	3.06	2.91	4.14	3.45	3.27	2.91	3.07	2.90	2.87	3.11	3.26	3.27
Cemaneige_x2	0.62	0.05	0.60	0.06	0.02	0.85	0.84	0.66	0.28	0.86	0.43	0.78	0.21	0.55	0.51	0.02	0.48	0.35	0.49	0.26

Table 23: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Rhône catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
x2	3.00	2.99	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.99	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.99	3.00	3.00	3.00
x3	11.66	11.83	11.69	11.78	11.78	11.93	11.86	11.86	11.64	11.91	11.98	11.83	11.76	12.01	11.69	11.51	12.02	11.80	12.19	11.84
x4	1.25	1.24	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.23	1.24	1.25	1.24	1.26	1.23	1.25	1.25	1.22	1.23	1.25	1.24	1.23	1.23	1.26
Cemaneige_x1	99.88	99.94	99.99	100.00	99.95	99.97	99.93	99.86	99.96	100.00	99.87	99.99	99.99	99.94	99.93	99.89	99.96	99.95	99.96	99.94
Cemaneige_x2	0.40	0.76	0.89	0.34	0.79	0.35	0.35	0.84	0.58	0.90	0.87	0.41	0.35	1.00	0.59	0.47	0.02	0.66	0.06	0.59

Table 24: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Saltina catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.20
x2	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.99	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.99	3.00	2.99	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
x3	229.49	229.44	229.64	230.03	227.37	229.41	228.66	229.27	228.84	230.61	229.28	229.47	229.10	229.35	228.84	229.48	229.20	229.21	228.49	226.85
x4	0.60	0.57	0.58	0.59	0.58	0.58	0.58	0.60	0.59	0.52	0.60	0.59	0.60	0.58	0.60	0.58	0.60	0.60	0.58	0.58
Cemaneige_x1	99.95	99.96	99.93	99.92	99.95	99.97	99.97	99.97	99.96	99.99	99.94	99.99	99.93	99.98	99.94	99.97	100.00	99.75	99.93	99.95
Cemaneige_x2	0.67	0.75	0.38	0.50	0.82	0.91	0.33	0.66	0.76	0.64	0.95	0.84	0.94	0.61	0.05	0.87	0.08	0.17	0.94	0.96

Table 25: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Sitter catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	0.16	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.16	0.17	0.17	0.16	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17
x2	0.54	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.54	0.52	0.54	0.52	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.52	0.55	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.54
x3	51.51	49.11	48.97	48.63	50.25	47.24	49.89	48.34	49.70	50.57	49.91	48.82	51.98	49.91	50.18	51.68	50.43	49.65	50.36	49.51
x4	0.90	0.92	0.93	0.95	0.90	1.01	0.91	0.95	0.89	0.94	0.91	0.93	0.85	0.91	0.89	0.88	0.90	0.92	0.89	0.91
Cemaneige_x1	100.00	99.98	99.95	99.96	99.97	99.92	99.88	100.00	99.82	99.96	99.98	99.95	99.88	99.97	99.94	99.98	99.98	99.96	99.99	99.97
Cemaneige_x2	0.52	0.29	0.91	0.01	0.36	0.26	0.08	0.45	0.56	0.92	0.55	0.18	0.66	0.20	0.30	0.92	0.10	0.65	0.25	0.72

Table 26: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Thur catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11
x2	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.31	0.32	0.31	0.31	0.33	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.31	0.32	0.33	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.32
x3	27.07	27.36	27.19	27.27	27.25	27.24	27.26	27.64	27.11	27.55	27.02	26.95	27.00	27.37	27.71	27.40	26.85	27.30	26.96	27.24
x4	1.81	1.83	1.79	1.80	1.79	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.84	1.80	1.84	1.84	1.84	1.80	1.80	1.80	1.85	1.79	1.85	1.83
Cemaneige_x1	95.38	94.56	95.90	96.19	91.87	96.79	96.54	94.81	93.43	96.08	93.90	95.87	91.29	94.34	96.14	95.14	95.52	92.52	92.14	94.81
Cemaneige_x2	0.87	0.93	0.30	0.29	0.91	0.86	0.24	0.66	0.66	0.14	0.57	0.55	0.22	0.17	0.02	0.61	0.20	0.98	0.74	0.20

Table 27: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Ticino catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	0.92	0.92	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.92	0.93	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.93	0.92	0.93	0.93	0.92	0.94	0.93
x2	2.80	2.67	3.00	2.99	2.99	2.98	2.81	2.95	2.98	2.90	3.00	3.00	2.99	3.00	3.00	2.96	2.96	2.76	3.00	2.82
x3	93.14	87.85	103.60	103.04	101.47	103.01	95.23	100.16	101.61	97.96	102.32	102.80	102.76	102.71	102.65	100.89	100.42	91.19	103.46	95.23
x4	1.07	1.09	0.63	0.65	0.68	0.69	1.07	0.65	0.69	0.60	0.54	0.58	0.58	0.71	0.71	0.67	0.67	1.08	0.64	1.06
Cemaneige_x1	99.88	99.71	99.90	99.88	99.78	99.01	99.85	99.93	99.88	99.92	99.99	99.92	99.77	99.81	99.91	100.00	99.93	99.34	99.90	99.81
Cemaneige_x2	0.12	0.86	0.76	0.36	0.37	0.30	0.57	0.45	0.42	0.28	0.67	0.45	0.45	0.74	0.93	0.36	0.06	0.97	0.32	0.24

Table 28: Optimal parameter sets for GR4J generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Venoge catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
x1	0.26	0.29	0.30	0.27	0.30	0.26	0.29	0.28	0.27	0.30	0.31	0.29	0.29	0.26	0.30	0.24	0.28	0.30	0.29	0.27
x2	-0.47	-0.39	-0.35	-0.43	-0.35	-0.43	-0.35	-0.42	-0.43	-0.35	-0.34	-0.36	-0.38	-0.41	-0.35	-0.49	-0.40	-0.36	-0.36	-0.40
x3	92.46	72.22	64.90	82.29	65.27	83.37	63.15	80.40	83.77	63.60	61.62	66.47	70.96	76.45	64.16	94.92	76.60	67.54	66.35	74.18
x4	1.29	1.37	1.42	1.32	1.40	1.32	1.39	1.31	1.31	1.39	1.43	1.39	1.37	1.32	1.38	1.25	1.35	1.38	1.39	1.36
Cemaneige_x1	61.47	63.48	63.06	61.41	63.62	61.61	65.14	60.64	61.01	64.67	64.83	63.86	61.81	62.66	63.92	62.83	61.62	62.56	63.72	63.05
Cemaneige_x2	0.01	0.28	0.10	0.95	0.29	0.77	0.73	0.52	0.54	0.36	0.71	0.67	0.50	0.65	0.37	0.79	0.26	0.23	0.06	0.39

B.2 HBV

Table 29: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Broye catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	1.89	2.05	1.83	2.01	1.88	1.90	2.99	2.78	1.97	1.64	1.62	1.72	1.92	1.98	1.87	2.07	1.57	1.99	1.98	1.83
Melt_Fact	2.50	2.51	1.98	3.15	3.05	2.37	1.05	1.07	1.58	1.94	2.26	3.24	2.80	3.82	1.56	3.16	3.27	2.92	2.50	2.40
Refreeze_Fact	1.72	3.27	2.80	0.03	3.14	0.85	0.47	2.88	2.79	2.10	0.26	2.69	0.05	2.95	0.76	1.64	2.50	2.93	0.00	0.07
Snow_SWI	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.06
Porosity	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.11
Field_Cap	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.46	1.00	0.27	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.74	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.96	1.00	0.98
Beta	0.36	0.23	0.42	0.14	0.18	0.03	1.32	6.84	0.43	0.30	0.19	0.13	0.38	0.18	0.37	0.35	0.20	0.15	0.36	0.19
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	432.24	11.81	267.17	830.99	14.84	14.89	13.31	761.90	686.17	6.80	9.89	11.00	824.44	12.38	12.21	24.39	10.95	12.78	727.09	14.19
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.12	0.59	0.56	0.02	0.03	0.38	0.14	0.28	0.09	0.31	0.60	0.13	0.35	0.59	0.59	0.54	0.43	0.22	0.56	0.18
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.06	0.04	0.07	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.09	0.10	0.07	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.04
T_Conc_Max_Bas	1.01	2.49	1.01	1.01	1.25	1.28	1.24	1.14	1.03	2.34	2.45	2.23	1.01	2.24	2.23	1.01	2.32	2.16	1.03	1.29
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	22.66	4.13	13.32	59.92	87.93	0.06	42.81	40.74	28.28	10.21	43.79	82.22	3.74	20.43	68.06	7.86	18.06	32.96	59.42	13.37
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	3.02	0.07	3.00	0.16	0.11	0.16	4.87	3.81	6.34	6.31	2.80	4.05	6.86	3.61	6.24	4.43	3.42	0.27	4.96	2.14
Sat_Wilt	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.00
Alpha	4.42	6.98	5.82	3.04	2.38	0.68	4.47	4.03	3.69	0.09	0.08	0.73	2.80	0.47	6.79	4.24	0.26	0.73	3.45	0.99
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.10	0.00	0.89	1.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02
Thickness_Topsoil	1.35	0.50	1.23	1.68	0.49	0.16	2.06	4.16	1.22	1.63	0.13	0.66	1.31	0.21	1.23	1.19	0.40	0.29	1.23	0.48
Melt_For_Corr	0.11	0.60	0.12	0.17	0.13	0.39	0.11	0.06	0.43	0.02	0.78	0.29	0.13	0.02	0.08	0.28	0.03	0.29	0.09	0.22
Glac_Storage_Effect	0.51	1.96	1.22	1.84	0.45	1.02	1.28	1.54	0.67	0.98	1.39	0.34	1.86	1.87	0.54	1.77	0.94	1.04	1.03	1.18

Table 30: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Dischma catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	-2.10	-1.87	-2.02	-2.48	-2.41	-2.11	-2.00	-1.06	-2.12	-2.41	-2.43	-2.33	-2.30	-2.15	-2.28	-1.44	-1.29	-1.00	-1.37	-2.09
Melt_Fact	2.39	2.22	2.57	2.90	3.40	2.43	2.60	3.30	2.66	3.38	2.67	3.36	3.38	2.70	2.93	3.36	3.45	3.01	3.62	2.45
Refreeze_Fact	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.37	0.79	0.03	0.08	0.29	0.03	1.07	0.11	0.24	0.65	0.04	0.45	1.21	1.29	0.02	1.87	0.02
Snow_SWI	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.05
Porosity	0.23	0.20	0.17	0.19	0.21	0.22	0.20	0.12	0.17	0.21	0.19	0.19	0.21	0.21	0.23	0.14	0.13	0.23	0.10	0.22
Field_Cap	0.21	0.19	0.31	0.25	0.34	0.25	0.24	0.22	0.16	0.38	0.36	0.41	0.28	0.16	0.28	0.01	0.25	0.09	0.26	0.08
Beta	5.43	6.98	6.28	3.94	5.35	6.87	5.33	4.79	6.94	4.90	6.95	6.90	6.83	6.99	6.85	5.96	5.84	2.13	3.80	5.08
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	26.24	25.18	934.33	31.95	37.89	29.65	869.37	29.29	38.69	37.46	975.94	629.62	33.86	34.46	792.71	32.24	34.17	35.51	36.54	29.30
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.36	0.42	0.46	0.28	0.32	0.59	0.06	0.56	0.56	0.04	0.03	0.18	0.36	0.25	0.30	0.50	0.19	0.18	0.38	0.54
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.09
T_Conc_Max_Bas	1.69	1.76	1.01	1.71	1.48	1.63	1.02	1.87	1.01	1.00	1.01	1.01	1.74	1.69	1.08	1.76	1.75	1.13	1.77	1.71
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	95.21	75.93	46.07	35.74	50.42	5.86	29.82	83.05	37.05	47.50	75.65	77.34	22.88	27.19	96.01	99.91	0.76	69.70	91.83	6.41
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	0.18	4.06	2.44	6.03	0.69	6.93	3.30	3.63	3.46	1.10	3.72	5.31	2.08	0.18	6.58	2.86	1.18	0.45	6.82	6.41
Sat_Wilt	0.56	0.53	0.66	0.60	0.71	0.60	0.59	0.57	0.51	0.75	0.72	0.78	0.65	0.51	0.63	0.37	0.61	0.44	0.62	0.43
Alpha	7.56	7.59	7.89	3.95	5.70	0.94	4.42	3.29	5.16	1.02	4.42	0.51	2.85	4.16	1.57	3.45	8.88	2.94	6.45	4.57
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.94	0.99	0.66	0.96	0.41	0.52	0.62	0.98	0.10	0.61	0.96	0.33	0.77	0.99	0.28	0.06	0.49	0.38	0.53	0.92
Thickness_Topsoil	0.12	0.11	0.12	0.14	0.11	0.11	0.10	0.13	0.13	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.10	0.15	0.11
Melt_For_Corr	0.04	0.93	0.82	0.28	0.15	0.15	0.24	0.06	0.29	0.33	0.09	0.01	0.54	0.02	0.16	0.02	0.01	0.17	0.03	0.30
Glac_Storage_Effect	0.11	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.10

Table 31: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Lonza catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	-2.88	-2.50	-3.00	-2.99	-2.68	-3.00	-2.99	-3.00	-3.00	-2.94	-2.98	-2.94	-3.00	-2.51	-3.00	-2.99	-2.47	-2.99	-3.00	-2.97
Melt_Fact	1.50	1.14	1.76	1.73	1.31	1.51	1.51	1.39	1.43	1.39	1.45	1.45	1.49	1.22	1.80	1.43	1.36	1.81	1.79	1.38
Refreeze_Fact	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Snow_SWI	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Porosity	0.59	0.58	0.60	0.60	0.59	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.58	0.60	0.58	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.57	0.59	0.59	0.60
Field_Cap	0.05	0.59	0.07	0.07	0.64	0.33	0.44	0.23	0.53	0.17	0.35	0.39	0.46	0.66	0.01	0.39	0.56	0.00	0.01	0.61
Beta	0.89	0.83	0.82	1.04	0.63	1.25	0.77	0.81	1.16	1.15	0.94	1.02	0.77	0.81	0.91	0.81	6.33	0.58	0.56	0.91
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	12.38	900.61	824.63	844.32	58.90	47.73	78.85	47.50	838.27	61.80	63.15	8.33	663.78	50.52	88.55	60.45	47.93	927.47	382.84	14.51
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.33	0.56	0.22	0.39	0.02	0.18	0.40	0.25	0.22	0.22	0.41	0.32	0.26	0.53	0.18	0.37	0.59	0.34	0.15	0.32
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.06	0.29	0.05	0.05	0.60	0.49	0.52	0.60	0.58	0.60	0.58	0.06	0.50	0.60	0.05	0.60	0.21	0.05	0.05	0.07
T_Conc_Max_Bas	1.00	1.36	1.34	1.33	1.37	1.08	1.30	1.45	1.43	1.37	1.45	1.25	1.39	1.41	1.36	1.49	1.36	1.35	1.33	1.73
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	66.04	76.72	92.83	16.56	34.13	18.17	70.14	52.22	5.78	54.10	7.07	35.27	18.19	41.06	51.73	76.31	11.88	52.47	95.90	64.01
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	4.04	3.56	0.26	2.26	6.49	2.10	2.71	1.99	3.41	1.37	3.70	6.41	5.47	2.58	3.91	1.38	2.50	4.79	5.51	0.89
Sat_Wilt	0.43	0.75	0.88	0.88	0.89	0.74	0.85	0.54	0.88	0.48	0.72	0.73	0.84	0.85	0.90	0.74	0.80	0.89	0.90	0.90
Alpha	0.01	7.16	7.94	2.27	3.54	0.54	6.63	0.36	0.79	7.78	6.36	0.02	2.11	7.38	1.28	2.59	6.07	8.29	3.96	4.41
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.43	0.14	0.20	0.07	0.05	0.48	0.86	0.69	0.21	0.39	0.60	0.30	0.80	0.55	0.06	0.85	0.81	0.45	0.74	0.21
Thickness_Topsoil	0.11	0.11	0.13	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.13	0.10	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.11
Melt_For_Corr	0.96	0.91	0.62	0.02	0.99	0.96	0.55	0.99	0.89	0.96	0.75	0.93	0.61	0.97	0.61	0.96	0.02	0.27	0.33	0.91
Glac_Storage_Effect	1.99	1.70	2.00	1.98	0.12	0.13	0.12	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.12	1.99	0.13	0.11	2.00	0.12	1.95	2.00	2.00	2.00

Table 32: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Lütschine catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	-2.48	-2.50	-2.57	-2.70	-2.62	-2.54	-2.82	-2.41	-2.52	-2.74	-2.54	-2.56	-2.50	-2.76	-2.52	-2.43	-2.59	-2.47	-2.61	-2.78
Melt_Fact	1.01	1.02	1.01	1.02	1.00	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.00	1.00	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.01	1.00	1.00	1.01
Refreeze_Fact	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00
Snow_SWI	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Porosity	0.60	0.60	0.59	0.60	0.60	0.59	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.59	0.59
Field_Cap	0.59	0.20	0.53	0.81	0.20	0.84	0.32	0.99	0.48	0.54	0.09	0.77	0.26	0.30	0.75	0.64	0.86	0.17	0.65	0.88
Beta	0.45	0.44	0.45	0.41	0.44	0.54	0.33	0.60	0.43	0.44	0.38	0.37	0.43	0.45	0.43	0.37	0.38	0.48	0.40	0.64
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	584.44	619.14	26.65	330.19	397.12	767.96	35.52	588.05	42.47	849.19	560.97	41.03	26.69	508.32	956.99	38.54	32.10	917.19	769.95	663.53
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.32	0.21	0.27	0.35	0.41	0.39	0.27	0.20	0.13	0.08	0.24	0.53	0.21	0.47	0.42	0.45	0.32	0.41	0.20	0.52
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
T_Conc_Max_Bas	1.01	1.01	1.04	1.01	1.03	1.03	1.01	1.00	1.02	1.00	1.00	1.02	1.03	1.01	1.00	1.00	1.03	1.01	1.02	1.02
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	76.11	57.79	86.98	75.17	84.37	2.15	59.92	74.26	95.51	96.22	60.40	69.94	97.85	43.60	35.80	99.18	93.69	97.00	49.08	32.43
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	6.52	0.95	5.79	2.15	6.14	0.28	5.67	4.25	4.78	5.80	0.33	0.23	4.24	3.91	5.57	0.60	1.54	1.06	3.78	3.00
Sat_Wilt	0.53	0.14	0.39	0.76	0.17	0.78	0.31	0.81	0.46	0.53	0.06	0.68	0.25	0.22	0.73	0.60	0.83	0.06	0.62	0.61
Alpha	0.32	4.98	0.15	6.78	5.72	8.90	5.07	6.78	4.41	2.37	4.20	0.12	0.19	0.01	2.63	6.19	0.09	4.29	6.57	1.32
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.16	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06
Thickness_Topsoil	0.15	0.11	0.15	0.13	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.18	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.14	0.11	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.16	0.12	0.19
Melt_For_Corr	0.97	0.01	0.99	0.07	0.03	0.11	0.21	0.99	0.31	0.09	0.99	0.98	0.31	0.07	0.06	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.08	0.08
Glac_Storage_Effect	0.68	0.71	0.60	0.77	0.69	0.75	0.70	0.68	0.72	0.74	0.64	0.61	0.67	0.80	0.71	0.68	0.62	0.66	0.69	0.77

Table 33: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Massa catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	-2.40	-2.75	-0.59	-2.72	-2.91	-0.43	2.36	-2.58	-2.19	-0.42	-2.15	-2.65	-2.14	-0.04	-2.08	-0.18	-2.30	0.35	-2.15	1.65
Melt_Fact	2.36	1.93	2.49	1.87	1.99	2.45	2.53	2.20	2.15	2.47	2.48	2.04	2.50	2.27	2.47	2.65	2.21	2.44	2.49	2.77
Refreeze_Fact	3.46	1.83	3.30	2.08	1.90	1.61	0.00	2.39	1.75	1.69	3.48	1.64	3.49	1.73	3.49	3.44	2.44	0.76	3.47	1.79
Snow_SWI	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Porosity	0.26	0.59	0.60	0.56	0.53	0.10	0.10	0.54	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.60	0.11	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.14	0.11	0.15	0.10
Field_Cap	0.12	0.51	0.02	0.03	0.76	0.80	0.32	0.03	0.88	0.06	0.16	0.87	0.33	0.40	0.71	0.33	0.06	0.81	0.35	0.16
Beta	2.95	4.65	0.04	1.57	3.67	3.46	2.51	0.81	1.74	1.27	3.20	2.78	0.84	1.94	3.50	5.74	2.87	4.01	6.55	0.15
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	10.73	8.71	935.78	5.09	8.63	742.14	25.81	853.68	881.36	990.96	698.51	818.19	990.41	9.17	908.82	510.73	9.09	949.68	75.19	22.04
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.37	0.44	0.13	0.40	0.58	0.42	0.34	0.08	0.27	0.49	0.43	0.51	0.40	0.49	0.59	0.55	0.44	0.13	0.53	0.10
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.17	0.16	0.24	0.12	0.18	0.33	0.23	0.37	0.43	0.32	0.60	0.47	0.60	0.14	0.60	0.23	0.17	0.32	0.60	0.13
T_Conc_Max_Bas	1.16	1.09	1.01	1.15	1.02	1.00	1.00	1.02	1.03	1.01	1.49	1.02	1.50	1.06	1.54	1.06	1.19	1.01	1.41	1.03
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	64.35	61.59	64.62	32.38	58.08	35.78	62.68	43.62	22.56	15.31	22.58	8.03	35.72	89.48	88.04	55.35	35.38	17.73	94.62	14.98
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	1.14	1.06	0.43	5.52	6.24	1.53	2.43	5.64	3.60	2.90	5.13	5.36	5.24	0.07	5.75	5.69	6.69	4.15	1.84	5.62
Sat_Wilt	0.12	0.51	0.02	0.03	0.76	0.81	0.32	0.03	0.89	0.07	0.18	0.88	0.35	0.40	0.73	0.34	0.07	0.82	0.37	0.16
Alpha	7.57	6.25	0.04	4.61	7.79	0.14	3.73	7.82	5.22	4.43	0.45	0.71	1.08	0.09	3.41	1.70	0.15	7.41	2.48	8.94
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.32	0.02	0.09	0.50	0.07	0.02	0.36	1.00	0.60	0.52	0.89	0.46	0.30	0.36	0.80	0.35	0.46	0.78	0.03	0.37
Thickness_Topsoil	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.16	0.11	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.12	0.15	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.11
Melt_For_Corr	0.06	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.98	0.26	0.17	0.36	0.70	0.10	0.01	0.99	0.02	0.99	0.02	0.19	0.91	0.54	0.02	0.98
Glac_Storage_Effect	0.51	1.99	0.35	0.70	0.51	0.88	0.11	0.85	0.19	0.46	0.12	0.80	0.11	1.77	0.46	0.87	1.30	0.42	0.14	1.50

Table 34: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Rhône catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	-3.00	-2.99	-2.99	-2.99	-2.96	-2.99	-2.99	-3.00	-2.99	-3.00	-3.00	-2.99	-2.97	-2.99	-2.98	-2.86	-2.99	-2.99	-2.99	-3.00
Melt_Fact	1.95	1.87	1.95	1.98	1.97	2.06	1.96	1.96	1.99	1.98	1.95	1.95	1.87	2.15	1.96	1.88	1.85	2.00	1.99	1.99
Refreeze_Fact	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Snow_SWI	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Porosity	0.60	0.59	0.60	0.60	0.59	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.59	0.59	0.60	0.60	0.59	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.58	0.60	0.59	0.60
Field_Cap	0.96	0.00	0.84	0.57	0.16	0.36	0.48	0.84	0.87	0.58	0.19	0.25	0.03	0.26	0.03	0.17	0.00	0.15	0.98	0.92
Beta	1.57	1.77	1.55	0.38	1.54	0.89	0.39	2.01	1.42	1.88	1.73	0.85	3.88	0.38	1.64	0.92	0.71	0.37	0.58	1.60
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	972.65	7.76	507.92	8.26	10.59	323.04	8.31	12.63	11.33	12.16	5.44	14.33	5.20	920.03	572.10	6.83	8.82	5.70	8.00	406.93
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.46	0.33	0.55	0.03	0.02	0.12	0.04	0.03	0.40	0.01	0.02	0.45	0.01	0.43	0.15	0.02	0.29	0.16	0.15	0.38
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.60	0.33	0.60	0.28	0.45	0.05	0.31	0.55	0.40	0.49	0.53	0.52	0.28	0.05	0.60	0.05	0.04	0.19	0.25	0.60
T_Conc_Max_Bas	1.00	1.00	1.02	1.00	1.01	1.52	1.03	1.06	1.01	1.02	1.01	1.00	1.00	1.45	1.01	1.49	1.49	1.04	1.02	1.01
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	50.81	43.34	10.57	46.63	50.58	59.29	82.27	91.12	10.52	8.02	16.91	13.99	46.45	60.25	37.32	89.39	12.10	58.68	58.18	22.22
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	4.94	4.58	1.20	0.41	4.73	3.04	4.75	4.41	0.16	1.87	2.84	5.89	1.25	0.06	4.50	2.58	0.20	4.65	6.76	6.82
Sat_Wilt	0.85	0.90	0.68	0.32	0.01	0.01	0.33	0.34	0.30	0.45	0.05	0.20	0.90	0.15	0.02	0.71	0.74	0.01	0.65	0.77
Alpha	2.31	0.34	4.76	4.87	1.38	7.64	5.16	7.28	0.32	1.64	1.09	0.33	1.36	7.74	1.69	8.57	0.20	0.56	0.61	3.12
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.04	0.16	0.01	0.00	0.05	0.07	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.18	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.00
Thickness_Topsoil	0.36	0.10	0.40	0.11	0.31	0.15	0.12	0.41	0.35	0.38	0.33	0.16	0.11	0.11	0.37	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.15	0.41
Melt_For_Corr	0.34	0.49	0.53	0.81	0.59	0.34	0.05	0.41	0.70	0.85	0.42	0.18	0.98	0.65	0.04	0.36	0.66	0.97	0.74	0.34
Glac_Storage_Effect	0.17	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.16	1.85	0.16	0.17	0.16	0.17	0.16	0.16	0.16	1.68	0.16	1.68	1.67	0.16	0.17	0.17

Table 35: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Saltina catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	-2.97	-2.88	-2.91	-2.95	-2.99	-2.94	-2.94	-2.86	-2.95	-2.95	-2.93	-2.95	-2.87	-2.97	-2.95	-2.90	-2.98	-2.86	-2.94	-2.93
Melt_Fact	7.12	6.28	6.96	7.39	6.94	6.74	6.84	6.46	7.23	6.37	6.84	7.88	6.63	7.03	6.79	6.99	7.38	6.56	6.73	7.19
Refreeze_Fact	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	2.27	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00
Snow_SWI	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Porosity	0.58	0.57	0.10	0.59	0.58	0.47	0.34	0.44	0.41	0.37	0.58	0.60	0.42	0.10	0.60	0.19	0.59	0.47	0.56	0.59
Field_Cap	0.61	0.78	0.99	0.61	0.66	0.35	0.86	0.73	0.84	0.33	0.48	0.52	0.29	1.00	0.96	0.98	0.77	0.73	0.90	1.00
Beta	0.04	0.15	1.45	0.19	0.21	0.11	0.06	0.12	0.17	0.10	0.15	0.24	0.13	2.80	0.37	0.88	0.13	0.13	0.22	0.36
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	68.91	45.55	52.14	45.76	43.01	32.01	619.73	44.27	744.48	31.43	44.01	892.04	47.77	38.13	995.01	65.32	42.65	34.06	37.06	43.14
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.23	0.21	0.41	0.33	0.10	0.49	0.24	0.11	0.46	0.48	0.22	0.08	0.46	0.37	0.28	0.57	0.41	0.45	0.46	0.01
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
T_Conc_Max_Bas	1.95	2.04	1.98	2.01	2.03	2.03	1.08	2.06	1.02	1.94	1.98	1.04	1.98	1.46	1.02	2.13	1.99	2.11	2.09	2.06
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	82.80	1.39	2.22	31.34	27.47	73.29	28.85	78.63	40.17	98.29	10.14	21.30	54.68	13.60	96.75	29.85	87.01	11.62	72.67	67.00
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	3.61	3.96	4.50	5.16	4.02	6.35	5.34	2.72	0.27	2.81	2.58	6.67	2.64	1.06	0.97	5.75	6.09	4.30	2.23	6.65
Sat_Wilt	0.57	0.06	0.01	0.21	0.14	0.07	0.62	0.36	0.52	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.00	0.60	0.12	0.24	0.24
Alpha	3.61	5.49	5.41	7.62	8.84	0.11	5.09	1.23	4.41	0.07	4.95	2.16	1.59	0.05	7.02	6.27	0.46	0.06	0.07	5.99
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.99	0.45	0.04	0.11	0.03	0.12	0.97	0.20	0.00	0.24	0.27	0.30	0.01	0.73	0.01	0.74	0.00	0.83	0.14	0.00
Thickness_Topsoil	0.27	0.27	0.14	0.27	0.26	0.30	0.27	0.28	0.28	0.31	0.24	0.29	0.24	0.10	0.27	0.24	0.28	0.25	0.24	0.30
Melt_For_Corr	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01
Glac_Storage_Effect	0.58	0.79	0.68	0.75	0.74	0.76	0.55	0.73	0.57	0.72	0.66	0.60	0.77	0.59	0.58	0.68	0.74	0.76	0.78	0.75

Table 36: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Sitter catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	-0.47	-0.45	-0.40	-0.41	-0.43	-0.39	-0.43	-0.44	-1.29	-0.44	-0.41	-0.47	-0.46	-0.42	-0.45	-0.44	-0.47	-0.47	-0.39	-0.43
Melt_Fact	1.02	1.02	1.01	1.03	1.01	1.00	1.04	1.03	1.02	1.00	1.02	1.05	1.05	1.01	1.04	1.01	1.02	1.01	1.06	1.01
Refreeze_Fact	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.17	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
Snow_SWI	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Porosity	0.60	0.32	0.10	0.49	0.10	0.15	0.22	0.56	0.10	0.58	0.11	0.42	0.56	0.48	0.32	0.10	0.52	0.60	0.59	0.60
Field_Cap	0.99	0.99	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.97	1.00	0.99	0.91	0.99	0.98	0.99	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.93	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Beta	0.02	0.05	0.07	0.03	0.09	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	16.58	17.95	768.81	18.45	824.44	18.59	18.11	15.19	11.55	17.98	934.64	17.90	13.54	10.44	16.62	20.09	9.98	18.56	16.97	17.40
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.57	0.52	0.44	0.49	0.02	0.58	0.30	0.59	0.53	0.23	0.23	0.39	0.58	0.08	0.55	0.47	0.34	0.41	0.31	0.59
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.13	0.14	0.22	0.14	0.22	0.15	0.16	0.13	0.08	0.15	0.21	0.15	0.11	0.13	0.14	0.17	0.10	0.15	0.15	0.14
T_Conc_Max_Bas	1.27	1.13	1.01	1.13	1.02	1.06	1.11	1.38	1.59	1.10	1.02	1.17	1.53	1.32	1.22	1.00	1.31	1.07	1.16	1.24
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	94.46	8.25	62.30	33.44	88.10	99.44	38.16	63.59	18.72	90.04	1.41	39.20	10.78	42.71	68.12	96.20	55.34	88.55	52.98	37.94
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	3.66	3.90	3.61	6.56	3.16	0.80	0.55	6.70	1.19	1.88	0.28	3.77	1.65	2.75	5.89	0.46	6.89	0.89	6.25	6.17
Sat_Wilt	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.59	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.03	0.06	0.02	0.00	0.00
Alpha	1.11	8.11	6.31	5.32	2.52	7.22	8.76	5.62	0.13	6.37	5.06	8.69	3.14	0.64	0.20	4.98	0.19	4.54	0.37	4.37
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.30	0.04	0.26	0.25	0.14	0.00	0.03	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.37	0.30	0.16	0.28	0.99	0.11	0.50	0.45	0.51
Thickness_Topsoil	0.12	0.13	0.99	0.10	1.04	0.19	0.11	0.10	0.13	0.10	1.16	0.17	0.10	0.12	0.15	0.83	0.13	0.13	0.10	0.11
Melt_For_Corr	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.74	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01
Glac_Storage_Effect	0.92	1.25	0.97	0.92	0.99	1.77	0.98	0.82	1.81	0.83	0.97	0.80	1.09	1.04	0.98	0.36	0.82	1.07	1.07	1.04

Table 37: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Thur catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	0.21	0.15	0.10	0.19	0.18	0.61	0.31	0.22	0.61	0.15	0.26	0.25	0.24	0.59	0.13	0.15	0.19	0.15	0.62	0.58
Melt_Fact	1.03	1.18	1.82	1.02	1.04	1.09	1.01	1.00	1.00	1.17	1.10	1.11	1.03	1.00	1.01	1.34	1.07	1.10	1.02	1.00
Refreeze_Fact	0.02	2.86	2.86	0.00	2.42	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	3.10	0.07	3.00	0.01	0.03	2.54	0.65	0.33	1.20	0.01	0.00
Snow_SWI	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Porosity	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.18	0.25	0.42	0.16	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.13	0.10	0.15	0.46	0.34	0.23	0.10	0.16	0.10
Field_Cap	1.00	1.00	0.51	0.94	1.00	0.77	1.00	1.00	0.70	1.00	0.97	1.00	0.99	0.77	1.00	0.99	0.71	1.00	0.30	0.99
Beta	0.19	0.16	0.03	0.13	0.11	0.05	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.11	0.13	0.10	0.15	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.12	0.05	0.13
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	945.65	13.97	7.13	947.11	13.95	14.33	14.20	15.01	871.29	11.92	17.00	12.61	838.45	896.10	12.79	8.22	11.16	12.34	546.67	19.39
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.05	0.39	0.39	0.23	0.53	0.48	0.59	0.57	0.20	0.59	0.57	0.55	0.22	0.54	0.59	0.40	0.53	0.60	0.02	0.58
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.13	0.10	0.05	0.13	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.11	0.09	0.12	0.08	0.12	0.11	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.10	0.11	0.11
T_Conc_Max_Bas	1.44	2.61	2.94	1.46	2.62	2.66	2.59	2.43	1.12	2.46	2.26	2.82	1.38	1.14	2.73	2.88	2.50	2.58	1.19	2.08
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	70.72	43.85	43.16	13.77	26.11	65.51	13.06	80.24	8.91	29.85	44.61	77.22	73.32	45.45	38.64	86.14	35.16	69.29	0.70	61.19
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	0.51	4.38	1.14	3.65	5.67	0.92	2.22	2.29	1.64	3.13	4.41	4.65	0.63	6.69	1.72	5.59	4.43	4.23	4.35	0.02
Sat_Wilt	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.01	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.56	0.00	0.00	0.32	0.00	0.11	0.01
Alpha	2.66	7.65	0.05	2.29	2.13	5.57	2.05	8.14	6.90	3.75	2.87	5.29	6.50	0.60	2.17	0.11	8.95	1.72	1.55	3.27
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01
Thickness_Topsoil	0.99	0.94	0.15	0.88	0.28	0.21	0.11	0.27	0.97	0.40	0.71	0.28	0.97	1.01	0.10	0.13	0.33	0.59	1.04	0.91
Melt_For_Corr	0.04	0.39	0.31	0.01	0.44	0.60	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.25	0.02	0.65	0.01	0.01	0.36	0.34	0.28	0.35	0.02	0.34
Glac_Storage_Effect	0.98	1.25	1.32	0.83	1.36	1.32	0.96	1.57	0.98	1.76	1.40	0.85	0.95	0.89	1.55	1.25	1.21	1.90	0.92	1.18

Table 38: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Ticino catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	-2.23	-2.58	-2.60	-2.25	-2.27	-2.25	-1.92	-2.30	-2.61	-2.61	-2.30	-2.25	-2.24	-2.23	-2.30	-2.25	-2.38	-1.98	-2.37	-2.33
Melt_Fact	10.00	1.36	1.36	1.42	1.25	9.95	1.82	8.97	1.33	1.38	1.24	8.32	1.61	9.96	1.43	9.50	1.22	2.18	1.40	1.57
Refreeze_Fact	0.06	0.24	0.24	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.03	0.08	0.24	0.21	0.03	0.07	0.03	0.07	0.03	0.06	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.03
Snow_SWI	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Porosity	0.29	0.26	0.39	0.42	0.34	0.46	0.10	0.32	0.34	0.39	0.44	0.24	0.44	0.35	0.42	0.38	0.11	0.22	0.45	0.36
Field_Cap	1.00	1.00	0.96	0.98	0.97	1.00	0.97	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.96	0.99	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.97	0.89	1.00	1.00	0.99
Beta	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	37.84	862.94	131.88	38.41	40.10	41.04	38.37	36.67	39.89	902.69	40.31	15.54	666.30	37.21	899.74	38.84	39.20	850.19	991.77	29.85
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.56	0.40	0.52	0.55	0.60	0.60	0.49	0.58	0.27	0.42	0.58	0.11	0.57	0.33	0.08	0.56	0.57	0.40	0.56	0.29
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
T_Conc_Max_Bas	1.68	1.00	1.01	1.57	1.54	2.51	2.66	2.57	1.50	1.00	1.55	1.77	1.02	2.58	1.03	2.55	2.52	1.04	1.01	1.75
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	38.66	1.31	9.65	11.09	91.81	73.75	33.30	73.54	73.12	23.36	40.84	83.24	87.29	69.67	45.47	42.40	6.57	5.08	42.61	27.30
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	0.78	5.25	5.43	2.74	4.95	0.85	2.47	2.97	6.11	0.80	1.70	2.40	2.25	2.22	0.21	5.04	1.90	5.38	2.98	2.17
Sat_Wilt	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00
Alpha	0.12	2.07	2.86	8.51	2.19	0.58	1.72	6.27	7.94	3.44	2.24	0.09	0.34	2.01	5.95	5.32	5.87	4.73	6.43	0.12
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.01
Thickness_Topsoil	0.14	0.15	0.12	0.11	0.13	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.10	0.12	0.14	0.10	0.18	0.12	0.16	0.14	0.16	0.15	0.12
Melt_For_Corr	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01
Glac_Storage_Effect	0.54	0.86	0.91	0.66	0.79	0.91	1.34	1.43	0.64	0.96	0.74	1.03	0.97	1.11	0.81	0.98	1.64	1.03	0.65	0.73

Table 39: Optimal parameter sets for HBV generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Venoge catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
RainSnow_Temp	2.23	2.21	2.28	2.33	2.25	2.16	2.34	2.28	2.18	2.97	2.17	2.31	2.20	2.40	2.23	2.25	2.32	2.27	1.46	2.27
Melt_Fact	1.05	1.10	1.00	1.10	1.06	1.08	1.04	1.00	1.01	1.12	2.62	1.08	1.03	1.07	1.03	1.01	1.32	1.07	1.07	1.00
Refreeze_Fact	0.34	1.11	0.52	3.10	0.36	1.33	1.07	3.25	0.28	3.32	0.52	0.03	0.92	3.37	0.42	0.27	1.80	0.02	0.02	0.33
Snow_SWI	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.06
Porosity	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
Field_Cap	1.00	0.88	1.00	1.00	0.76	0.99	1.00	1.00	0.53	1.00	0.64	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.73	0.87	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00
Beta	0.27	0.16	0.39	0.30	0.22	0.24	0.44	0.38	0.13	0.63	0.13	0.48	0.38	0.41	0.15	0.10	0.46	0.27	0.09	0.39
Max_Perc_Rate_Fast_Res	13.48	12.41	22.41	14.00	916.33	13.19	15.57	20.91	756.57	737.88	14.21	485.94	940.84	843.96	998.13	608.35	22.50	13.76	5.65	512.54
BaseFlow_Coeff_Fast_Res	0.60	0.57	0.26	0.54	0.54	0.44	0.57	0.32	0.23	0.47	0.58	0.53	0.33	0.14	0.11	0.51	0.05	0.59	0.04	0.22
BaseFlow_Coeff_Slow_Res	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.04
T_Conc_Max_Bas	2.94	2.82	1.21	2.75	1.04	2.92	2.22	1.04	1.01	1.18	2.97	1.14	1.01	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.41	2.92	2.43	1.02
Prec_Lapse_PCALT	17.47	14.90	96.52	63.26	32.64	89.25	56.35	40.58	6.40	55.92	76.22	78.50	83.27	56.42	84.14	72.02	11.23	19.91	1.70	14.48
Adiab_Lapse_TCALT	5.11	5.52	0.72	0.36	0.10	1.38	0.36	1.40	2.21	6.84	6.67	0.30	3.84	4.76	1.29	5.80	1.07	5.66	5.07	0.72
Sat_Wilt	0.01	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.24	0.02	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.70	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00
Alpha	2.07	0.08	1.48	3.95	4.44	6.41	7.86	7.53	4.17	8.78	2.93	6.74	6.84	4.67	3.92	7.46	3.77	4.53	0.45	1.19
Max_Cap_Rise_Rate	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.79	0.01
Thickness_Topsoil	0.69	0.84	1.28	0.93	1.39	0.73	1.07	1.34	1.87	1.81	0.95	1.29	1.26	1.17	1.67	2.00	1.22	0.77	0.65	1.32
Melt_For_Corr	0.07	0.43	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.07	0.02	0.05	0.01	0.04	0.95	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.04
Glac_Storage_Effect	0.29	0.17	1.72	1.07	1.96	1.59	1.90	0.87	0.55	1.85	0.23	1.42	1.78	0.96	0.47	0.63	0.43	1.98	1.56	1.69

B.3 HMETS

Table 40: Optimal parameter sets for HMETS generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Broye catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	5.41	6.75	5.63	7.84	6.95	1.58	5.13	5.82	8.81	8.81	6.82	4.74	1.45	4.29	7.69	5.01	5.98	7.13	6.59	5.89
beta1	2.93	3.48	2.96	4.51	3.58	0.73	2.81	3.09	4.81	4.99	3.55	2.46	0.69	2.15	4.45	2.36	3.08	3.61	3.48	3.04
alpha2	4.12	4.86	5.49	6.37	4.04	5.15	5.55	6.77	5.25	6.48	6.66	6.30	4.56	4.17	3.46	10.34	7.97	4.48	7.95	7.81
beta2	0.34	0.53	0.61	0.68	0.43	0.33	0.47	0.75	0.60	0.77	0.74	0.71	0.32	0.43	0.30	1.14	0.92	0.48	0.92	0.89
ddf_min	1.64	1.52	1.89	1.69	1.50	1.55	1.88	2.17	1.51	1.99	2.34	1.93	2.33	1.73	1.65	1.74	1.89	1.95	1.77	1.73
ddf_plus	1.31	14.79	0.79	1.71	1.47	8.65	8.00	18.11	2.16	7.04	3.44	2.00	10.70	6.52	11.81	0.09	14.17	16.04	7.27	2.48
T_bm	-0.73	-0.73	-0.76	-0.64	-0.63	-0.31	-0.40	-0.33	-0.65	-0.24	-0.35	-0.66	-0.36	-0.31	-0.48	-0.83	-0.50	-0.53	-0.62	-0.52
K_cum	0.03	0.02	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.18	0.12	0.04	0.03	0.18	0.06	0.01	0.05	0.10	0.05	0.12	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.04
fc_min	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.10	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.07	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
fc_plus	0.19	0.02	0.07	0.20	0.01	0.20	0.02	0.15	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.20	0.05	0.20	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
C_cum	0.01	0.10	0.04	0.03	0.10	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.08	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.10
T_bf	-3.82	-4.07	-0.09	-3.46	-2.33	-1.29	0.22	-2.09	-3.78	-4.93	-3.98	1.02	-1.35	-1.27	-1.59	-4.10	-1.05	-4.06	-0.75	-3.98
K_f	3.94	4.30	1.36	1.86	0.17	1.30	3.28	2.98	0.98	3.60	3.95	1.00	1.87	0.68	3.60	4.71	0.00	3.00	4.89	1.55
F_e	0.08	0.80	0.00	0.82	0.47	0.82	0.39	0.99	0.23	0.65	0.04	0.14	0.47	0.98	0.05	0.67	0.94	0.97	0.19	0.92
ET_eff	2.07	1.76	1.85	1.95	1.67	2.17	2.08	1.73	1.72	1.74	1.72	1.75	2.16	1.74	2.02	1.69	1.76	1.71	1.76	1.70
c_r	0.60	0.37	0.40	0.59	0.40	0.62	0.67	0.42	0.38	0.46	0.39	0.42	0.64	0.44	0.60	0.39	0.40	0.40	0.45	0.39
c_vp	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
c_va	-2.62	-2.61	-3.18	-2.00	-3.22	-3.19	-2.86	-1.51	-1.37	-3.25	-3.94	-1.56	-3.93	-3.44	-2.02	-1.51	-1.99	-1.15	-2.16	-1.19
c_p	-3.83	-2.68	-4.07	-3.00	-2.74	-2.73	-3.82	-4.56	-2.82	-2.56	-3.10	-2.49	-3.53	-4.70	-4.81	-4.65	-2.20	-2.73	-4.07	-4.68
Thick_TOP	0.03	0.07	0.08	0.03	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.02	0.06	0.03	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.09
Thick_PHREATIC	1.77	1.88	1.16	1.91	1.99	1.73	1.91	1.86	1.94	1.92	1.79	1.89	1.93	1.90	1.89	1.93	1.84	1.94	1.82	1.99

Table 41: Optimal parameter sets for HMETS generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Dischma catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	7.85	2.92	4.41	10.38	17.75	12.63	2.66	1.23	9.14	2.54	3.52	12.10	14.68	4.36	6.37	17.37	2.39	4.41	14.86	17.22
beta1	0.24	0.08	0.14	0.34	0.51	0.41	0.18	0.08	0.30	0.22	0.23	0.37	0.44	0.38	0.19	0.50	0.20	0.15	0.45	0.51
alpha2	4.61	4.16	6.66	4.08	3.53	3.65	11.49	12.48	4.34	12.26	12.88	2.28	4.33	9.95	5.45	2.71	12.01	3.96	6.18	4.28
beta2	0.77	0.95	1.28	0.62	0.43	0.53	0.21	0.23	0.68	0.27	0.25	0.32	0.64	0.19	0.89	0.33	0.23	0.88	0.94	0.63
ddf_min	1.55	1.99	1.79	2.32	1.57	2.02	2.30	2.58	2.07	2.22	2.22	2.33	2.54	2.06	1.57	1.73	2.44	1.69	1.79	2.61
ddf_plus	1.60	0.07	0.84	0.33	0.86	0.19	0.29	0.46	0.03	0.06	0.26	0.90	0.18	0.28	1.03	0.32	0.05	0.86	0.25	0.48
T_bm	-0.56	-0.96	-0.97	-0.91	-0.93	-0.96	-0.92	-0.64	-0.90	-1.00	-0.96	-0.46	-0.80	-0.99	-0.88	-0.98	-0.98	-0.98	-0.98	-0.69
K_cum	0.18	0.14	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.17	0.11	0.17	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.16	0.06	0.17	0.17	0.19	0.12	0.20	0.03	0.09
fc_min	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
fc_plus	0.18	0.01	0.01	0.07	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.18	0.02	0.01	0.06	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.18
C_cum	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.10	0.06	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.05	0.07	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.08	0.08	0.08
T_bf	-3.07	-2.14	-2.12	0.30	-4.64	-4.99	-1.20	-3.85	-3.73	-4.73	-2.19	-2.76	-4.98	-3.55	-2.52	-4.83	-3.24	1.53	-3.13	-4.63
K_f	4.77	0.09	4.96	0.00	0.09	4.49	0.10	0.03	1.18	0.47	0.03	0.25	3.55	0.12	0.41	3.11	4.45	3.27	0.10	3.43
F_e	0.94	0.76	0.97	0.67	0.41	0.83	0.93	0.37	0.10	0.45	0.04	0.27	0.06	0.04	0.52	0.01	0.24	0.56	0.34	0.50
ET_eff	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
c_r	0.60	0.62	0.62	0.59	0.52	0.57	0.61	0.73	0.55	0.60	0.56	0.58	0.53	0.58	0.54	0.50	0.61	0.65	0.51	0.60
c_vp	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.02
c_va	-3.30	-3.57	-2.01	-2.70	-3.75	-3.95	-2.85	-3.78	-3.84	-1.71	-4.19	-3.72	-4.79	-3.79	-2.96	-4.05	-2.91	-1.57	-3.16	-4.35
c_p	-3.18	-2.98	-3.53	-2.89	-4.93	-2.75	-5.00	-2.77	-4.20	-2.14	-2.69	-2.69	-2.29	-4.57	-3.49	-4.52	-3.49	-4.51	-4.83	-3.94
Thick_TOP	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02
Thick_PHREATIC	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.79	0.00	0.02

Table 42: Optimal parameter sets for HMETS generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Lonza catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	3.97	0.89	2.49	6.81	3.92	1.42	0.59	3.60	16.43	8.93	12.56	7.50	19.80	16.44	15.90	8.54	12.84	4.32	8.72	14.38
beta1	0.34	0.02	0.28	0.18	0.13	0.01	0.03	0.10	0.48	0.23	0.39	0.21	0.50	0.45	0.43	0.30	0.37	0.38	0.20	0.42
alpha2	11.03	0.64	11.99	3.95	5.45	4.80	11.35	4.76	7.25	5.15	6.42	3.38	3.96	6.27	3.79	2.51	1.74	9.78	5.22	6.24
beta2	0.19	0.46	0.33	0.57	1.05	0.96	0.19	0.92	1.19	0.84	1.00	0.56	0.54	0.96	0.52	0.43	0.29	0.16	0.77	0.99
ddf_min	1.91	1.77	1.63	1.55	1.67	1.82	1.63	1.91	1.51	1.84	1.85	1.81	2.14	1.56	1.73	1.69	1.83	2.06	2.36	1.55
ddf_plus	0.06	0.25	0.27	0.61	0.29	0.15	0.54	0.23	0.36	0.27	0.12	0.28	0.08	0.48	0.21	0.12	0.16	0.12	0.34	0.36
T_bm	-0.97	-0.95	-0.96	-0.90	-0.97	-0.95	-0.96	-0.99	-0.99	-0.98	-0.93	-1.00	-1.00	-0.94	-0.95	-0.97	-0.98	-0.96	-0.72	-0.99
K_cum	0.06	0.11	0.05	0.10	0.12	0.13	0.02	0.03	0.16	0.18	0.07	0.04	0.01	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.01	0.18	0.17	0.18
fc_min	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
fc_plus	0.08	0.01	0.19	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.20	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.18	0.13	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.01
C_cum	0.10	0.10	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.07	0.06	0.09	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.06	0.10	0.10	0.09	0.07
T_bf	-3.25	1.43	-4.61	0.07	-4.96	-1.15	-2.93	-0.30	-5.00	-4.18	-4.87	1.56	0.24	-4.44	-4.80	1.94	-4.93	1.98	-4.18	-3.77
K_f	3.30	3.96	2.18	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.27	0.49	1.30	0.67	4.38	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.02	4.98	1.76	0.44
F_e	0.29	0.06	0.20	0.58	0.31	0.28	0.50	0.44	0.47	0.65	0.52	0.80	0.76	0.35	0.11	0.02	0.83	0.03	0.84	0.21
ET_eff	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
c_r	0.47	0.74	0.52	0.45	0.48	0.52	0.64	0.53	0.46	0.47	0.47	0.50	0.46	0.43	0.45	0.49	0.50	0.43	0.45	0.46
c_vp	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
c_va	-4.15	-4.61	-1.14	-1.44	-2.45	-4.49	-1.63	-3.52	-3.05	-3.00	-4.67	-3.95	-1.83	-3.12	-3.38	-2.57	-4.34	-1.76	-4.44	-3.38
c_p	-4.88	-3.59	-3.18	-4.75	-3.20	-2.69	-4.86	-4.29	-2.46	-4.79	-2.25	-4.40	-2.05	-3.03	-3.38	-2.24	-4.24	-4.84	-3.54	-4.82
Thick_TOP	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
Thick_PHREATIC	1.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.41	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.92	1.84	0.00	1.79	1.64

Table 43: Optimal parameter sets for HMETS generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Lütschine catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	8.15	11.14	13.38	11.93	2.97	7.28	6.40	1.82	8.11	9.30	12.85	2.88	2.03	8.13	17.42	2.92	3.37	3.32	2.25	2.50
beta1	0.23	0.39	0.41	0.42	0.28	0.25	0.17	0.12	0.26	0.29	0.41	0.24	0.16	0.26	0.49	0.08	0.08	0.11	0.15	0.05
alpha2	4.62	4.12	3.62	4.99	7.95	3.36	2.72	9.72	3.59	3.72	4.67	11.25	10.15	3.95	3.87	2.39	3.33	2.02	12.48	2.54
beta2	0.56	0.71	0.54	0.78	0.15	0.56	0.32	0.15	0.56	0.59	0.80	0.24	0.24	0.60	0.47	0.49	0.63	0.43	0.22	0.52
ddf_min	1.60	2.19	1.56	1.58	1.63	1.58	1.50	1.51	1.62	2.65	1.52	2.21	2.26	1.54	1.53	1.62	1.66	1.99	1.51	1.65
ddf_plus	19.82	0.12	1.88	0.75	0.67	0.64	19.89	8.63	1.62	0.78	1.00	0.13	2.42	1.09	2.15	19.96	3.18	0.27	7.54	1.48
T_bm	-0.40	-0.99	-0.94	-0.97	-0.98	-1.00	-0.39	-0.67	-0.94	-0.96	-0.99	-1.00	-0.91	-0.95	-0.98	-0.29	-0.86	-0.99	-0.76	-0.98
K_cum	0.01	0.11	0.01	0.02	0.15	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.10	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
fc_min	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.02
fc_plus	0.01	0.07	0.15	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.15	0.02	0.12	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.15	0.01	0.13	0.07
C_cum	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.10	0.06	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.10	0.04	0.08	0.07	0.01	0.08	0.04	0.10	0.07	0.07
T_bf	-0.87	-3.07	1.23	-4.93	-0.20	-2.33	-1.98	-0.71	-2.35	-0.57	-0.47	-4.92	1.15	-4.30	-0.80	-0.16	-0.24	-4.59	0.65	-2.05
K_f	0.52	0.86	0.41	2.14	0.23	0.68	0.63	3.04	1.92	1.99	0.42	2.72	2.11	2.22	0.98	0.37	2.02	2.49	2.97	1.82
F_e	0.48	0.70	0.83	0.05	1.00	0.52	0.30	0.16	0.15	0.12	0.73	0.01	0.31	0.28	0.72	0.02	0.26	0.17	0.34	0.13
ET_eff	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00
c_r	0.53	0.52	0.50	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.54	0.52	0.48	0.49	0.48	0.50	0.50	0.49	0.63	0.56	0.56	0.56	0.57
c_vp	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.02
c_va	-3.29	-3.10	-4.91	-1.19	-3.43	-4.50	-3.55	-3.81	-2.79	-2.19	-2.23	-4.92	-2.63	-1.76	-4.18	-1.51	-3.88	-1.80	-1.73	-2.18
c_p	-3.70	-4.96	-4.90	-2.78	-2.88	-2.66	-4.61	-3.84	-4.00	-3.62	-3.70	-4.86	-2.82	-4.67	-2.14	-2.76	-2.69	-2.03	-4.03	-3.40
Thick_TOP	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
Thick_PHREATIC	0.01	0.01	0.89	0.00	0.02	0.98	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.88	0.01	1.37	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.07	0.02

Table 44: Optimal parameter sets for HMETS generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Massa catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	11.39	3.85	3.79	10.19	18.35	9.32	10.19	2.91	9.82	8.44	3.61	14.85	6.39	10.97	14.08	10.15	6.40	14.23	13.13	2.16
beta1	0.60	0.27	0.20	0.27	0.83	0.66	0.36	0.07	0.38	0.32	0.25	0.44	0.49	0.69	1.12	0.35	0.47	0.48	1.30	0.11
alpha2	9.70	9.92	7.86	9.34	6.31	12.37	1.08	2.18	5.13	4.79	9.69	3.40	8.69	12.74	9.09	3.39	8.24	6.21	12.66	0.75
beta2	0.17	0.24	0.25	0.77	1.25	0.36	0.25	0.42	0.77	1.09	0.23	0.36	0.22	0.27	0.23	0.46	0.21	0.61	0.52	0.64
ddf_min	2.04	2.92	2.25	2.07	2.79	2.68	1.62	2.24	2.85	2.38	2.47	2.77	2.75	1.62	1.74	2.77	2.82	2.89	2.09	1.99
ddf_plus	19.25	7.54	6.52	6.20	8.36	6.94	18.78	17.91	10.54	4.07	5.63	4.26	15.79	16.14	16.25	7.63	2.79	10.19	10.18	4.77
T_bm	-0.58	-0.96	-0.98	-0.96	-0.64	-0.83	-0.51	-0.55	-0.60	-0.89	-0.98	-1.00	-0.49	-0.58	-0.61	-0.83	-1.00	-0.57	-0.77	-0.96
K_cum	0.01	0.10	0.01	0.06	0.17	0.17	0.01	0.01	0.20	0.18	0.02	0.06	0.10	0.02	0.11	0.02	0.13	0.06	0.12	0.19
fc_min	0.07	0.09	0.04	0.10	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.08	0.10	0.05	0.08	0.10	0.07	0.09	0.07	0.07	0.04	0.06	0.07	0.07
fc_plus	0.10	0.16	0.06	0.18	0.17	0.07	0.02	0.05	0.08	0.10	0.09	0.06	0.10	0.15	0.04	0.14	0.13	0.11	0.01	0.13
C_cum	0.10	0.07	0.03	0.10	0.07	0.06	0.03	0.01	0.08	0.03	0.08	0.04	0.05	0.09	0.02	0.10	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.09
T_bf	-1.61	-0.41	-2.01	-2.52	-2.82	-2.23	-3.79	-1.81	-2.52	-2.73	-2.53	-2.27	-1.24	-1.27	0.22	-2.42	-4.33	-2.89	-0.95	-3.50
K_f	3.41	3.53	4.32	4.07	3.89	4.98	4.40	4.14	3.84	1.65	4.16	4.05	4.35	2.96	3.95	4.97	3.92	4.47	3.44	4.66
F_e	0.92	0.71	0.99	0.83	0.78	0.44	0.77	0.88	0.89	0.78	0.87	0.32	0.55	0.86	0.64	0.93	0.73	0.94	0.78	0.40
ET_eff	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.01
c_r	0.49	0.57	0.48	0.44	0.60	0.46	0.70	0.60	0.54	0.67	0.46	0.46	0.44	0.41	0.36	0.53	0.46	0.48	0.42	0.78
c_vp	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.01
c_va	-3.09	-4.87	-1.17	-1.80	-4.94	-4.55	-2.15	-2.36	-3.84	-1.28	-4.72	-3.68	-3.57	-3.75	-1.01	-1.64	-4.98	-3.75	-3.34	-3.58
c_p	-4.28	-3.65	-2.56	-2.89	-3.79	-3.68	-3.93	-3.72	-4.77	-2.60	-4.39	-3.47	-4.56	-3.80	-4.04	-4.15	-4.62	-2.90	-2.84	-4.09
Thick_TOP	0.07	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.08	0.06	0.37	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.18	0.22	0.09	0.08	0.01	0.12	0.01
Thick_PHREATIC	0.02	1.08	0.05	0.01	0.06	0.02	0.00	0.05	1.53	0.03	0.20	0.00	1.10	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.00	0.01

Table 45: Optimal parameter sets for HMETS generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Rhône catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	3.25	14.75	6.34	2.90	10.31	11.84	6.54	7.99	2.29	15.69	10.58	13.02	4.30	1.47	0.77	3.02	17.31	14.49	8.39	7.12
beta1	0.66	0.69	1.15	0.75	2.81	3.26	1.66	1.71	0.01	0.46	0.31	0.39	0.44	0.16	0.04	0.52	0.59	0.50	1.30	1.02
alpha2	4.77	5.58	9.71	11.82	11.42	6.47	9.72	12.69	2.02	2.96	2.27	4.58	10.55	11.37	1.55	7.32	4.74	7.26	12.95	10.99
beta2	0.19	1.24	0.32	0.44	0.44	0.27	0.39	0.46	0.22	0.34	0.32	0.68	0.28	0.41	1.14	0.26	0.73	1.13	0.51	0.34
ddf_min	1.63	2.01	1.89	2.10	1.95	1.78	1.95	2.25	2.91	1.92	1.63	1.98	2.28	2.21	2.53	2.35	1.62	1.91	1.54	1.86
ddf_plus	0.74	0.49	0.54	0.20	0.30	0.63	0.30	0.28	0.43	0.98	1.47	0.90	0.68	0.26	0.03	0.15	1.17	0.49	0.96	0.31
T_bm	-0.91	-0.98	-0.76	-0.95	-0.94	-0.88	-0.90	-0.53	-0.86	-0.89	-0.94	-0.92	0.03	-0.87	-0.84	-0.91	-0.99	-0.89	-0.62	-0.81
K_cum	0.19	0.06	0.18	0.20	0.08	0.10	0.19	0.09	0.08	0.15	0.19	0.15	0.08	0.15	0.15	0.17	0.09	0.20	0.13	0.18
fc_min	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
fc_plus	0.18	0.19	0.02	0.04	0.18	0.10	0.04	0.01	0.14	0.11	0.15	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.01	0.18	0.01	0.04	0.20	0.02
C_cum	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.07	0.07	0.09	0.09	0.10	0.08	0.07	0.09
T_bf	1.31	1.49	-4.82	-4.58	-4.90	1.74	-4.65	-0.58	-4.44	-2.16	-4.15	-2.27	-2.79	-4.20	1.09	-4.95	-4.97	-4.52	-3.22	-4.73
K_f	3.29	3.63	0.37	1.02	0.12	4.77	4.65	4.83	2.94	0.01	3.23	0.19	4.38	0.72	2.95	0.01	1.41	1.18	1.15	3.60
F_e	0.55	0.89	0.40	0.68	0.36	0.63	0.67	0.22	0.37	0.42	0.80	0.91	0.55	0.90	0.95	0.12	0.61	0.30	0.44	0.34
ET_eff	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01
c_r	0.35	0.43	0.34	0.38	0.37	0.49	0.34	0.40	0.47	0.40	0.45	0.42	0.31	0.34	0.75	0.52	0.42	0.27	0.38	0.32
c_vp	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00
c_va	-2.34	-2.35	-4.77	-3.81	-1.50	-2.65	-2.25	-1.82	-4.55	-4.64	-2.01	-2.46	-1.71	-1.49	-2.72	-1.67	-4.66	-1.26	-4.31	-1.85
c_p	-3.70	-3.31	-3.65	-2.96	-3.02	-4.55	-3.51	-3.95	-3.42	-3.94	-4.00	-3.28	-3.43	-3.32	-4.07	-4.98	-2.13	-4.21	-3.41	-2.89
Thick_TOP	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00
Thick_PHREATIC	1.60	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.06	0.00	1.80	0.01	0.00	1.23	0.00	1.74	0.02	0.00	0.66	0.95	0.00	1.94	0.01	1.86

Table 46: Optimal parameter sets for HMETs generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Saltina catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	18.99	4.09	7.70	14.56	15.53	16.86	6.04	12.69	6.02	9.47	10.21	3.49	1.39	5.36	12.70	18.59	8.68	1.80	12.23	15.05
beta1	0.52	0.11	0.22	0.44	0.43	0.49	0.16	0.36	0.19	0.28	0.30	0.10	0.02	0.19	0.34	0.53	0.28	0.04	0.39	0.44
alpha2	0.84	0.86	1.32	0.98	1.00	0.92	1.11	1.04	1.33	1.15	0.89	1.04	0.92	1.28	0.83	0.83	1.30	1.27	0.85	0.89
beta2	0.18	0.30	0.35	0.24	0.23	0.20	0.33	0.25	0.40	0.25	0.22	0.44	0.52	0.45	0.21	0.18	0.38	0.95	0.21	0.18
ddf_min	1.50	1.62	1.50	1.61	1.55	1.55	1.54	1.55	1.51	1.51	1.51	1.55	1.55	1.50	1.58	1.55	1.53	1.53	1.52	1.50
ddf_plus	0.18	0.01	0.29	0.04	0.15	0.03	0.10	0.12	0.00	9.51	0.06	0.08	0.01	0.03	0.10	0.08	0.24	0.04	0.11	0.01
T_bm	0.78	0.82	0.78	0.92	0.75	0.78	0.79	0.61	0.37	0.99	1.00	0.71	0.66	0.50	0.66	0.68	0.64	0.96	0.91	0.74
K_cum	0.05	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.12	0.06	0.10	0.05	0.01	0.17	0.01	0.16	0.13	0.09	0.18	0.16	0.14	0.02	0.12
fc_min	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
fc_plus	0.17	0.15	0.03	0.05	0.18	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.11	0.05	0.20	0.19	0.15	0.16	0.18	0.02	0.02	0.10
C_cum	0.08	0.08	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.09	0.08	0.04	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.06	0.03
T_bf	-2.77	-2.79	-1.17	-3.93	0.91	-1.55	-2.58	-2.02	-3.16	-3.95	-3.96	-4.82	-4.71	-2.22	-3.99	-4.79	-0.69	-4.81	-0.04	-4.70
K_f	2.09	1.23	0.69	2.81	0.26	0.05	4.74	3.05	2.16	2.92	4.62	0.72	2.78	1.84	3.86	3.71	0.76	4.25	0.05	2.19
F_e	0.44	0.07	0.32	0.58	0.52	0.26	0.64	0.25	0.38	0.13	0.74	0.12	0.95	0.27	0.40	0.29	0.77	0.52	0.16	0.26
ET_eff	0.50	0.52	0.46	0.49	0.53	0.38	0.46	0.51	0.54	0.50	0.37	0.46	0.31	0.42	0.50	0.54	0.34	0.31	0.52	0.47
c_r	0.62	0.69	0.80	0.70	0.67	0.64	0.62	0.69	0.67	0.82	0.70	0.76	0.68	0.72	0.61	0.68	0.83	0.67	0.69	0.59
c_vp	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02
c_va	-2.53	-3.26	-1.41	-2.71	-1.15	-1.97	-4.65	-4.95	-1.19	-2.68	-3.48	-2.18	-1.52	-1.98	-1.16	-4.37	-4.21	-4.86	-3.93	-1.55
c_p	-4.60	-2.11	-4.16	-4.50	-3.08	-4.04	-3.50	-2.54	-2.01	-2.60	-4.90	-4.66	-3.39	-4.11	-3.65	-2.35	-5.00	-3.05	-4.07	-2.30
Thick_TOP	0.48	0.27	0.21	0.23	0.31	0.45	0.27	0.24	0.33	0.20	0.38	0.19	0.41	0.36	0.42	0.32	0.17	0.46	0.31	0.35
Thick_PHREATIC	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.00	1.32	0.71	0.04	0.08	0.05	0.98	0.03	1.84	0.56	0.06	0.01	1.31	2.00	0.10	0.01

Table 47: Optimal parameter sets for HMETS generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Sitter catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	1.89	1.96	2.70	2.17	1.50	5.44	3.55	4.95	2.20	1.99	3.21	2.33	1.48	3.03	2.42	4.09	5.34	1.81	2.19	4.59
beta1	1.42	1.38	1.84	1.47	0.89	4.11	2.82	3.64	1.47	1.28	2.24	1.58	0.98	2.16	1.21	2.97	4.57	1.14	1.40	3.69
alpha2	4.74	3.92	3.76	3.40	3.76	4.33	2.65	4.77	5.90	2.26	3.13	3.44	4.43	4.91	7.44	4.81	4.72	3.05	2.81	3.66
beta2	0.45	0.34	0.35	0.34	0.30	0.47	0.24	0.51	0.58	0.16	0.28	0.31	0.38	0.48	0.55	0.60	0.57	0.25	0.23	0.38
ddf_min	1.51	1.51	1.51	2.32	1.52	1.52	1.50	1.51	1.50	1.50	1.51	1.51	1.51	1.50	1.52	1.87	1.50	1.51	1.50	1.50
ddf_plus	0.04	0.04	0.10	17.86	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.00	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01	16.01	0.06	17.19	0.00	0.11
T_bm	0.60	-0.37	-0.87	-0.15	-0.98	-0.53	0.61	-0.72	-0.75	-0.97	-0.98	-0.79	-0.88	-0.60	-0.51	-0.45	0.62	-0.46	-0.99	0.74
K_cum	0.09	0.11	0.07	0.03	0.06	0.08	0.11	0.09	0.19	0.03	0.14	0.19	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.12
fc_min	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
fc_plus	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
C_cum	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
T_bf	-4.94	-3.22	0.03	-4.69	0.21	-4.59	-4.94	-3.47	-3.39	-2.52	0.46	-3.26	-2.77	-4.60	-3.50	-4.30	-4.82	-3.92	-0.07	-4.45
K_f	0.01	0.01	4.98	2.47	4.60	0.01	0.01	2.67	4.86	4.94	3.74	4.49	4.05	4.35	2.02	2.48	0.01	1.79	4.83	0.00
F_e	0.30	0.12	0.95	0.24	0.77	0.09	0.12	0.48	0.01	0.01	0.96	0.07	0.01	0.19	0.76	0.29	0.29	0.44	0.89	0.13
ET_eff	0.87	0.79	0.83	0.88	0.83	0.80	0.88	0.87	0.84	0.87	0.87	0.88	0.84	0.86	0.85	0.79	0.87	0.89	0.85	0.89
c_r	0.57	0.55	0.50	0.58	0.52	0.50	0.54	0.48	0.52	0.50	0.49	0.50	0.50	0.53	0.40	0.57	0.55	0.56	0.50	0.53
c_vp	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00
c_va	-2.57	-2.58	-4.67	-3.27	-2.33	-4.34	-4.92	-5.00	-3.22	-3.61	-3.63	-2.19	-4.68	-3.33	-4.52	-4.99	-4.82	-2.43	-3.61	-1.47
c_p	-3.38	-2.28	-3.74	-2.91	-3.35	-4.05	-4.67	-4.62	-2.29	-3.77	-2.08	-3.01	-4.92	-3.18	-3.59	-2.37	-2.31	-2.79	-2.30	-2.87
Thick_TOP	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Thick_PHREATIC	0.01	1.91	1.16	0.00	1.31	1.49	0.00	0.34	0.80	0.79	1.55	1.13	1.03	0.29	0.68	1.64	0.01	0.00	1.05	0.01

Table 48: Optimal parameter sets for HMETS generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Thur catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	8.55	7.49	8.67	6.26	6.62	7.30	6.01	6.82	3.39	8.83	5.97	8.09	7.21	2.17	5.09	6.56	7.60	7.76	9.04	8.15
beta1	4.07	3.67	4.08	3.07	2.92	3.67	2.93	3.06	1.52	4.13	2.97	3.92	3.27	0.50	2.39	3.04	3.75	3.56	4.69	3.90
alpha2	10.14	5.77	8.06	5.18	7.27	7.32	6.75	5.16	3.61	6.12	6.44	8.84	6.19	2.97	8.09	9.31	2.72	6.22	10.43	5.74
beta2	1.39	0.75	1.18	0.69	0.92	0.98	0.87	0.69	0.37	0.87	0.85	1.20	0.85	1.49	0.98	1.32	0.32	0.85	1.49	0.80
ddf_min	1.52	1.75	2.80	1.90	2.24	1.85	1.51	2.57	2.25	2.84	1.55	1.76	2.15	2.29	2.95	1.59	1.60	1.92	2.09	2.68
ddf_plus	2.42	1.86	1.31	0.30	4.38	1.58	1.64	4.60	0.75	0.15	4.63	5.19	1.41	1.60	9.41	1.71	0.60	3.57	2.82	0.61
T_bm	-0.41	-0.49	-0.31	-0.67	-0.26	-0.49	-0.51	-0.24	-0.50	-0.44	-0.33	-0.28	-0.38	-0.34	-0.13	-0.40	-0.72	-0.40	-0.30	-0.38
K_cum	0.01	0.07	0.03	0.01	0.14	0.03	0.08	0.10	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.09	0.19	0.18	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
fc_min	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.10	0.08	0.07	0.09	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.06
fc_plus	0.02	0.15	0.06	0.20	0.08	0.09	0.14	0.11	0.15	0.01	0.06	0.03	0.16	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.20	0.04	0.08	0.07
C_cum	0.05	0.01	0.09	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.04	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.05	0.09	0.09	0.04	0.06	0.01	0.02	0.07	0.06
T_bf	-3.28	-1.96	-1.03	-2.82	-2.99	-1.34	-2.80	-1.66	-3.39	-4.63	-3.26	-3.24	-3.26	-1.66	-3.64	-2.83	-2.64	-1.04	-3.21	-2.55
K_f	0.88	1.31	0.13	1.09	2.42	0.63	1.96	0.99	3.34	4.84	0.67	0.36	0.76	0.31	3.40	0.64	1.59	0.53	2.05	0.38
F_e	0.07	0.94	0.84	0.37	0.65	0.81	0.55	0.07	0.59	0.83	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.55	0.80	0.06	0.72	0.02	0.95	0.30
ET_eff	1.78	1.83	1.73	1.79	1.77	1.99	1.82	1.67	1.84	1.86	1.79	1.77	1.73	1.75	1.87	1.69	1.98	1.86	1.79	1.72
c_r	0.72	0.76	0.56	0.64	0.37	0.72	0.72	0.41	0.94	0.53	0.74	0.71	0.43	0.51	0.89	0.45	0.71	0.44	0.75	0.44
c_vp	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
c_va	-3.63	-4.00	-1.41	-4.19	-2.40	-1.20	-1.94	-1.85	-3.91	-2.92	-2.08	-1.21	-4.00	-4.00	-4.61	-2.65	-1.26	-1.22	-3.83	-1.33
c_p	-2.10	-3.13	-3.02	-3.09	-4.54	-4.40	-3.13	-3.67	-4.19	-4.44	-3.85	-4.49	-2.90	-3.22	-3.26	-4.29	-3.01	-4.74	-3.74	-4.40
Thick_TOP	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.50	0.03	0.03	0.12	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.05	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.08
Thick_PHREATIC	1.99	1.98	1.71	1.95	0.27	0.00	1.83	1.85	1.66	0.02	1.98	1.96	1.45	1.44	1.72	1.88	0.78	0.02	1.98	1.66

Table 49: Optimal parameter sets for HMETS generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Ticino catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	1.61	1.65	0.83	6.02	1.31	4.49	0.91	6.78	1.12	1.55	2.17	6.51	4.19	4.19	4.58	0.99	6.00	2.16	1.04	0.59
beta1	0.07	0.06	0.11	0.26	0.19	0.18	0.13	0.28	0.03	0.06	0.08	0.26	0.17	0.18	0.20	0.13	0.23	0.09	0.12	0.06
alpha2	1.72	2.14	8.25	2.40	7.12	1.71	9.18	2.97	2.05	1.78	1.34	3.57	2.46	2.24	1.90	10.22	2.79	2.33	9.10	5.44
beta2	0.76	1.09	0.23	0.59	0.20	0.45	0.26	0.64	0.85	0.90	0.46	0.74	0.73	0.71	0.53	0.30	0.56	0.99	0.24	0.15
ddf_min	2.30	1.56	2.97	2.44	2.22	1.58	1.51	1.87	2.62	1.67	1.96	2.33	2.44	2.17	2.80	1.63	1.82	2.02	1.89	2.55
ddf_plus	7.25	19.83	5.08	12.25	2.54	7.92	1.45	2.88	12.72	8.21	2.37	3.17	4.22	10.80	18.25	8.48	10.80	4.25	3.74	2.13
T_bm	-0.30	-0.14	-0.37	-0.24	-0.59	-0.38	-0.96	-0.82	-0.28	-0.34	-0.76	-0.58	-0.54	-0.28	-0.16	-0.34	-0.26	-0.45	-0.60	-0.74
K_cum	0.14	0.18	0.20	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.02	0.20	0.17	0.10	0.17	0.05	0.03	0.18	0.20	0.20	0.19	0.16	0.04
fc_min	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.05
fc_plus	0.04	0.12	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.09	0.08	0.03	0.06	0.18	0.03	0.17	0.18	0.08	0.08	0.11	0.14	0.01	0.02	0.02
C_cum	0.04	0.08	0.10	0.07	0.01	0.08	0.01	0.01	0.09	0.05	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.09	0.02	0.04	0.09	0.10	0.10
T_bf	-2.81	-4.83	-2.53	-2.09	-2.11	-1.72	-0.78	0.90	1.61	-2.80	-3.35	-4.10	1.04	-3.55	-2.53	-0.95	-2.67	-1.88	-2.78	-2.67
K_f	1.51	1.16	1.16	2.43	0.96	1.99	0.31	0.61	1.00	2.77	3.30	3.60	0.61	1.98	2.23	1.12	1.80	1.09	2.71	2.39
F_e	0.07	0.00	0.80	0.01	0.23	0.26	0.97	0.80	0.56	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.74	0.14	0.01	0.61	0.03	0.13	0.20	0.38
ET_eff	1.18	1.07	1.19	1.18	1.07	1.11	1.05	1.16	1.17	1.06	1.19	1.19	1.07	0.97	1.05	1.03	1.08	1.06	0.97	1.09
c_r	0.56	0.58	0.56	0.47	0.51	0.48	0.62	0.45	0.59	0.58	0.52	0.44	0.49	0.51	0.49	0.55	0.45	0.54	0.52	0.56
c_vp	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
c_va	-2.87	-1.67	-2.37	-1.43	-1.91	-3.18	-3.67	-3.92	-4.20	-3.54	-3.02	-1.33	-4.00	-3.97	-1.17	-3.33	-1.16	-3.94	-2.57	-2.46
c_p	-4.08	-3.35	-2.79	-4.60	-4.84	-4.98	-4.38	-2.27	-2.20	-4.13	-3.05	-2.83	-4.40	-4.98	-3.41	-2.36	-4.33	-3.37	-3.80	-4.43
Thick_TOP	0.49	0.49	0.47	0.50	0.28	0.49	0.23	0.48	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.41	0.48	0.44	0.43	0.44	0.19	0.50	0.40	0.44
Thick_PHREATIC	0.01	1.13	0.01	0.00	1.24	0.87	1.44	0.00	0.75	1.53	0.01	0.03	1.18	1.97	1.54	1.98	0.14	1.31	1.99	1.05

Table 50: Optimal parameter sets for HMETs generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Venoge catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699354 plus column title, e.g. 1699354089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
alpha1	7.67	5.95	9.34	6.18	2.23	2.85	2.84	1.81	1.48	2.85	4.86	4.81	6.00	2.56	3.86	5.35	3.95	5.60	1.55	3.14
beta1	2.54	1.87	3.15	1.86	0.55	0.74	0.76	0.43	0.31	0.76	1.38	1.42	1.86	0.68	1.17	1.65	1.18	1.75	0.36	0.80
alpha2	11.71	7.83	6.23	5.01	4.27	4.47	8.76	5.50	4.22	5.95	6.15	6.45	6.54	9.93	6.98	10.22	6.61	3.60	5.09	7.54
beta2	1.04	0.59	0.49	0.35	0.24	0.25	0.54	0.29	0.21	0.38	0.44	0.45	0.49	0.59	0.48	0.78	0.47	0.25	0.21	0.44
ddf_min	2.35	1.81	1.99	1.53	2.18	1.66	2.17	1.58	1.53	1.58	1.61	1.57	1.50	1.53	1.54	1.98	1.51	1.86	1.51	2.95
ddf_plus	0.94	2.51	7.48	0.14	6.88	0.44	3.55	4.70	4.38	0.08	2.51	17.61	3.57	0.09	0.25	9.99	9.27	9.52	8.87	15.89
T_bm	-0.20	-0.34	-0.13	-0.49	-0.15	-0.35	-0.15	-0.27	-0.16	-0.42	-0.44	-0.40	-0.25	-0.58	-0.39	-0.10	-0.10	-0.11	-0.23	-0.10
K_cum	0.02	0.04	0.15	0.16	0.09	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.12	0.18	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.09	0.02	0.10	0.15	0.09	0.06	0.06
fc_min	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.04	0.09	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.09	0.04	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.00
fc_plus	0.17	0.10	0.06	0.17	0.02	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.07	0.20	0.18	0.03	0.01	0.20	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.13	0.16	0.08
C_cum	0.09	0.06	0.04	0.08	0.07	0.06	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.05	0.03	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.04	0.07	0.10	0.10	0.01	0.10
T_bf	-0.04	-0.07	0.10	-0.53	0.21	-1.83	-4.88	0.35	-0.58	0.11	1.73	-1.00	-4.96	-0.84	0.24	-1.78	-4.95	-4.66	-0.16	1.97
K_f	1.67	4.16	1.76	0.76	0.84	2.62	3.67	0.27	4.91	1.17	0.93	4.92	0.45	3.37	0.16	2.63	0.90	2.03	2.67	1.04
F_e	0.90	0.68	0.34	0.08	0.00	0.42	0.92	0.00	0.79	0.99	0.01	0.63	0.04	0.01	0.30	0.89	0.95	0.90	0.43	0.11
ET_eff	1.30	1.40	1.29	1.29	1.31	1.32	1.31	1.31	1.36	1.30	1.33	1.31	1.42	1.28	1.29	1.31	1.27	1.31	1.52	1.32
c_r	0.38	0.38	0.37	0.38	0.75	0.68	0.67	0.81	0.99	0.38	0.37	0.38	0.37	0.74	0.65	0.38	0.37	0.39	0.48	0.95
c_vp	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
c_va	-4.54	-4.17	-2.60	-3.00	-1.58	-2.99	-4.47	-4.31	-4.60	-4.06	-3.21	-2.39	-3.94	-3.62	-4.93	-3.47	-4.39	-1.44	-1.28	-2.70
c_p	-4.51	-2.24	-3.91	-2.18	-2.99	-4.87	-2.22	-4.71	-4.00	-4.22	-3.48	-2.89	-3.94	-3.07	-4.28	-2.10	-2.96	-2.56	-3.57	-3.54
Thick_TOP	0.16	0.15	0.15	0.16	0.22	0.17	0.20	0.22	0.26	0.13	0.15	0.16	0.15	0.23	0.21	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.04	0.27
Thick_PHREATIC	1.98	0.07	1.99	1.96	1.96	2.00	1.77	1.98	0.92	1.99	1.09	1.87	0.37	1.81	1.95	1.97	2.00	1.81	1.99	1.98

B.4 HYMOD

Table 51: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Broye catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K _q	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
C _{max}	14.84	10.74	13.46	15.12	14.27	13.19	14.67	14.68	14.82	9.81	14.42	11.75	13.67	12.44	14.28	13.55	12.90	14.45	12.46	13.77
T _{zero}	2.94	2.32	2.94	2.95	2.32	2.95	2.95	1.45	2.94	2.94	2.38	1.46	2.95	2.94	2.31	2.31	1.46	2.32	2.95	2.32
K _s	1.00	0.19	0.21	0.20	0.18	0.21	0.19	0.18	0.99	1.00	0.18	0.18	0.19	0.19	0.18	0.16	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.99
C _{melt}	3.80	1.88	5.64	3.79	17.36	2.05	15.59	4.24	1.76	9.06	2.18	12.36	7.72	13.51	4.56	9.91	0.36	9.19	1.28	1.81
T _{melt}	-0.50	-0.83	-0.33	-0.50	-0.09	-0.94	-0.12	-0.26	-1.08	-0.21	-0.73	-0.09	-0.25	-0.14	-0.34	-0.16	-2.99	-0.17	-1.48	-0.87
B _{exp}	9.99	2.00	8.28	9.99	9.99	6.66	9.98	9.99	9.99	1.42	9.95	2.88	9.92	4.32	9.98	8.54	5.14	9.93	4.01	9.97
PET _{Corr}	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Alpha	0.03	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.10	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.09	0.06	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.03	0.01

Table 52: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Dischma catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K _q	0.16	1.00	0.16	1.00	0.13	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.17	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.16	0.17	0.15
C _{max}	1.19	1.09	1.23	1.03	1.18	1.74	1.46	1.37	1.20	3.41	1.69	1.28	1.88	2.41	1.18	1.56	1.29	1.21	4.33	2.27
T _{zero}	-1.66	-2.11	-1.66	-1.66	-2.14	-1.67	-1.66	-1.66	-1.66	-1.66	-1.66	-2.13	-1.67	-1.67	-1.65	-1.66	-1.65	-1.67	-1.66	-1.65
K _s	1.00	0.04	0.93	0.04	0.97	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	1.00	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.93	0.61	1.00
C _{melt}	1.84	4.00	1.92	4.00	9.05	2.20	1.85	2.73	2.08	1.79	2.99	3.60	1.82	1.87	2.87	2.03	3.38	1.89	1.93	2.30
T _{melt}	-0.45	0.95	-0.33	0.70	1.57	-0.03	-0.40	0.22	-0.25	-0.18	0.38	0.73	-0.32	-0.10	0.16	-0.25	0.36	-0.34	0.05	-0.07
B _{exp}	9.96	9.97	9.97	9.98	10.00	10.00	9.99	9.98	9.99	9.99	9.98	9.99	9.99	9.90	9.96	10.00	9.98	9.98	9.99	9.97
PET _{Corr}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Alpha	0.04	0.80	0.00	0.79	0.00	0.73	0.72	0.80	0.76	0.05	0.80	0.82	0.81	0.76	0.75	0.74	0.79	0.00	0.00	0.08

Table 53: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Lonza catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K_q	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.55	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.68	0.39
C_max	1.01	1.21	1.40	1.22	1.58	2.02	1.77	1.44	1.11	2.29	1.30	1.17	1.16	1.09	1.27	1.73	1.05	1.30	1.54	1.06
T_zero	1.91	-2.25	0.05	1.92	1.89	-2.25	-2.24	-2.24	-2.25	1.96	1.90	-2.24	-2.26	-2.25	-2.25	-2.49	-2.24	1.88	-2.25	-2.25
K_s	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.06	1.00	0.07	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.06	0.05	0.11	0.94
C_melt	1.37	1.45	1.35	1.24	1.28	1.17	1.34	1.49	1.47	1.12	1.23	1.52	1.58	1.76	1.68	2.03	1.68	1.25	1.27	1.55
T_melt	-2.77	-1.51	-2.68	-2.89	-2.71	-1.55	0.29	-0.37	-1.53	-2.93	-2.89	-1.47	-0.13	-0.50	0.26	1.49	-0.38	-2.81	0.41	0.76
B_exp	9.99	9.94	9.98	9.95	9.94	10.00	9.99	10.00	9.99	9.99	9.99	9.98	9.89	9.93	9.97	9.90	9.95	9.94	10.00	10.00
PET_Corr	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Alpha	0.64	0.69	0.67	0.59	0.58	0.51	0.16	0.58	0.69	0.51	0.58	0.70	0.62	0.68	0.64	0.64	0.69	0.54	0.01	0.01

Table 54: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Lütshine catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K_q	1.00	1.00	0.26	0.22	0.28	0.25	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.26	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.22
C_max	1.30	1.96	1.27	1.38	1.79	2.59	1.52	4.31	1.62	1.64	1.42	1.16	1.15	1.09	2.28	1.29	1.80	1.38	1.31	1.07
T_zero	-0.72	-0.72	-0.49	-0.71	-0.49	-0.72	-0.49	-0.71	-0.50	-0.47	-0.71	-0.72	-0.71	-0.49	-0.71	-0.49	-0.73	-0.72	-0.71	-0.49
K_s	0.07	0.07	1.00	1.00	0.93	0.99	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.06	1.00	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.99
C_melt	0.67	0.61	0.92	0.88	0.75	0.88	0.70	0.81	1.08	1.49	0.65	0.63	0.74	0.85	0.88	1.05	0.89	0.63	0.82	0.93
T_melt	-2.79	-3.00	-2.09	-2.12	-2.61	-2.14	-2.79	-2.29	-1.76	-1.30	-2.91	-3.00	-2.57	-2.31	-2.12	-1.84	-2.07	-3.00	-2.31	-2.09
B_exp	9.97	9.99	9.97	9.84	9.98	9.93	9.99	9.99	9.97	9.97	10.00	9.99	9.97	9.93	9.78	9.95	9.99	9.97	9.98	9.98
PET_Corr	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Alpha	0.60	0.58	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.19	0.58	0.60	0.66	0.69	0.59	0.59	0.61	0.03	0.64	0.66	0.64	0.57	0.63	0.00

Table 55: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Massa catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K_q	0.97	0.99	0.20	0.92	0.16	0.23	0.63	0.26	0.99	0.18	0.94	0.94	0.31	0.96	0.13	0.20	0.18	0.15	0.96	0.15
C_max	1.25	1.76	1.14	1.97	2.31	1.13	1.10	1.26	1.08	1.47	1.54	1.00	1.62	1.08	2.18	1.06	1.05	1.54	2.46	1.11
T_zero	-1.70	-2.59	-2.98	-2.93	-2.95	-2.92	-2.08	-2.94	-2.94	-2.95	-2.45	-2.90	-2.50	-2.97	-2.94	-2.99	-2.94	-2.95	-2.34	-2.95
K_s	0.19	0.09	0.93	0.09	0.13	0.17	0.91	0.08	0.08	0.18	0.18	0.12	0.94	0.08	0.16	0.72	1.00	0.95	0.17	0.99
C_melt	2.28	2.31	4.02	3.49	14.51	3.02	1.99	14.44	4.52	5.45	1.74	2.54	2.69	4.27	17.22	3.92	4.94	10.57	2.18	9.30
T_melt	-1.45	-1.32	-0.73	-0.85	-0.20	-0.99	-1.60	-0.21	-0.66	-0.54	-1.77	-1.15	-1.14	-0.69	-0.17	-0.75	-0.60	-0.28	-1.43	-0.32
B_exp	9.55	9.93	9.80	9.95	9.79	8.89	9.67	9.97	9.77	9.75	9.30	9.38	9.88	9.68	9.92	9.99	9.65	9.05	9.94	9.67
PET_Corr	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Alpha	0.45	0.54	0.01	0.79	0.42	0.15	0.86	0.83	0.84	0.02	0.18	0.65	0.75	0.84	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.56	0.00

Table 56: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Rhône catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K _q	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.33	1.00	1.00	0.98	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.97	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
C _{max}	1.06	1.39	1.43	1.17	2.02	1.68	1.26	1.91	1.19	2.84	1.14	1.96	1.22	2.01	1.16	1.90	1.23	1.44	1.54	1.72
T _{zero}	-2.08	-2.07	-2.06	-2.06	1.65	-2.13	1.65	-2.07	-2.06	1.65	-2.28	-2.07	1.64	1.65	-2.13	1.63	1.65	1.64	-2.06	-2.06
K _s	0.08	0.11	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.87	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.08	0.11	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.09
C _{melt}	2.94	2.78	2.46	3.34	1.84	3.29	2.20	2.92	2.77	1.92	3.75	2.68	2.31	1.98	3.52	1.88	1.99	2.16	2.63	2.77
T _{melt}	0.71	0.94	-0.29	1.33	-2.34	1.66	-1.26	0.76	0.80	-2.06	2.29	0.85	-1.19	-1.92	2.32	-2.20	-1.95	-1.46	0.67	0.77
B _{exp}	10.00	9.88	10.00	9.98	9.97	9.93	10.00	9.99	9.97	9.82	10.00	9.90	9.94	9.94	9.98	9.94	9.98	9.99	9.99	9.90
PET _{Corr}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Alpha	0.57	0.46	0.48	0.65	0.44	0.56	0.00	0.58	0.49	0.54	0.59	0.38	0.57	0.50	0.45	0.46	0.45	0.52	0.40	0.48

Table 57: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Saltina catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K _q	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.07	0.10	0.11	0.09	1.00	0.08	0.09	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.07	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.09
C _{max}	1.56	2.01	1.75	1.17	2.02	2.22	2.09	2.58	1.08	1.57	3.46	1.45	1.64	4.76	1.08	1.63	1.20	1.53	1.02	1.38
T _{zero}	0.65	0.70	1.20	0.46	0.75	0.71	0.73	0.70	0.71	0.73	0.70	0.66	0.71	0.70	0.34	1.24	0.66	0.67	0.62	0.71
K _s	0.02	0.02	0.02	1.00	1.00	0.01	0.99	0.02	0.93	1.00	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	1.00	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.99
C _{melt}	1.90	4.73	1.47	9.06	0.61	6.16	1.74	2.02	1.48	1.06	1.99	4.04	3.22	1.57	9.20	1.69	1.77	2.12	4.30	0.67
T _{melt}	1.02	2.92	0.28	2.59	-2.97	2.68	0.28	1.67	-0.60	-1.16	1.74	2.39	2.02	1.45	2.62	0.57	0.92	1.44	2.48	-2.99
B _{exp}	6.78	10.00	7.87	4.87	8.80	9.98	9.97	9.92	4.49	6.09	9.99	6.17	7.24	9.96	4.59	7.38	5.09	6.62	4.60	5.25
PET _{Corr}	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.72	1.00	0.99	0.05	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00
Alpha	0.69	0.74	0.68	0.02	0.13	0.30	0.01	0.65	0.00	0.01	0.68	0.74	0.73	0.68	0.01	0.69	0.69	0.67	0.72	0.01

Table 58: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Sitter catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K _q	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
C _{max}	1.19	4.65	2.49	1.10	5.04	1.12	2.36	1.71	1.26	1.19	1.89	1.15	2.35	1.55	1.82	1.48	2.00	1.07	2.14	1.57
T _{zero}	-1.57	-1.53	-1.58	-1.57	-1.51	-1.58	-1.58	-1.58	-1.59	-1.57	-1.54	-1.58	-1.57	-1.58	-1.54	-1.55	-1.57	-1.58	-1.58	-1.56
K _s	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.10	0.12	0.08	0.10	0.13	0.08	1.00	0.10	0.08	1.00	1.00	0.10	0.09	0.99	0.98	0.10	0.98
C _{melt}	1.05	1.02	0.97	0.70	0.82	0.78	0.81	0.94	0.68	0.79	0.94	0.74	0.69	0.90	0.84	0.65	0.92	0.66	0.71	0.54
T _{melt}	1.97	1.75	1.59	-0.02	1.01	0.52	0.75	1.46	-0.11	0.91	1.49	0.18	0.36	1.32	1.05	-0.28	1.42	0.33	0.28	-0.60
B _{exp}	0.37	2.50	1.03	1.06	2.90	0.38	0.99	0.39	0.39	0.36	0.39	0.36	0.97	0.35	0.38	0.33	0.41	0.37	0.84	0.33
PET _{Corr}	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.98	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.98	1.00	0.96	1.00	1.00	1.00
Alpha	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.08	0.03	0.12	0.09	0.11	0.11	0.00	0.08	0.13	0.01	0.00	0.08	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00

Table 59: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Thur catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K_q	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
C_max	3.24	11.49	11.07	9.82	8.14	9.97	10.65	11.52	10.55	11.00	8.76	10.78	8.81	9.90	7.98	7.05	10.76	9.80	11.21	10.67
T_zero	-0.26	-0.09	-0.36	1.18	-0.04	-1.30	-0.00	-0.63	0.11	0.12	-0.41	0.10	-0.41	-0.11	0.83	-0.64	-0.42	0.01	1.18	0.83
K_s	0.20	0.45	0.20	0.20	0.21	0.20	0.21	0.20	0.22	0.21	0.22	0.21	0.21	0.20	0.00	0.22	0.20	0.22	0.22	0.24
C_melt	14.67	1.30	2.13	5.98	8.92	19.25	5.15	1.29	6.15	12.42	13.81	1.07	3.06	0.52	2.75	6.76	6.10	5.01	14.95	3.39
T_melt	2.26	-0.66	-0.32	-0.24	-0.10	-0.03	-0.15	-0.52	-0.15	-0.08	2.30	-1.02	-0.22	-1.80	-0.52	2.18	-0.11	-0.15	-0.10	-0.43
B_exp	0.66	9.99	9.98	5.60	2.14	6.01	9.97	10.00	6.09	9.99	10.00	10.00	2.89	5.47	9.99	2.72	9.99	5.17	9.99	9.98
PET_Corr	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Alpha	0.16	0.01	0.09	0.04	0.07	0.09	0.07	0.08	0.10	0.09	0.12	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.11	0.12	0.09	0.07	0.03	0.06

Table 60: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Ticino catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K_q	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.19	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.98	0.20	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.21	0.28
C_max	1.88	2.68	1.73	1.81	1.47	2.28	1.66	1.44	2.58	1.59	1.44	1.27	2.68	2.91	1.82	2.15	1.70	1.22	1.48	2.07
T_zero	0.07	0.07	-2.57	-2.58	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.08	0.06	-1.55	-1.54	0.08	-0.13	-0.14	0.08	0.07	0.06	0.07	-1.30	-0.51
K_s	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.99	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.97	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.99	1.00
C_melt	7.93	18.92	0.90	2.69	0.73	8.63	16.25	15.89	1.95	6.08	15.87	5.28	19.89	15.51	2.37	13.75	1.05	9.52	19.82	7.73
T_melt	-0.28	-0.12	0.10	2.62	-2.88	-0.26	-0.14	-0.14	-1.14	2.96	-0.01	-0.43	-0.11	-0.13	-0.93	-0.16	-2.12	-0.24	-0.02	-0.16
B_exp	1.76	2.56	9.99	10.00	1.31	2.01	1.52	1.35	2.27	9.98	9.97	1.28	2.51	2.97	1.64	1.95	1.60	1.23	7.11	1.67
PET_Corr	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.11	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00
Alpha	0.68	0.67	0.74	0.74	0.01	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.00	0.69	0.67	0.68	0.67	0.68	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.00	0.00

Table 61: Optimal parameter sets for HYMOD generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Venoge catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
K_q	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
C_max	11.50	16.10	11.71	12.46	14.86	14.45	14.42	16.58	14.02	15.51	14.27	15.01	14.08	17.14	14.44	14.66	15.71	14.62	15.65	15.44
T_zero	2.55	1.37	2.55	2.67	2.55	2.55	0.73	2.65	2.55	2.55	0.94	2.54	2.55	2.54	2.77	2.55	2.55	2.68	2.55	2.55
K_s	0.15	0.13	0.16	0.16	0.15	0.16	0.13	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.12	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.15	0.15	0.16
C_melt	0.44	0.31	0.68	0.53	0.47	19.98	16.37	5.46	0.44	4.60	0.18	3.67	8.29	0.63	14.98	10.27	0.71	0.63	0.51	5.59
T_melt	-2.98	-2.15	-2.05	-2.84	-2.99	-0.07	-0.04	-0.28	-2.99	-0.30	-2.99	-0.38	-0.17	-2.20	-0.10	-0.14	-1.94	-2.37	-2.74	-0.25
B_exp	1.93	9.99	2.10	2.67	8.66	6.50	6.87	10.00	5.21	9.98	6.09	9.81	5.49	9.99	6.39	7.41	9.99	7.19	9.99	10.00
PET_Corr	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.61	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Alpha	0.25	0.35	0.28	0.29	0.28	0.35	0.40	0.32	0.26	0.33	0.34	0.35	0.35	0.28	0.32	0.35	0.29	0.27	0.27	0.35

B.5 MOHYSE

Table 62: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Broye catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Pet_Coeff	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.74	1.72	1.73	1.91	1.73	1.99	1.72	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.72	1.72	2.00	1.89	1.74	1.73	2.00
Aet_Coeff	0.99	1.00	1.00	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.62	0.50	1.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.50	0.50	1.00	0.65	0.50	0.51	1.00
Melt_Factor	2.11	2.41	2.03	2.85	2.08	3.00	2.56	3.21	3.71	2.09	3.31	3.39	2.62	2.67	2.85	2.12	3.86	2.44	2.15	2.24
DD_Melt_Temp	-0.68	-0.59	-0.71	-0.47	-0.66	-0.45	-0.54	-0.42	-0.38	-0.64	-0.42	-0.42	-0.52	-0.51	-0.47	-0.66	-0.36	-0.55	-0.64	-0.63
Thickness_Topsoil	0.50	0.51	0.52	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.51	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Perc_Coeff_Topsoil	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02
Baseflow_Coeff_Topsoil	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.04
Baseflow_Coeff_Gwsoil	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.01	0.99	0.02	0.99	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.99	0.99	0.02	0.01	0.99	0.99	0.02
Gamma_Shape_Alpha	4.97	3.44	5.00	3.82	4.99	3.74	4.83	4.99	4.21	5.00	4.35	4.88	4.40	3.57	4.54	4.26	4.77	4.99	4.96	4.04
Gamma_Scale_Beta	5.94	4.77	5.91	3.36	4.23	3.31	5.12	4.28	5.33	4.24	5.46	5.83	5.48	3.22	3.81	5.37	4.99	4.51	4.34	5.22

Table 63: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Dischma catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Pet_Coeff	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Aet_Coeff	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Melt_Factor	2.76	2.34	3.37	2.00	2.00	2.79	2.00	2.01	2.00	2.00	2.01	2.43	2.01	2.01	2.83	2.00	3.41	2.00	2.61	3.37
DD_Melt_Temp	-0.33	-0.54	-0.14	-0.98	-1.00	-0.43	-1.09	-0.96	-1.12	-1.00	-0.98	-0.56	-0.98	-0.94	-0.55	-0.89	-0.11	-1.03	-0.29	-0.12
Thickness_Topsoil	0.53	0.54	0.52	0.57	0.54	0.54	0.53	0.51	0.55	0.57	0.51	0.57	0.51	1.15	0.51	0.54	0.54	4.24	0.52	0.50
Perc_Coeff_Topsoil	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99
Baseflow_Coeff_Topsoil	0.20	0.25	0.09	0.26	0.26	0.17	0.13	0.28	0.18	0.28	0.27	0.22	0.31	0.23	0.11	0.35	0.08	0.24	0.26	0.11
Baseflow_Coeff_Gwsoil	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04
Gamma_Shape_Alpha	2.02	1.77	4.81	3.37	4.42	1.72	4.92	4.92	1.14	3.94	4.98	1.17	2.67	0.82	4.99	2.50	3.62	4.70	3.76	4.29
Gamma_Scale_Beta	2.22	1.37	6.84	2.92	3.60	2.05	5.46	3.86	1.27	3.21	4.31	1.40	1.93	18.22	5.32	1.49	12.69	4.06	3.05	5.16

Table 64: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Lonza catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Pet.Coeff	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Aet.Coeff	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Melt.Factor	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.01	2.00	2.00	2.01
DD.Melt.Temp	-1.64	-1.65	-1.66	-1.63	-1.63	-1.64	-1.68	-1.67	-1.65	-1.63	-1.64	-1.68	-1.66	-1.66	-1.65	-1.63	-1.63	-1.63	-1.68	-1.57
Thickness.Topsoil	5.96	6.93	2.83	0.71	1.79	7.12	3.68	9.08	5.62	6.67	2.23	3.69	0.94	3.76	0.51	8.05	1.22	2.28	0.53	0.51
Perc.Coeff.Topsoil	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99
Baseflow.Coeff.Topsoil	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.99	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.17	0.18	0.16	0.17	0.17	0.17
Baseflow.Coeff.Gwsoil	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.99	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.05
Gamma.Shape.Alpha	0.52	4.85	4.38	2.23	2.98	3.59	1.23	1.10	4.94	4.71	4.56	3.15	1.31	3.24	0.62	2.20	4.90	2.05	2.08	0.66
Gamma.Scale.Beta	2.08	10.13	8.48	5.99	7.86	7.84	0.07	3.72	10.89	18.88	9.29	6.88	4.33	7.25	15.94	5.69	12.66	6.84	5.40	9.99

Table 65: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Lütshine catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Pet.Coeff	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Aet.Coeff	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Melt.Factor	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.01	2.02	2.00	2.00	2.01	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
DD.Melt.Temp	-1.06	-1.07	-1.07	-1.03	-1.07	-1.08	-1.05	-1.04	-1.01	-1.08	-1.06	-1.06	-1.07	-1.08	-1.08	-1.07	-1.02	-1.07	-1.08	-1.06
Thickness.Topsoil	3.82	0.55	0.75	6.45	7.29	0.86	7.53	6.48	4.01	2.25	8.87	5.83	6.28	6.18	3.15	3.82	7.44	8.45	1.73	0.64
Perc.Coeff.Topsoil	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.02	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99
Baseflow.Coeff.Topsoil	0.15	0.16	0.16	0.19	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.17	0.18	0.03	0.16	0.16	0.15	0.16	0.18	0.99	0.17	0.17	0.16	0.17
Baseflow.Coeff.Gwsoil	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.99	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.99	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Gamma.Shape.Alpha	4.81	4.63	3.09	0.53	2.23	3.55	4.66	2.42	2.42	4.35	3.28	3.31	2.68	2.52	2.12	0.98	4.54	3.42	1.64	2.23
Gamma.Scale.Beta	9.01	8.67	6.12	0.76	3.90	6.08	7.79	4.14	3.82	16.30	6.12	6.34	5.54	6.07	3.38	0.07	7.22	5.83	4.16	4.33

Table 66: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Massa catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Pet.Coeff	0.54	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.52	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Aet.Coeff	0.62	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.56	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.53	0.50	0.50	0.53	0.51	0.50	0.52	0.51	0.57	0.51
Melt.Factor	2.14	2.46	2.97	2.54	3.24	2.14	2.01	3.24	2.22	2.95	2.80	3.87	2.23	2.03	2.13	2.31	2.41	3.78	2.15	2.56
DD.Melt.Temp	-1.79	-1.55	-1.29	-1.50	-1.19	-1.80	-1.93	-1.19	-1.74	-1.29	-1.38	-1.00	-1.72	-1.88	-1.80	-1.66	-1.58	-1.02	-1.78	-1.49
Thickness.Topsoil	9.95	3.62	4.84	5.55	1.65	4.92	3.64	6.13	5.67	1.22	1.19	9.98	9.09	9.80	1.15	9.92	6.08	7.52	9.98	7.29
Perc.Coeff.Topsoil	0.96	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.99
Baseflow.Coeff.Topsoil	0.94	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.71	0.83	0.18	0.08	0.27	0.04	0.03	0.09	0.36	0.56	0.18	0.38	0.26	0.07	0.38	0.06
Baseflow.Coeff.Gwsoil	0.15	0.13	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.12	0.19	0.11	0.12	0.15	0.11	0.09	0.12	0.17	0.18	0.13	0.13	0.09	0.19	0.13
Gamma.Shape.Alpha	1.08	0.81	3.44	3.66	1.76	2.11	1.29	3.81	4.30	1.28	2.25	3.41	4.16	1.73	2.95	4.36	3.83	3.32	2.19	1.95
Gamma.Scale.Beta	0.24	10.37	4.59	6.19	0.27	0.87	1.55	4.16	4.76	11.93	19.70	3.62	4.13	1.20	18.01	4.11	3.14	4.42	1.11	14.93

Table 67: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Rhône catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Pet.Coeff	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Aet.Coeff	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Melt.Factor	2.11	2.17	2.13	2.09	2.07	2.06	2.06	2.15	2.11	2.11	2.29	2.14	2.05	2.12	2.34	2.13	2.18	2.10	2.10	2.22
DD.Melt.Temp	-1.36	-1.23	-1.31	-1.33	-1.46	-1.45	-1.45	-1.26	-1.32	-1.36	-1.11	-1.45	-1.50	-1.32	-1.21	-1.34	-1.23	-1.37	-1.30	-1.10
Thickness.Topsoil	0.55	0.77	0.59	0.50	0.60	0.60	7.52	0.53	0.54	0.55	5.56	0.63	0.56	0.93	5.52	0.51	6.25	0.52	0.53	5.02
Perc.Coeff.Topsoil	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99
Baseflow.Coeff.Topsoil	0.48	0.45	0.48	0.48	0.50	0.51	0.64	0.50	0.51	0.48	0.99	0.45	0.52	0.49	0.99	0.45	0.99	0.50	0.51	0.99
Baseflow.Coeff.Gwsoil	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.98	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.91	0.08	0.98	0.07	0.07	0.98
Gamma.Shape.Alpha	4.85	3.56	4.91	2.90	2.80	1.37	0.51	2.54	3.03	2.86	0.73	4.62	1.69	4.86	0.52	2.48	0.56	2.48	3.07	1.17
Gamma.Scale.Beta	5.20	4.07	5.54	3.84	3.14	1.74	0.28	2.59	3.37	3.47	0.09	4.92	1.90	5.22	0.05	3.38	0.08	2.54	3.79	0.16

Table 68: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Saltina catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Pet.Coeff	1.65	1.25	1.23	1.60	1.38	1.45	1.34	1.30	1.54	1.46	1.47	2.00	1.69	1.40	1.38	1.07	1.49	1.56	1.62	1.58
Aet.Coeff	0.66	0.51	0.80	0.64	0.50	0.50	0.89	0.61	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.73	0.77	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.93	0.55
Melt.Factor	2.43	2.80	2.44	2.56	2.78	2.04	2.57	2.27	2.83	2.72	2.37	2.47	2.68	2.33	2.32	3.36	2.53	2.53	2.14	2.59
DD.Melt.Temp	2.18	2.57	2.33	2.38	2.51	1.77	2.40	2.11	2.61	2.54	2.25	2.28	2.46	2.20	2.09	2.66	2.49	2.33	1.93	2.53
Thickness.Topsoil	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.52	0.50	0.51	0.52	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.51	0.53	0.51	0.51	0.50	0.52	0.50	0.53	0.54
Perc.Coeff.Topsoil	0.69	0.31	0.35	0.66	0.40	0.51	0.44	0.40	0.56	0.49	0.52	0.80	0.67	0.50	0.49	0.19	0.54	0.59	0.74	0.62
Baseflow.Coeff.Topsoil	0.20	0.10	0.12	0.20	0.12	0.16	0.14	0.13	0.16	0.15	0.16	0.22	0.19	0.16	0.15	0.05	0.17	0.17	0.22	0.19
Baseflow.Coeff.Gwsoil	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01
Gamma.Shape.Alpha	4.92	1.79	1.44	2.67	1.22	4.25	3.13	2.57	3.13	2.42	3.06	4.85	2.51	4.19	4.99	2.23	4.22	2.97	4.96	3.76
Gamma.Scale.Beta	5.45	11.98	19.19	2.97	13.30	5.51	5.23	4.65	4.50	3.82	4.09	4.55	2.78	5.34	6.72	10.88	5.44	4.33	4.78	4.33

Table 69: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Sitter catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Pet.Coeff	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Aet.Coeff	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.96	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.94	1.00	1.00	1.00
Melt.Factor	2.00	3.04	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.01	2.03	2.04	2.03	2.00	2.97	2.00	2.00	2.01	2.00	2.00	2.01	2.01	2.06
DD.Melt.Temp	1.52	2.60	1.32	1.34	1.49	1.52	1.47	1.58	1.61	1.57	1.52	2.53	1.50	1.53	1.54	1.17	1.53	1.49	1.54	1.64
Thickness.Topsoil	0.51	0.50	0.51	0.53	0.50	0.52	0.51	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.50
Perc.Coeff.Topsoil	0.23	0.22	0.21	0.22	0.21	0.23	0.22	0.25	0.24	0.22	0.23	0.21	0.21	0.22	0.21	0.21	0.23	0.22	0.22	0.22
Baseflow.Coeff.Topsoil	0.24	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.24	0.25	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.24	0.23
Baseflow.Coeff.Gwsoil	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07
Gamma.Shape.Alpha	4.99	3.50	2.88	1.45	0.59	4.89	4.46	2.45	4.97	2.66	4.99	0.94	1.65	4.38	4.37	0.88	3.40	2.36	1.05	2.22
Gamma.Scale.Beta	16.32	19.68	11.84	12.85	16.88	11.52	15.27	5.89	9.81	14.19	11.17	12.77	8.96	13.20	12.32	14.17	8.54	16.05	12.85	13.24

Table 70: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Thur catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	
Pet_Coeff	2.00	1.99	1.98	2.00	2.00	1.67	1.66	2.00	1.96	1.67	2.00	1.93	1.81	1.67	1.66	1.95	1.67	1.67	2.00	1.97	
Aet_Coeff	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Melt_Factor	3.75	2.33	3.74	3.16	3.31	2.12	2.44	2.32	2.71	2.77	2.99	3.94	3.19	2.37	3.82	3.71	3.07	2.78	2.96	3.03	
DD_Melt_Temp	-0.28	-0.48	-0.28	-0.34	-0.32	-0.55	-0.47	-0.49	-0.39	-0.42	-0.35	-0.25	-0.33	-0.48	-0.27	-0.28	-0.37	-0.41	-0.36	-0.35	
Thickness_Topsoil	0.50	0.53	0.54	0.53	0.50	0.53	0.50	0.51	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.52	0.50	0.50	0.52	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.54	
Perc_Coeff_Topsoil	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.03	0.09	0.08	0.01	0.09	0.06	0.04	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.02	0.09	0.07	
Baseflow_Coeff_Topsoil	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.03	0.05	0.13	0.12	0.07	0.13	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.01	0.07	0.13	0.12	
Baseflow_Coeff_Gwsoil	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.99	0.99	0.05	0.04	0.99	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.99	0.99	0.03	0.99	0.99	0.04	0.04	
Gamma_Shape_Alpha	4.99	4.97	4.99	2.73	4.28	3.45	4.99	4.50	4.84	5.00	4.89	4.47	4.04	3.68	5.00	5.00	3.48	3.54	3.33	4.99	
Gamma_Scale_Beta	4.00	3.77	3.94	2.07	3.26	3.17	4.33	3.43	3.86	4.35	3.89	3.83	3.47	3.29	4.35	3.98	3.18	3.21	2.43	3.96	

Table 71: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Ticino catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Pet_Coeff	1.28	2.00	2.00	1.99	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.99	2.00	1.16	2.00	2.00	1.29	1.17	2.00	2.00	1.28	1.99	1.28	2.00
Aet_Coeff	0.85	0.50	0.50	0.52	0.50	0.50	0.74	0.66	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.99	0.51	0.50	0.98	1.00	0.50	1.00	0.50
Melt_Factor	2.22	3.25	3.96	3.65	3.30	2.18	3.65	2.33	3.67	2.21	2.37	3.56	2.70	3.40	3.99	3.53	3.45	2.64	3.17	3.72
DD_Melt_Temp	-1.03	-0.70	-0.58	-0.62	-0.69	-1.05	-0.62	-0.98	-0.62	-1.03	-0.97	-0.64	-0.84	-0.67	-0.56	-0.63	-0.66	-0.87	-0.72	-0.61
Thickness_Topsoil	0.51	0.52	0.50	0.52	0.51	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.61	0.52	0.53	0.51	0.66	0.53	0.51	0.51	0.52	0.50	0.50
Perc_Coeff_Topsoil	0.10	0.55	0.55	0.56	0.55	0.54	0.61	0.62	0.54	0.01	0.55	0.54	0.11	0.02	0.54	0.55	0.11	0.54	0.12	0.54
Baseflow_Coeff_Topsoil	0.04	0.11	0.13	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.20	0.13	0.13	0.01	0.12	0.14	0.05	0.01	0.13	0.50	0.04	0.12	0.05	0.13
Baseflow_Coeff_Gwsoil	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.89	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.95	0.03	0.99	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
Gamma_Shape_Alpha	4.22	4.81	4.51	2.60	1.66	4.54	0.65	4.07	3.45	2.23	4.62	1.92	2.57	3.42	3.41	0.99	4.76	3.96	0.99	2.12
Gamma_Scale_Beta	8.10	5.00	4.28	2.22	1.48	4.25	0.26	3.64	3.20	1.66	4.66	1.65	5.34	2.81	3.11	0.04	9.83	3.80	2.30	1.82

Table 72: Optimal parameter sets for MOHYSE generated with a computational budget of 5000 for the Venoge catchment. Column names have been abbreviated. Full random seed number consist of prefix 1699349 plus column title, e.g. 1699349089

Parameter	089	090	091	092	093	094	095	096	097	098	099	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Pet_Coeff	1.89	1.90	1.88	1.76	1.82	1.85	1.86	1.83	1.82	1.82	1.82	1.89	1.83	1.88	1.90	1.82	1.87	1.83	1.88	1.83
Aet_Coeff	1.00	1.00	0.96	0.77	0.57	1.00	1.00	0.50	0.62	0.79	0.56	1.00	0.90	1.00	1.00	0.84	0.99	0.51	0.99	0.85
Melt_Factor	2.01	2.39	2.01	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.01	2.30	2.00	2.80	2.02	2.01	3.09	2.00	2.56	2.04	2.25	2.01	3.11
DD_Melt_Temp	5.00	-0.19	-0.31	4.96	-0.23	4.98	-0.43	-0.22	-0.19	-0.23	-0.16	-0.27	-0.24	-0.23	-0.24	-0.17	5.00	-0.20	-0.26	-0.14
Thickness_Topsoil	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.52	0.50	0.51	0.52	0.52	0.50	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.54	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.51
Perc_Coeff_Topsoil	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Baseflow_Coeff_Topsoil	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02
Baseflow_Coeff_Gwsoil	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.99	0.98	0.03	0.03	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.03	0.99	0.03	0.02	0.99	0.02	0.99	0.02	0.98
Gamma_Shape_Alpha	5.00	3.63	3.63	4.98	4.96	3.35	4.55	3.71	3.63	5.00	4.27	3.90	2.78	5.00	4.96	4.99	3.09	4.95	3.95	4.97
Gamma_Scale_Beta	3.62	2.44	2.33	3.32	3.27	2.33	3.05	2.48	2.40	3.39	2.80	2.56	1.81	3.28	3.35	3.28	2.28	3.29	2.49	3.36

Declaration of consent

on the basis of Article 30 of the RSL Phil.-nat. 18

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Bachelor Master Dissertation

Title of the thesis: The Raven Hydrological Modelling Framework - Simulating Runoff in a Swiss context

Supervisor: Dr. Pascal Horton
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